
Seismic stability analysis of circular tunnels in soils under harmonic excitation

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Certificate

It is certified that the work contained in this thesis entitled "Seismic stability analysis of circular tunnels in soils under harmonic excitation" by "Gowtham G" has been carried out under my supervision and that it has not been submitted elsewhere for a degree.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "J. Sahoo".

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Declaration

This is to certify that the thesis titled “**Seismic stability analysis of circular tunnels in soils under harmonic excitation**” has been authored by me. It presents the research conducted by me under the supervision of **Dr. Jagdish Prasad Sahoo**.

To the best of my knowledge, it is an original work, both in terms of research content and narrative, and has not been submitted elsewhere, in part or in full, for a degree. Further, due credit has been attributed to the relevant state-of-the-art and collaborations (if any) with appropriate citations and acknowledgments, in line with established norms and practices.

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Abstract

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The stability of a tunnel involves assessing the stresses experienced by the tunnel support systems under the action of various driving forces causing its collapse such as earthquakes. Literature reports that the influence of surrounding soil's inertia on the seismic tunnel response is more substantial than structure's inertia during earthquakes. Numerous studies available on the seismic tunnel response relate to ground deformation, amplification of seismic waves, and lining displacements and forces for given lining properties. The magnitude of ultimate stress that the surrounding soil offers onto the tunnel periphery depends on many factors, like soil type, tunnel cover depth, magnitude and phase of seismic accelerations, etc. Very limited studies report the support pressure requirement of tunnels based on stresses imposed by the surrounding soil under seismic loadings employing pseudo-static approach without considering the effect of vertical seismic acceleration; however, seismic accelerations vary in space and time.

In the present thesis, the seismic stability analysis of circular tunnels has been performed considering the effect of (i) soil type – cohesive-frictional and granular soils, (ii)

ground surcharge and friction angle's anisotropy, (iii) interference in piggyback dual tunnels, and (iv) heterogeneity in the wave velocities propagation. Spatiotemporal horizontal and vertical seismic accelerations due to shear and primary wave propagation caused by harmonic base shaking have been used. The tunnel support systems are expected to resist the maximum normal stress imposed by the surrounding medium at its ultimate collapse, which has been reported as the support pressure in the present study. The stability analysis is done using the finite element limit analysis, the lower bound approach, which discretizes the soil domain to triangular elements containing three nodes and each containing three unknown stresses. The soil is assumed to follow the plane-strain Mohr-Coulomb yield criterion with an associative flow rule. The soil has been considered dry with its properties assumed invariant with seismicity. All computations in the present thesis have been performed using self-written MATLAB (2022) codes, and MOSEK (2022) toolbox has been used for optimization.

The variation of support pressure for tunnels in cohesive-frictional soils in the dimensionless frequency-time domain indicated that the influence of shear waves is prominent when the magnitude of soil cohesion is low, and vice versa. In general, support pressure increases with an increase in horizontal acceleration coefficient, and a decrease in soil friction angle and cohesion. The influence of horizontal acceleration coefficient is lower for tunnels in soils with a high cohesion. Furthermore, for tunnels in soils with a high cohesion and low friction angle, as the tunnel cover depth increases, the normal stress distribution tends to be uniform around the periphery. The normal stress magnitude around the tunnel periphery increases for a decrease in soil cohesion and friction angle.

The influence of ground surcharge and friction angle's anisotropy has been studied on the seismic stability of circular tunnels in granular soils. The anisotropy in soil friction angle has been accounted for using an equivalent friction angle, which is a function of the maximum friction angle and anisotropy ratio. For any tunnel cover depth, the support pressure for tunnels in soils with a low equivalent friction angle is predominantly

affected by shear waves. For a higher equivalent friction angle, the support pressure is affected by shear and primary waves for tunnels with a lower and higher cover, respectively. The magnitude of ground surcharge is insignificant for tunnels placed at a cover depth-to-diameter ratio greater than 3. The support pressure for tunnels placed at a larger cover depth is not affected by seismicity. From a comparative analysis between tunnels in cohesive-frictional and granular soils, the influence of shear waves on the support pressure decreases and that of primary waves increases with the magnitude of soil cohesion. As the magnitude of soil cohesion increases, the collapse pattern tends to be symmetrical around the tunnel periphery, indicating the reduced influence of horizontal seismic acceleration.

The interaction effect between top and bottom tunnels in piggyback configuration have been observed by varying their center-to-center distance. From the variation of support pressure for top and bottom tunnels in the dimensionless frequency-time space, it has been found that shear waves influence the seismic stability when soil friction angle is low. Compared to the top tunnel, bottom tunnel's support pressure is less sensitive to changes in the horizontal acceleration coefficient. For any tunnel cover depth, horizontal acceleration coefficient and soil friction angle, there exists a critical separation distance till which the support pressure for bottom tunnel is higher than the top, and it plummets thereafter. The collapse patterns indicate a unified soil collapse around tunnels with a low separation distance, and an independent pattern evolves with an increasing spacing between top and bottom tunnels. The magnitude of normal stress is significant near the invert and crown for top and bottom tunnels, respectively, when they are placed close to each other.

Since the above investigations considered wave velocity to be constant with depth, an attempt has been made to study the influence of the wave velocity's heterogeneity on the seismic tunnel stability in isotropic granular soils. The depth-dependent shear and primary wave velocities were modeled using a generalized power-law function. Analytical expressions for spatiotemporal horizontal and vertical seismic accelerations were derived by satisfying the boundary conditions on the ground surface and the base. These have been

applied to study the influence of inhomogeneous wave velocities on the support pressure variation. For a given value of the dimensionless shear wave frequency, the support pressure increases with an increase in the power parameter (n) and horizontal acceleration coefficient, and a decrease in soil friction angle, and wave velocity ratio, V_0/V_H (ratio of wave velocity at the ground surface to base). For a given combination of V_0/V_H and n , the support pressure increases when the selected frequency is closer to the corresponding fundamental frequency. Given the values of other input parameters, the region of soil collapse increases with the power parameter, and this is evident for a lower wave velocity ratio.

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Symbols

$\underline{\mathbf{A}}$	global matrix containing coefficients of all constraints
\mathbf{A}_{bc}^{bd}	coefficient matrix for stress boundary conditions
\mathbf{A}_{dc}^d	coefficient matrix for statically admissible stress discontinuity conditions
\mathbf{A}_{eq}^e	coefficient matrix for element equilibrium
\mathbf{A}_{int}^t	coefficient matrix for soil-tunnel lining interface constraints
\mathbf{A}_{yield}^i	coefficient matrix for the second-order cone formulation of the yield criterion
$a_h(z, t)$	horizontal seismic acceleration along depth and time
$a_r(z, t)$	magnitude of the resultant acceleration along depth and time
$a_v(z, t)$	vertical seismic acceleration along depth and time
\mathcal{A}_h	depth-dependent horizontal seismic acceleration amplitude
\mathcal{A}_v	depth-dependent vertical seismic acceleration amplitude
\mathcal{A}^e	area of an element
\mathbf{B}_l	global vector of lower bound values of constraints
\mathbf{B}_u	global vector of upper bound values of constraints
\mathbf{b}_{bc}^{bd}	vector of constants associated with stress boundary conditions
\mathbf{b}_{dc}^d	vector of constants associated with statically admissible stress discontinuity
\mathbf{b}_{eq}^e	vector of constants associated with element equilibrium
\mathbf{b}_{int}^t	vector of constants associated with soil-tunnel lining interface constraints
\mathbf{b}_{yield}^i	vector of constants for the second-order cone formulation of the yield criterion
\mathbf{b}_l	lower bound for independent variables
\mathbf{b}_u	upper bound for independent variables
b_x	body force per unit volume for an element along X-axis
b_z	body force per unit volume for an element along Z-axis
C	tunnel cover
c	soil cohesion
\mathbf{c}	global matrix of constraints corresponding to the objective function

c_{na}	modified soil cohesion accounting for the dilatancy angle
c_a	soil-tunnel lining interface adhesion
D	tunnel diameter
\mathcal{F}_h	horizontal amplification ratio
\mathcal{F}_v	vertical amplification ratio
g	acceleration due to gravity
H	total depth of the domain
k_h	coefficient of seismic acceleration in the horizontal direction
k_v	coefficient of seismic acceleration in the vertical direction
\mathcal{L}^3	Lorentz cone or the second-order cone
m	anisotropy ratio for anisotropic granular soil
N	total number of nodes in the domain
N_t	number of nodes along the tunnel periphery
n	power parameter for heterogeneous wave velocities
Q	collapse load magnitude per unit length of the tunnel
RI	region of infeasibility
S	center-to-center separation distance between top and bottom tunnels corresponding to piggyback dual tunnels
$\mathcal{S}_p^{V_0/V_H}$	set of primary wave fundamental frequencies for a given wave velocity ratio
$\mathcal{S}_s^{V_0/V_H}$	set of shear wave fundamental frequencies for a given wave velocity ratio
TF_h	transfer function for the horizontal acceleration
TF_v	transfer function for the vertical acceleration
T_p	period of excitation for primary waves
T_s	period of excitation for shear waves
t	time
V_p	propagation velocity of primary waves for homogeneous condition
V_s	propagation velocity of shear waves for homogeneous condition
V_{p0}	primary wave velocity at the ground surface
V_{pH}	primary wave velocity at the base
V_{s0}	shear wave velocity at the ground surface
V_{sH}	shear wave velocity at the base
V_0/V_H	ratio of wave velocity at the ground surface to base
z	depth from the ground surface
γ	soil's unit weight

Δ_{k_h}	absolute percentage difference in support pressure for the change in horizontal acceleration coefficient
Δ_m	absolute percentage difference in support pressure to the change in anisotropy ratio
Δ_n	absolute percentage difference in the support pressure for the change in power parameter
$\Delta_{q/\gamma D}$	absolute percentage difference in support pressure for the change in ground surcharge magnitude
$\Delta_{S/D}$	absolute percentage difference in support pressure, for piggyback dual tunnels, due to the change in separation distance
Δ_{V_0/V_H}	absolute percentage difference in the support pressure for the change in wave velocity ratio
$\Delta_{\gamma D/c}$	absolute percentage difference in support pressure for the change in $\gamma D/c$
Δ_ϕ	absolute percentage difference in support pressure for the change in soil friction angle
Δ_{ϕ_1}	absolute percentage difference in support pressure for the change in maximum soil friction angle
δ	friction angle along the soil-tunnel lining interface
ε_{S-P}	ratio of peak support pressures near the fundamental frequency of shear and primary waves corresponding to single tunnels
ε_{S-P}^1	ratio of peak support pressures near the fundamental frequency of shear and primary waves for the top tunnel in piggyback dual tunnels
ε_{S-P}^2	ratio of peak support pressures near the fundamental frequency of shear and primary waves for the bottom tunnel in piggyback dual tunnels
Θ	angle of discontinuity with the positive X-axis
θ	angle made by radial lines from tunnel center to nodes along the tunnel periphery with respect to positive X-axis
$\vartheta(z, t)$	direction of the resultant acceleration along depth and time
ξ_p	damping ratio for primary wave propagation
ξ_s	damping ratio for shear wave propagation
σ	global vector of stress unknowns in the domain
σ_n	normal stress
σ_s	support pressure for tunnels (single tunnel case)
σ_{s_1}	support pressure for the top tunnel to piggyback dual tunnels

σ_{s_2}	support pressure for the bottom tunnel to piggyback dual tunnels
σ_x	normal stress on the X plane
σ_z	normal stress on the Z plane
τ	shear stress
τ_{xz}	shear stress on the X/Z plane
ϕ	internal friction angle of soil
ϕ_{na}	modified soil friction angle accounting for the dilatancy angle
ϕ_1	maximum value of friction angle for the direction of deviator stress parallel to the direction of soil deposition or perpendicular to the bedding plane, that is, in the vertical direction
ϕ_2	minimum value of friction angle for the direction of deviator stress perpendicular to the direction of soil deposition or parallel to the bedding plane, that is, in the horizontal direction
χ	vector of auxiliary variables for conic constraints
ψ	dilation angle
ω_p	angular frequency of primary waves
ω_s	angular frequency of shear waves

List of Publications

Publications from the research work conducted at IIT Kanpur.

PhD:

1. **Gowtham, G.**, and Sahoo, J.P. (2024). Stability analysis of circular tunnels using spatiotemporal accelerations formulated considering heterogeneity of seismic wave propagation velocities. *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, 181. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soildyn.2024.108654>
2. **Gowtham, G.**, and Sahoo, J.P. (2024). Seismic stability of circular tunnels in anisotropic granular soil with surcharge loading based on the modified pseudo-dynamic approach. *International Journal of Geomechanics, ASCE*, 24(5). <https://doi.org/10.1061/IJGNALGMENG-9293>
3. Sahoo, J. P., and **Gowtham, G.** (2023). Stability evaluation of circular tunnels in cohesive frictional soil under earthquake loading using the modified pseudo-dynamic approach. *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, 166. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soildyn.2022.107740>
4. **Gowtham, G.**, and Sahoo, J.P. Seismic active earth pressure of granular soils considering inhomogeneous wave velocities under harmonic excitation. *Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering, ASCE*. Under review
5. **Gowtham, G.**, and Sahoo, J.P. Effect of seismic body wave propagation on the stability of piggyback twin circular tunnels. *Journal of Earthquake Engineering*. Under review
6. **Gowtham, G.**, and Sahoo, J.P. Modified pseudo-dynamic analysis for assessing stability of circular tunnels in granular soils under seismic conditions. *Tunnelling and Underground Space Technology*. Under review

MTech:

1. **Gowtham, G.**, and Sahoo, J.P. (2024). Seismic stability analysis of square and rectangular tunnels in cohesive-frictional soils. *Natural Hazards Review, ASCE*, 25(3). <https://doi.org/10.1061/NHREFO.NHENG-1955>
2. **Gowtham, G.**, and Sahoo, J.P. (2023). Stability of square and rectangular tunnels in sand under seismic loading. *Natural Hazards*, 119, 1863–1881. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-023-06188-3>

1

Introduction

1.1 General

According to the Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs, Government of India, as of 2011, around 377 million Indians live in urban areas, and it is predicted that, by 2036, this number will rise to 400 million, or about 40% of India's population will be urbanized (Kouamé, 2024). Catering to this burgeoning trend of an urbanizing India is important as these urban spaces contribute substantially to the country's GDP. It is estimated that India needs to spend an average of 1.2% of its GDP annually to meet the infrastructure needs of 2036 (Kouamé, 2024). Thus, there is an increasing need for excellent infrastructure in urban spaces that could drive the nation's vision of becoming a developed country. Out of many facets of urban development, a sizable investment is required to meet the infrastructure needs of seamless transportation in cities. This is followed by the need for provision of water and sewerage systems. Furthermore, there is an increasing demand for space above the ground surface, making the use of underground space vital in terms of urban tunnels. Therefore, ensuring the stability of such underground tunnels is of utmost importance for engineers to provide uninterrupted access to people. Nowadays, tunneling

through complicated urban spaces is possible owing to the limited disturbance caused by tunnel boring machines to the surrounding soil. The stability assessment of tunnels placed in soils is two folds - *face* and *peripheral* stability. The soil collapse at the advancing face of tunnel is prevented using compressed air or applying pressurized bentonite slurry. On the other hand, the soil collapse along the tunnel periphery is avoided by support systems in the form of precast concrete or steel liners. Therefore, peripheral stability is ensured by tunnel lining systems where the minimum support pressure offered by them should be greater than or equal to the maximum stress magnitude imposed by the surrounding soil at impending state of collapse. Various ground and loading conditions such as soil type, tunnel cover depth, ground surcharge magnitude, and earthquake forces influence the stress magnitude that will be imposed on the tunnel periphery. The present thesis focuses on the peripheral stability assessment of single and piggyback dual circular tunnels in cohesive-frictional and granular soils subjected to seismic loadings, which has been considered to arise due to harmonic base shaking in horizontal and vertical directions.

The problems of soil mechanics are of two types - stability and elasticity problems. The stability problem involves finding the collapse load causing ultimate failure of the soil mass, whereas elasticity problems find stress or deformation when there is no failure. As stated before, problems dealt with in the present thesis fall under the realm of "stability problems" involving collapse load computations. Several methods are available to solve a stability problem - the slip line method, limit equilibrium method, limit analysis, and numerical methods. The slip line method involves solving a set of governing equations for plastic equilibrium consisting of stress equilibrium equations, yield criterion, and stress boundary conditions. The above-said system of equations is simplified by introducing a new coordinate system that coincides with the potential failure surfaces. These failure surfaces, appearing as lines in two-dimensions, are called *slip lines*. The major pitfall of the slip line method is the negligence of stress-strain relationship of soils,

which should be satisfied for a valid solution. Furthermore, the stress field developed from this method is termed as a partial stress field as only a part of the soil is considered to be at a state of imminent collapse. The limit equilibrium method assumes a failure surface of simple geometries and solves the stability problem in order to find the vulnerable position of failure surface and the corresponding collapse load. However, none of the equations of solid mechanics is satisfied anywhere inside or outside of the assumed failure surface. Furthermore, the stress-strain relationship is also not taken into account. In general, limit analysis refers to finding solutions to stability problems applying the collapse load theorems - *lower bound* and *upper bound* theorem. Like the aforementioned methods, the lower bound theorem of limit analysis seeks a *statically admissible stress field* over the entire soil domain satisfying the stress equilibrium equations and boundary conditions, and not violating the yield criterion. On the other hand, the upper bound theorem of limit analysis computes the collapse load by equating the external work rate to the internal dissipation rate from a *kinematically admissible velocity field* satisfying the velocity boundary conditions, and strain-velocity compatibility equations. The collapse load estimates from lower and upper bound theorems bracket the actual collapse load as they are lower and higher than the true collapse load, respectively. Unlike the slip line and limit equilibrium methods, the stress-strain relationship of soil is considered in an idealized manner using the *normality condition or flow rule*, which renders limit analysis solutions to be rigorous. Further, the major advantage of limit analysis solutions is that the governing equations are satisfied everywhere within the soil domain. Stability problems can also be solved using any of the numerical methods like finite element method, finite difference technique, etc. However, these methods perform incremental analysis to establish the complete load-deformation behavior requiring very high computational rigor and time to arrive at the collapse load, depending on problem's complexity.

The collapse load from limit analysis is dependent on the stress or velocity field that has been initially assumed for the problem. Even though the collapse load computed from lower and upper bound theorems of limit analysis are unique, the stress field and collapse mechanism from these theorems are not. In other words, the same lower bound estimate can be obtained from different stress fields. Similarly, various kinematically admissible velocity fields might result in the same upper bound estimate of the collapse load. Thus, it is necessary to compute the best collapse load by assuming various stress fields and collapse mechanisms such that they provide the greatest lower bound and the least upper bound to the actual collapse load, respectively. Moreover, since soil is considered a continuum, governing conditions of the classical limit analysis need to be satisfied at infinite locations within the domain, which is cumbersome for problems with complicated geometry and loading conditions. In order to circumvent this problem, the soil continuum is discretized using any numerical procedure, and the governing conditions are satisfied at all the "points" of this "discrete domain". Thus evolved the new conjuncture between numerical methods and the classical limit analysis. Of the several numerical procedures, the finite element method has gained grounds to discretize the soil medium for the numerical application of limit theorems, which is known as the *finite element limit analysis*. The important advantage of using this coupled analysis is that it eliminates the assumption of a stress field or collapse mechanism. As stated before, the best lower and upper bound estimates are that which provides the greatest and least collapse load, respectively, conforming to corresponding governing conditions. Thus, the act of finding the best estimate gives itself to an optimization problem. Several studies are available, under the realm of finite element limit analysis application to soil mechanics, to solve the resultant optimization problem with the technique used ranging from that using primitive schemes like simplex/revised simplex algorithm to a more complex ones like the interior-point algorithm (Lysmer, 1970; Anderheggen and Knöpfel, 1972; Bottero et al., 1980; Sloan, 1988; Lyamin and Sloan, 2002; Makrodimopoulos and Martin, 2006; Krabbenhøft et al., 2007).

From the design point of view, the solutions obtained using the lower bound theorem of limit analysis remain always safe as the limit load computed by this method is smaller than or equal to the true collapse load. Thus, in the present thesis, the finite element approach in the framework of lower bound theorem of limit analysis was adopted to compute the support pressure required to maintain the stability of circular tunnels in cohesive-frictional and granular soils subjected to seismic loadings. The algorithm formulated by Sloan (1988) for finite element lower bound limit analysis is used along with the second-order cone programming optimization scheme given by Makrodimopoulos and Martin (2006) to find the greatest lower bound. The analysis was performed with the consideration that seismicity is induced within the domain due to harmonic base excitation along horizontal and vertical directions, which gives rise to spatiotemporal seismic accelerations in these directions. The support pressure is computed as the maximum normal stress obtained from the stress distribution around the tunnel periphery. All computations in the present thesis have been performed using self-written MATLAB (2022) codes, and the second-order cone programming is done using the MOSEK (2022) toolbox for MATLAB (2022).

1.2 Motivation for the present research

Having a prediction that around 1.66 billion Indians, around 52% of the population, will occupy urban spaces by 2050 (UN DESA, 2018), India is in need of efficient urban infrastructure to serve this demand. A growing urban population translates to an increasing shortage of space for infrastructure above the ground, demanding the use of underground spaces in the form of tunnels. Tunnels are useful not only for transport facilities but also other infrastructure projects like water/sewerage provisions. The peripheral stability of tunnels depends on the resistance of support systems in the form of linings against the

stresses that the surrounding soil imposes on the tunnel periphery. The stress magnitude is influenced by various factors such as soil condition (granular/cohesive-frictional), seismicity, ground surcharge magnitude, and presence of another tunnel, among others. Several field investigations in tunnel sites after an earthquake have revealed that lining failure is the major form of earthquake-induced tunnel damage (Sharma and Judd, 1991; Wang et al., 2001; Konagai et al., 2005; Lu and Hwang, 2008; Li, 2012; Yu et al., 2016; Roy and Sarkar, 2017). It has been established that the inertia of the surrounding soil is more than that of the tunnel; hence, the seismic response of underground tunnels is different than those over the ground (Okamoto and Tamura, 1972; Wang, 1993; Kawashima, 2006). Though many studies are available for evaluating the seismic response like ground deformation and amplification of seismic waves in the presence of tunnels along with lining forces and displacements, very limited studies have computed the support pressure requirement of tunnel linings. In the light of the above, the following sections discuss the need for the research work taken up in the present thesis.

1.2.1 Stability of single tunnels

Several studies are available for the seismic response of single tunnels assuming structural parameters of the lining (Lee and Trifunac, 1979; John and Zahrah, 1987; Sharma and Judd, 1991; Luco and Barros, 1994; Penzien and Wu, 1998; Pakbaz and Yareevand, 2005; Amorosi and Boldini, 2009; Pitilakis et al., 2014; Moghadam and Baziar, 2016; Cabangon et al., 2023). Sahoo and Kumar (2014) computed the support pressure based on stresses imposed by the surrounding soil for tunnels in cohesive-frictional soils under seismic loadings considering the horizontal pseudo-static forces. Apart from the ignorance of vertical seismic accelerations, the use of pseudo-static method renders the seismic accelerations invariant of time and space. A study is, therefore, needed to compute the support pressure required to be exerted by the lining along the tunnel periphery taking into account

of the effect of various ground conditions and forces imparted due to the propagation of seismic body waves by varying both magnitude and phase of earthquake accelerations in space and time.

1.2.2 Stability of dual tunnels

The topic of dual circular tunnels—parallel and piggyback—is a well-researched one. The presence of another tunnel adjacent to the available one is inevitable with the growing use of underground space. Because of this, the tunnel response is influenced by its interaction with the other tunnel, which had been widely studied under seismic loadings indicate that the tunnel response is highly influenced by the spacing between two tunnels (Balendra et al., 1984; Moore and Guan, 1996; Liang et al., 2003; Liu and Wang, 2012; Alielahi and Adampira, 2016; Liu et al., 2016; Lin et al., 2017; Tsinidis et al., 2016; Feizi et al., 2022). Most of the studies consider the stability of parallel tunnels (Liang et al., 2003; Liu and Wang, 2012; Alielahi and Adampira, 2016; Lin et al., 2017; Tsinidis, 2018). However, provision of piggyback dual tunnels might be indispensable due to space constraints in urban areas (Do et al., 2014; Liu et al., 2016; Do et al., 2022; Feizi et al., 2022). Nonetheless, all the studies mentioned above assumed liner properties to compute liner force, ground deformations and seismic wave amplification. Furthermore, all studies mentioned above analyzed the interaction of dual tunnels under the realm of elasticity. Therefore, stress states obtained from these approaches ignore the ultimate collapse of the surrounding soil conforming to a failure criterion, which is detrimental in designing the tunnel lining to withstand the stress imposed by soil at its ultimate failure state. Literature is abundant on the static stability of dual circular tunnels. Currently, no research is available to compute the support pressure for piggyback dual circular tunnels based on stresses imposed by the surrounding soil under seismic loadings, emphasizing the interaction effects and normal stress distribution around the periphery.

1.2.3 Heterogeneity in wave propagation velocities

The seminal work of Bellezza (2014, 2015) on shear and primary wave propagation in soils due to harmonic base excitation is a great advancement compared to the popular theories by Okabe (1926) and Mononobe and Matsuo (1929), i.e., the pseudo-static approach, and Steedman and Zeng (1990), i.e., the conventional pseudo-dynamic approach. However, one of the assumptions in the solutions of Bellezza (2014, 2015) is that wave propagation velocities of the medium are homogeneous or constant with depth. On the contrary, several analytical studies are available that take into account of inhomogeneous wave velocities under harmonic base excitation (Gazetas, 1982; Dakoulas and Gazetas, 1985; Vrettos, 1990; Towhata, 1996; Travasarou and Gazetas, 2004; Rovithis et al., 2011). These studies use a continuous fit to the actual discrete wave velocity profile of the soil, which is acceptable when there is no steep impedance difference between soil layers along with a gradual change in soil age and type (Towhata, 2008; Garcia-Suarez et al., 2021, 2022). Out of the different continuous functions discussed in these studies, the generalized power-law function used by Rovithis et al. (2011) is quite intriguing as it provides the most common variation of wave velocity with depth (Garcia-Suarez and Asimaki, 2020; Garcia-Suarez et al., 2021). In the light of the above, Rovithis et al. (2011) obtained the analytical solution for the horizontal displacement amplitude that varies in space. The solution is incomplete in the sense of the number of boundary conditions that have been applied, i.e., the solutions conform to the zero-traction boundary condition on the ground surface. Because of this, the solution of Rovithis et al. (2011) gives only the spatial variation of horizontal seismic acceleration. It is well known that seismic accelerations vary in both space and time. Therefore, there is a need for finding seismic accelerations, considering inhomogeneous wave velocities, that satisfy the stress boundary condition on the ground surface and displacement compatibility at the base. Furthermore, very few studies are available that examine the influence of inhomogeneity in wave velocities on

seismic response of circular tunnels (Amorosi and Boldini, 2009; Tsinidis et al., 2016; Abate et al., 2023). These studies not only assume liner parameters but also use very specific functions to characterize wave velocity heterogeneity, which cannot be generalized. Hence, a comprehensive study to analyze the normal stress magnitude along the tunnel periphery placed in soils with heterogeneous wave propagation velocities, characterized using a generalized power-law function, is required.

1.3 Objectives of the present research

The primary objective of the research taken up in this thesis is to perform a comprehensive investigation of seismic stability of circular tunnels, considering

- *Effect of soil type*: Single circular tunnels placed in cohesive-frictional and granular soils have been analyzed considering the influence of dimensionless frequencies of seismic waves, horizontal acceleration coefficient, tunnel cover depth, soil friction angle, and cohesion.
- *Effect of ground surcharge and friction angle's anisotropy*: The influence of the magnitude of ground surcharge and induced anisotropy of soil friction angle on the support pressure has been considered for tunnels placed in granular soils. A thorough parametric study has been conducted including other input parameters like horizontal acceleration coefficient, friction angle, and tunnel cover depth.
- *Piggyback dual tunnels*: The seismic stability of dual circular tunnels that are vertically separated but having a common centerline placed in granular soils has been considered. The influence of center-to-center distance between tunnels on the support pressure has been analyzed along with the effect of horizontal acceleration

coefficient, dimensionless frequencies of shear and primary waves, tunnel cover depth, and soil friction angle.

- *Heterogeneous wave velocities*: The seismic stability of single circular tunnels in granular soils with inhomogeneous wave velocities have been analyzed. The horizontal and vertical seismic accelerations have been derived conforming to all boundary conditions of the problem, which were then applied as body forces to compute the support pressure. The interplay of heterogeneity parameters of shear and primary wave velocities, horizontal acceleration coefficient, tunnel cover depth, dimensionless frequency, and soil friction angle has been considered.

1.4 Scope of the present research

The present thesis furnishes support pressure magnitudes under seismic loadings considering harmonic base excitation using the finite element lower bound limit analysis approach for different surrounding conditions. Solutions from the present study for the support pressure have been provided in the form of non-dimensional charts for the ready use by practicing engineers for determining the thickness and stiffness of lining based on the theory of thin and thick-walled cylinders.

The solutions/methodology provided in the thesis will be useful to:

- compute the support pressure for circular tunnels under different ground conditions and earthquake forces
- find the critical center-to-center separation distance between piggyback tunnels, for given combination of input parameters, beyond which the interference effect will be negligible

- estimate the type of seismic wave that governs the support pressure variation in the dimensionless frequency-time space
- determine the region of collapse around tunnel periphery for given input parameters
- visualize the variation of normal stresses over the tunnel periphery under static and seismic loadings
- analyze the stress distribution around tunnels and visualize the phenomenon of soil arching
- determine spatiotemporal horizontal and vertical seismic accelerations for soil with a heterogeneous wave velocity profile, which can be applied to any geotechnical problem

1.5 Organization of the thesis

The present thesis has been organized to eight chapters. The present chapter, Chapter 1, introduces the thesis with a brief review of the problems solved in this thesis along with discussing the need, objective and scope of the work carried out in the present thesis.

Chapter 2 provides a comprehensive discussion on the literature relevant to the current thesis. The literature corresponding to the stability of single and dual circular tunnels under static loadings has been discussed initially. This is followed by a discussion on the previous research on the seismic stability of single and dual circular tunnels under different soil conditions. Finally, important contributions in the field of finite element limit analysis using the lower bound approach are briefly discussed.

The detailed description of the finite element limit analysis, using the lower bound theorem, combined with the second-order cone programming is provided in Chapter 3.

This chapter discusses the formulation of constraint matrices and objective function, and the maximization of collapse load using the second-order cone programming.

Chapter 4 discusses the results of the analysis conducted on the maximum normal stress imposed by surrounding soil on the tunnel periphery for single circular tunnels placed in dry, isotropic, and homogeneous cohesive-frictional soils.

The seismic stability of single circular tunnels placed in dry and homogeneous granular soil with anisotropic friction angle has been discussed in Chapter 5, considering the influence of ground surcharge. This chapter also compares the seismic stability of tunnels in cohesive-frictional and granular soils.

Chapter 6 attempts to study the interference effect on the support pressure for piggy-back dual circular tunnels placed in dry, isotropic, and homogeneous granular soils and subjected to seismic body waves.

The influence of inhomogeneous wave propagation velocities of shear and primary waves on the seismic stability of single circular tunnels in dry and isotropic granular soils has been discussed in Chapter 7.

Chapter 8 lists important takeaways from the present research. It also explores the possible future enhancements that could be made to the present work.

2

Literature review

2.1 General

The behavior of underground structures, like tunnels, in soil and rock masses is a widely researched topic. Urban tunnel stability requires the analysis of the tunnel face and periphery. The peripheral stability is established by supporting structures in concrete or steel linings. The current research studies the ultimate normal stress to be withstood by the lining elements under the action of earthquake forces. Because of space constraints under the ground, the construction of dual tunnels is inevitable. The state-of-knowledge in the static stability analysis of single circular tunnels is quite exhaustive (Atkinson and Potts, 1977; Davis et al., 1980; Wu and Lee, 2003; Lee et al., 2006; Osman et al., 2006; Yamamoto et al., 2011; Sahoo and Kumar, 2019; Kumar and Sahoo, 2020) and dual (Kim et al., 1998; Addenbrooke and Potts, 2001; Chehade and Shahrour, 2008; Chen et al., 2011; Zhang et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2017; Sahoo and Kumar, 2018; Xiao et al., 2019a). These studies postulated the findings from a wide range of experimental and numerical methods. The studies on single tunnels have revealed the dependence of their stability on the material properties, cover depth, and the relative stiffness of the lining and the

medium. Similarly, the stability of dual tunnels under static conditions is influenced by the separation distance between them. In other words, the interaction effects influence the stability of dual tunnels. The underground tunnel response for a seismic event differs from the superstructures. As far as seismic stability of single tunnels is concerned, analytical (Lee and Trifunac, 1979; Luco and Barros, 1994; Penzien and Wu, 1998; Pakbaz and Yareevand, 2005), experimental (Cilingir and Madabhushi, 2011; Lanzano et al., 2012; Moghadam and Baziar, 2016), and numerical (Amorosi and Boldini, 2009; Baziar et al., 2014; Pitilakis et al., 2014; Sahoo and Kumar, 2014; Vo-Minh and Nguyen, 2022; Cabangon et al., 2023) solutions are available in the literature. These studies indicate the possible vulnerability of a shallow tunnel rather than a deep one due to the interaction of seismic waves between the ground surface and tunnel periphery. On the other hand, numerous studies are available on the seismic stability analysis of dual tunnels (Balendra et al., 1984; Moore and Guan, 1996; Liang et al., 2003; Liu and Wang, 2012; Alielahi and Adampira, 2016; Liu et al., 2016; Lin et al., 2017; Tsinidis, 2018; Zlatanović et al., 2021; Feizi et al., 2022). From these studies, it is inferred that seismic stability is greatly influenced by the spacing between the two tunnels and the frequency of seismic waves. Most of the studies listed above considered the medium to be isotropic in terms of its shear strength properties. Kumar and Sahoo (2020) pointed out that the friction angle's anisotropy affects the static stability of single tunnels in granular soils. Therefore, the soil anisotropy is expected to influence the support pressure required for seismic cases. Moreover, very few studies consider the inhomogeneity in the wave propagation velocities of the soil medium in assessing the seismic stability of single tunnels (Amorosi and Boldini, 2009; Tsinidis et al., 2016; Huang et al., 2020, 2021; Abate et al., 2023). Though many studies have been conducted, section 2.2 discusses the literature on the static stability of single and dual circular tunnels relevant to the present study. Similarly, section 2.3 details the literature on seismic stability.

The problem of seismic stability of single and dual circular tunnels has been solved in this thesis using the lower bound theorem of limit analysis in combination with finite elements and second-order cone programming. Using the lower bound theorem, the collapse load can be found analytically from a statically admissible stress field over the domain following the equilibrium conditions, traction boundary conditions, and not violating the yield criterion (Hill, 1951; Drucker and Prager, 1952; Drucker, 1953). For problems involving complex loading and geometries, finding an analytical solution for the stress field might become a herculean task. Because of the advent of advanced numerical methods and efficient solvers, the lower bound theorem of limit analysis has been combined with the finite element method, which discretizes the continuum into *finite elements* and solves the governing equations over this element (Bottero et al., 1980; Pastor and Turgeman, 1982; Sloan, 1988). The difficulty in solving the resultant optimization problem involving large sparse matrices using the linear programming approach (simplex or revised simplex method) has been overcome by the advent of efficient optimization methods involving interior point algorithms, such as the Second-Order Cone Programming (SOCP) (Makrodimopoulos and Martin, 2006; Krabbenhøft et al., 2007). Section 2.4 enlists articles that have become milestones in the history of the development of the *Finite Element Limit Analysis - Lower Bound approach*.

2.2 Literature on the static stability of circular tunnels

2.2.1 Single tunnels

2.2.1.1 Atkinson and Potts (1977)

The support pressure required for the stability of circular tunnels in granular soils with and without ground surcharge was studied by Atkinson and Potts (1977). The investigation was done using centrifuge testing and limit theorems. The experimental setup consisted of a tunnel model of 60 mm diameter placed in dry granular soil of internal friction angle 50° . The centrifuge was accelerated at 75g to simulate a tunnel collapse with a 4.5 m diameter. The lining was provided using a cylindrical rubber membrane, and the support pressure to the model was provided employing compressed air, bentonite slurry, and a shield. Initially, the support pressure equal to the vertical earth pressure at the placement depth was provided. Then, it was reduced successively until a sudden and well-defined collapse occurred. Lead shots were buried in sand, and their movement was monitored by photographing them. From these images, the collapse pattern around the tunnel was judged, which was further used for theoretical studies. The statically admissible stress states and kinematically admissible collapse patterns were formulated for granular soils, assuming the Mohr-Coulomb yield criterion.

2.2.1.2 Davis et al. (1980)

Davis et al. (1980) used the plasticity theorems to investigate the peripheral and face of stability circular tunnels in cohesive soils under plane strain conditions. The influence of ground surcharge on stability was also considered. As the tunnel cover depth increased, its

stability is reduced, indicated by a rising stability number. Furthermore, a higher support pressure requirement was reported for unlined tunnels than a circular tunnel heading.

2.2.1.3 Wu and Lee (2003)

A study of ground settlement due to unlined single and parallel tunnels in cohesive soils was carried out by Wu and Lee (2003) using centrifuge tests and theoretical upper-bound formulations. The centrifuge model tests were conducted for a tunnel of 60 mm diameter placed at different cover depths, and the setup was accelerated at 100 g to simulate the behavior of a 6 m diameter tunnel model at the same cover depth. The cohesive soil of undrained shear strength 30~40 kPa was used for the model tests. Similar to Atkinson and Potts (1977), the tunnel support was provided by air pressure to balance the vertical overburden stress at the tunnel's center. It was then reduced at a rate of 20 kPa/min till a sudden collapse. The ground settlement owing to tunnel failure was monitored using LVDTs, and the collapse pattern was identified using the displaced positions of spaghetti around the tunnel. Test results were fitted using the Gaussian curve and compared with twelve field measurements from Taipei and Japan. Kinematically admissible velocity fields, consisting of rigid sliding wedges, were derived from the experimental observation of soil movement and used to obtain an upper bound to the tunnel support pressure.

2.2.1.4 Lee et al. (2006)

Lee et al. (2006) extended the work of Wu and Lee (2003) to study the pore pressure distribution and tunnel arching effects for single and parallel tunnels. The experimental results of the settlement profile and excess pore pressure ratio ($\Delta u/\sigma_{v0}$; Δu is the excess pore pressure, and σ_{v0} is the overburden pressure at the tunnel center) from the centrifuge tests were used to validate the numerical study using the Fast Lagrangian Analysis of

Continua (FLAC). This numerical model was used to study the arching behavior of single and parallel tunnels. The effect of tunnel arching was studied considering the variation in the vertical stress distributions above the tunnel spring line. The arching was quantified using the arching ratio, $AF(\%) = \Delta\sigma_v/\sigma_{v0}$, which is the ratio of the change in the vertical stress due to tunneling ($\Delta\sigma_v$) and the vertical overburden pressure at the tunnel center (σ_{v0}). For both single and parallel tunnels, it was concluded that the arching ratio above the tunnel decreased with the cover depth, indicating a higher reduction in vertical stresses due to tunneling for deeper tunnels. It was also found that along the center of a single tunnel and the center of both the tunnels (twin case), the arching ratio was negative, implying that the elements along these locations transferred the load to the adjacent non-yielding elements.

2.2.1.5 Yamamoto et al. (2011)

The peripheral stability of an unlined single circular tunnel in a cohesive-frictional medium was analyzed theoretically and numerically by Yamamoto et al. (2011). The theoretical analysis was carried out using upper-bound rigid block collapse mechanisms, and the numerical study was done with the help of finite element limit analysis. Lower and upper bounds to the ultimate surcharge applied on the ground surface were published. A fast non-linear optimization scheme was used to solve the optimization problem. Since the limit analysis solutions from the finite element procedure bracketed the actual collapse load with a margin of $\pm 6\%$, they were used to develop an empirical expression for tunnel stability considering smooth and rough tunnel-soil interfaces.

2.2.1.6 Kumar and Sahoo (2020)

For circular tunnels under water bodies, Kumar and Sahoo (2020) provided lower bound estimates for the ultimate support pressure. The finite element lower bound limit analysis was used, and an associative Mohr-Coulomb criterion was cast as a second-order cone. The tunnel was placed in granular soils for which anisotropy in its internal friction angle was considered using the equivalent friction angle defined by Meyerhof (1978). Similar to Sahoo and Kumar (2019), a steady-state seepage analysis was considered. Furthermore, drained analysis was performed, and anisotropy in permeability coefficients was also considered. However, the ratio of permeability coefficient in the horizontal to vertical directions did not influence the support pressure. Meanwhile, the support pressure dropped as the anisotropy ratio (= ratio of minimum to maximum friction angle) increased. Also, increasing the water table depth increases the support pressure. Nodal velocity patterns indicating the impending soil movement around the tunnel were also given, taking advantage of second-order cone programming's duality.

2.2.2 Dual tunnels

2.2.2.1 Kim et al. (1998)

Kim et al. (1998) studied the effect of shield tunneling adjacent to existing tunnels using reduced-scale models in Speswhite kaolin clay. The model tests were done in two setups - a plane-strain tank for parallel and a cylindrical tank setup for perpendicular tunnels. The process of shield tunneling was carried out using an in-house model tunneling machine. It was found that, for parallel tunnels, the tunneling process initially reduced the total stress on the existing lining, followed by an increase. The change in the total stress was hypothesized to be the initial decrease in horizontal stress because stress release lowered

the total stress, and increased vertical stress due to soil arching above the new tunnel caused a total stress increment in the later stages. Further, it was found that new tunnel installation increases the bending moment in the existing tunnel's lining. However, this increase depends on the clear spacing between the tunnels; the higher the spacing, the lower the bending moment increment. A similar observation was made for perpendicular tunnels, too. Apart from these, variations in pore pressure and liner strain measurements were also made.

2.2.2.2 Addenbrooke and Potts (2001)

The change in the settlement profiles of the ground surface due to parallel and piggyback tunnels was analyzed numerically by Addenbrooke and Potts (2001). The analysis was done using a plane-strain, nonlinear finite element procedure. All the tunnels had a diameter of $D = 4.146$ m. The parallel tunnels were placed at a constant depth of 34 m from the ground surface, and their center-to-center spacing was varied from 8 m to 32 m. For piggyback tunnels, the lower tunnel's center was at a depth of 34 m, and the center-to-center spacing of the top tunnel from the bottom one was varied from 10 m to 18 m. The soil profile consisted of made ground (0-3 m), Thames gravel (3-10 m), London clay (10-50 m), and Lambeth sand (> 50 m) with the water table at 2 m from the ground surface. The soil profile, till Lambeth sand, was modeled using the nonlinear elastic perfectly plastic Mohr-Coulomb yield criterion. The numerical analyses suggested that the superimposed, inverted Gaussian function cannot be used to represent the surface settlement above dual tunnels (parallel and piggyback). For the piggyback case, the lining deformation of the existing tunnel was lower when the new tunnel was constructed above it. Furthermore, the interaction effects in parallel and piggyback tunnels were insignificant for pillar widths and depths of $7D$ and $3D$, respectively.

2.2.2.3 Chehade and Shahrour (2008)

Cehade and Shahrour (2008) conducted parametric analysis on the influence of new tunnel construction on the ground settlement and liner forces of the existing ones. Three combinations were considered - horizontally and vertically separated, and tunnels separated at an angle. The soil yield was governed by the elastic perfectly plastic Mohr-Coulomb yield criterion with a non-associated flow rule. The liner elements of 0.50 m thickness were modeled to be linear elastic. The settlement profile of the parallel tunnels revealed that, with increased spacing, the ground settlement at the center of these tunnels reduces, indicating a loss of the interaction effect, and this critical spacing was observed to be three times the tunnel diameter. The bending moment and thrust of the existing tunnel lining were not affected by the parallel tunnel's spacing. For the vertically separated tunnels, the construction of the lower tunnel before the top one reduced the surface settlement and liner forces.

2.2.2.4 Chen et al. (2011)

Chen et al. (2011) reported field measurements of soil deformations, ground subsidence, and excess pore pressure from constructing parallel tunnels in China. The tunnels had an outer diameter of 6.5 m with a 0.35 m thick lining. The soil profile, with a total depth of 39.46 m, consisted of silt, silty sand, and lean clay, with a water table at 4 m below the ground surface. The pore pressure was found to increase with the tunnel advancement. Furthermore, the ground and subsurface deformations were altered by the tunneling process.

2.2.2.5 Sahoo and Kumar (2018)

The peripheral stability of parallel tunnels in purely cohesive and cohesive-frictional soils was studied by Sahoo and Kumar (2018) using the finite element upper bound method. The soil was assumed to follow the Tresca (purely cohesive) and Mohr-Coulomb (cohesive-frictional) yield criteria. These functions were linearized using a p -sided polygon. For purely cohesive soils, the heterogeneity in undrained cohesion was accounted for using a linear function. On the other hand, the cohesion and internal friction angle of the cohesive-frictional soils were kept constant with depth. The critical spacing, beyond which the interference effect is nullified, was found to vary from $1.5D$ to $15D$ ($D =$ tunnel diameter) depending on its cover depth. A lower tunnel cover and higher shear strength parameters were found to reduce this critical spacing.

2.2.2.6 Xiao et al. (2019)

Xiao et al. (2019a) used an adaptive finite element limit analysis to investigate the stability of dual unlined tunnels placed at different locations. Here, both horizontal and vertical spacing between the tunnels were varied. Lower and upper bounds to the ultimate surcharge on the tunnels were obtained using the modified feasible arc interior point algorithm. A decrease in the vertical spacing reduces the stability number (function of ultimate surcharge) for a constant horizontal spacing. On the contrary, the surcharge capacity increases with the horizontal spacing between tunnels.

2.3 Literature on the seismic stability of circular tunnels

2.3.1 Single tunnels

2.3.1.1 Lee and Trifunac (1979)

Lee and Trifunac (1979) performed an analytical study on the response of a single circular tunnel to incident SH waves. The medium was considered an elastic, isotropic, homogeneous half-space, and the seismic forces were represented as cylindrical waves. The resultant total transverse displacement field was formed by superimposing the displacements from incident, reflected and refracted seismic waves. Also, the effect of incident angle of the SH waves was studied. It was concluded that the displacement field due to scattering of seismic waves by the tunnel wall lasted in the medium till a considerable distance from its axis.

2.3.1.2 St. John and Zahrah (1987)

The article by John and Zahrah (1987) provides a comprehensive state-of-the-art report on the seismic design of underground structures. It details some analytical expressions to compute tunnel responses due to the propagation of primary, shear, and Rayleigh waves in a homogeneous, elastic soil medium. Discussions were made for circular and non-circular tunnels with and without lining. The degree to which the tunnel lining resists the distortion depends on its flexibility ratio, F . It's a relative measure of the lining's flexibility concerning the surrounding medium. Also, it depends on liner thickness, tunnel radius, Young's modulus, and Poisson's ratio of the liner and medium. For a perfectly flexible tunnel lining ($F \geq 20$), the liner will not resist the deformations of the medium. On the other hand, if the liner is relatively rigid ($F < 20$), it will resist the surrounding

deformations. It was stated that considering the tunnel liner to undergo unrestrained soil deformation will lead to a conservative design. Practically, most of the tunnel liners are flexible. Nonetheless, it was said that ground-structure interactions can be considered in special cases when the above approach becomes overly conservative.

2.3.1.3 Sharma and Judd (1991)

Sharma and Judd (1991) collated the seismic damage caused to underground tunnels from about 85 earthquake records to produce a correlation chart between the estimated peak ground acceleration and tunnel cover depth. From the 192 reports analyzed, it was found that tunnels with a cover depth of more than 50 m experienced less damage compared to the shallow ones. Also, unlined tunnels underwent severe damage compared to lined ones. Out of the many liner materials reported, it was found that the unreinforced concrete lining had maximum damage. Earthquakes of higher magnitudes and shorter epicentral distances caused relatively more damage to underground tunnels. The correlation between tunnel cover and peak ground acceleration said that the tunnel should be placed at a larger cover depth if a higher peak ground acceleration is expected at that site.

2.3.1.4 Luco and de Barros (1994)

The response of a long, unlined cylindrical cavity in a uniform, visco-elastic halfspace was studied by Luco and Barros (1994). The method of indirect boundary integral using the two-dimensional Green's functions was used. The structure's response to SH, SV, P, and Rayleigh waves was investigated. Displacements on the ground and tunnel cavity and the tangential and axial stresses were studied. Even though the formulation was for visco-elastic media, most results were presented for a very small damping ratio of 0.1%. It was

found that, for vertical SH wave propagation, a shallow tunnel cavity increases the vertical but decreases the horizontal ground displacements significantly. On the other hand, for P and Rayleigh waves, the tunnel closer to the ground screens surface displacements (vertical for P waves and both for Rayleigh waves).

2.3.1.5 Penzien and Wu (1998)

Penzien and Wu (1998) developed analytical solutions based on plane-strain conditions to compute the tunnel response regarding the lining deformations and stresses for a lined circular tunnel placed in an elastic medium. Three loading cases were considered - (a) in-situ soil stress relaxation after placing the tunnel lining, (b) overburden pressure application on the ground surface, and (c) response to free-field earthquake motions. For all these cases, expressions for soil-tunnel lining interactions were also formulated. Vertically propagating shear waves were considered to study the tunnel's transverse response. The soil's in-situ stress in tunnel lining's vicinity was deemed uniform throughout, thus representing the case where the tunnel axis is significantly away from the ground surface. The liner responses were analyzed under no- and full-slip conditions for steel and concrete linings. Allowing a relative slip between the lining and soil reduces the thrust and increases the bending moment and radial strain. Conclusively, it was stated that relative movement between soil and lining does not affect the maximum combined normal stress for the cases of in-situ soil stress relaxation and free-field earthquake motion.

2.3.1.6 Pakbaz and Yareevand (2005)

Pakbaz and Yareevand (2005) reviewed the analytical solutions available to compute the transverse stability of circular tunnels and analyzed the soil-tunnel lining interaction effects using the finite difference technique. The soil was considered homogeneous following an elastoplastic material model, and elastic beam elements were used for tunnel lining. The soil-lining interaction effects were found to be dependent on ground motion parameters like peak acceleration, duration and intensity, and their relative flexibility. The more rigid the tunnel lining, the lesser was the maximum bending moment and thrust force.

2.3.1.7 Amorosi and Boldini (2009)

Amorosi and Boldini (2009) studied the transverse response of circular tunnels to earthquake motions placed in soft and stiff clay profiles. The input parameters for analytical solutions by Wang (1993) were computed using the one-dimensional visco-elastic, free field analysis incorporating its shear strain dependency. Further, a two-dimensional, full dynamic analysis of the tunnel was performed using the finite element procedure. In this, linear soil models like visco-elastic and visco-elastoplastic were considered. The small strain shear modulus was assumed to vary continuously with depth as a function of plasticity index, over-consolidation ratio, and mean effective stress. The tunnel lining, which was 0.50 m thick, was considered to be made of precast concrete segments modeled using linear visco-elasticity. The acceleration time history of the Kalamata earthquake (1986) in Greece was used for the analysis. The finite element visco-elastic solutions compared well with the analytical ones for soft clay. Further, the analysis considering soil plasticity indicated that a seismic event could induce permanent increments in the bending moment and hoop force. Also, it was found that plasticity-based solutions predict the evolution of loads after the event because of the consolidation past an earthquake.

2.3.1.8 Cilingir and Madabhushi (2011)

Cilingir and Madabhushi (2011) studied the effect of burial depth of single circular tunnels in dry sand using dynamic centrifuge experiments. The experimental study was assisted with a fully dynamic finite element analysis. The physical model of the tunnel was made using an aluminum tube with a diameter of 100 mm. The centrifuge was accelerated at 50g to represent a prototype tunnel of 5 m in diameter. The effect of lining thickness was studied in terms of the flexibility ratio. For this purpose, prototype thicknesses of 88 mm and 12.5 mm were considered. Two cover depth-to-diameter ratios of 1 and 1.8 were used. The soil was assumed to follow a non-associated, elastoplastic Mohr-Coulomb model with hardening behavior in the numerical model. On the other hand, the liners were made of an elastic-rigid plastic material. Input motions were sinusoidal, with a frequency of 1 Hz at the prototype scale. The research also focused on finding the amplification/attenuation of seismic acceleration, earth pressures, liner forces, and deformations. The deformations were estimated using particle image velocimetry. The presence of circular tunnels was found to decrease the fundamental frequency of the medium. Further, compared to the free-field case, the amplification of seismic accelerations from base to ground was also lower in the presence of a tunnel. For a tunnel cover depth-to-diameter ratio of 1, the flexible tunnel de-amplified the peak acceleration compared to the free-field case. On the other hand, a rigid tunnel model placed at 1.8 times its diameter amplified the peak acceleration. Under any lining flexibility, this amplification was higher for deeper tunnels than shallower ones. The peak bending moments were found at the tunnel crown and shoulders, higher for a deeper tunnel. Similarly, the axial forces in deep tunnel linings were higher than in shallower linings.

2.3.1.9 Lanzano et al. (2012)

The behavior of circular tunnels in granular soils subjected to seismic action was studied by Lanzano et al. (2012) using dynamic centrifuge experiments. The model tunnel was an aluminum-copper alloy tube of length \times diameter \times thickness = 200 \times 75 \times 0.5 mm. Granular soil beds were prepared at relative densities of 40% and 75%, and the soil had a critical state friction angle of 32°. The centrifuge was accelerated at 80g and 40g during dynamic stages. The acceleration of 80g was mentioned to represent a prototype tunnel of 6 m diameter in a 24 m thick sand stratum. The cover depth-to-diameter ratios = 1 and 2 were considered. Six earthquake motions of amplitudes ranging between 0.05 and 0.15g and frequencies from 0.375 to 1.25 Hz at the prototype level were used. The experimental findings revealed that the acceleration magnitude recorded at the surface above the tunnel is less than below it, indicating the tunnel's ability to attenuate seismic accelerations. Further, the influence of the underground structure on the seismic acceleration was evident even at a distance of twice the tunnel's diameter. In many cases, the ratio of ground to base acceleration was higher for shallow than deep tunnels, denoting that tunnels with lower cover depths are more vulnerable to seismic damage. Apart from these, the normal thrust and liner bending moment were also observed during the experiment, and it was found that these liner forces were higher on the lower part of the tunnel than on its top.

2.3.1.10 Baziar et al. (2014)

Baziar et al. (2014) found that a box tunnel affects seismic accelerations due to waves traveling from the bedrock to ground surface. Dynamic centrifuge tests were performed using silicate sand of friction angle 45° for free-field conditions and with the tunnel. When accelerated at 40g, the centrifuge could simulate a peak ground acceleration of 0.5g in the prototype. An existing box tunnel in a subway line in Seoul, South Korea, with a 10.66 m

width and 7.38 m depth, was considered as the prototype. These experimental results were used to perform a finite difference numerical study and analyze the tunnel's effect on the seismic motion. Kobe, Northridge, and sinusoidal motions were considered as the input to the numerical model. Important conclusions from this study were - the tunnel's presence reduces the peak spectral amplification at the ground surface for a high-frequency motion compared to the free-field conditions; the natural frequency of the system is reduced because of the tunnel; the peak ground acceleration drops for any earthquake frequency compared to that from the free-field analysis.

2.3.1.11 Pitilakis et al. (2014)

Pitilakis et al. (2014) studied the interaction effects of the superstructure on the seismic response of circular tunnels in granular soils using dynamic time history analysis. The superstructures were modeled as a single degree of freedom oscillators. The tunnel diameter and cover depth varied from 5 m to 10 m each. Two soil profiles were considered - loose and dense deposits conforming to Type C and B of Eurocode 8 (2004), respectively. The shear wave velocity and friction angle varied with depth, and a constant damping of 5% was considered. A simplified Ricker wavelet of amplitude 0.1g and nominal frequency 1 Hz was provided as input at the model's base. The tunnel deformation was quantified using the ovaling ratio, R , defined as the ratio of the ovaling distortion of the tunnel with superstructures to that without them. The ovaling deformations and lining forces of a shallow tunnel were significantly affected due to the presence of an oscillating superstructure. In particular, it was concluded that the presence of superstructures increases the liner's bending moment and axial force by 25% and 30%, respectively.

2.3.1.12 Sahoo and Kumar (2014)

Upper bound solutions to the liner pressure for a single circular tunnel in cohesive-frictional soils were provided by Sahoo and Kumar (2014). The soil was modeled as an ideal plastic Mohr-Coulomb solid with an associated flow rule. The yield criterion was linearized, and a linear optimization procedure was used. The soil inertia in the horizontal direction was considered using the pseudo-static method. In this method, the soil inertia was kept constant through depth. The ultimate support pressure increased with the tunnel cover and seismic acceleration coefficient and decreased with soil friction angle. The effect of soil cohesion (c) was included using $\gamma D/c$; here, D = tunnel diameter. The support pressure increased with $\gamma D/c$.

2.3.1.13 Moghadam and Baziar (2016)

Moghadam and Baziar (2016) studied the ground amplification of the SV waves due to the presence of a lined circular tunnel. The initial investigation was done using 1g shake table tests on a tunnel model made of asbestos-cement tube with 25 cm internal diameter and 6 mm thickness. The existing tunnel in the Tehran, Iran subway line was considered the prototype. This tunnel structure had a diameter of 8 m, with its center at 8 m from the ground surface. Artificial crushed silicate sand at a relative density of 70% and with a unit weight of 16.4 kN/m³ was used in the experiment. The results from shake table experiments were used to numerically simulate model and prototype conditions with which parametric studies were performed. This study extensively studied the effect of the amplification ratio, defined as the ratio of peak ground acceleration with a tunnel to that without it, to assess the influence of shear wave velocity, tunnel burial depth, and the relative stiffness of the soil lining. The numerical results revealed that the tunnel's presence reduced the peak ground acceleration at the ground surface with respect to the free field

when the earthquake's wavelength was less than five times the tunnel diameter. On the other hand, if seismic motion's wavelength is higher than eight times the tunnel diameter, the underground structure does not affect the peak ground acceleration. A maximum amplification ratio was found for an unlined tunnel. If soil and lining had equal stiffness, the tunnel would experience free-field motions. Furthermore, if the tunnel axis is placed at a distance greater than 1.5 times its diameter, the amplification ratio shows no appreciable changes to its presence.

2.3.1.14 Cabangon et al. (2023)

The response of shallow circular tunnels in submerged, normally consolidated, Avezzano structured clay due to seismic loading in many directions was numerically studied by Cabangon et al. (2023) using PLAXIS 3D. The soil medium was modeled using the kinematic hardening multi-surface plasticity model for natural clays developed by Rouainia and Muir wood (2000). The circular tunnel had a diameter of 10 m and was placed at a cover depth of 15 m from the ground surface. The tunnel lining with a thickness of 0.5 m was modeled as a linear viscoelastic material, and no-slip was allowed. A rigid bedrock was considered at a depth of 70 m. The EW and NS components of the Montenegro earthquake motion were used at the model's base. The transverse liner forces predicted by the two-dimensional approach (using only transverse seismic waves) were more conservative than those from the 3D approach. The transverse earthquake waves dissipated along the tunnel length, which increased due to the presence and degradation of clay's structure. Finally, it was inferred that the liner hoop force, transverse bending moment, and shear force, predicted from an equivalent plane-strain (2D) analysis, was comparable with that from a full three-dimensional analysis.

2.3.2 Dual tunnels

2.3.2.1 Balendra et al. (1984)

Balendra et al. (1984) considered the case of twin, lined, circular tunnels placed in an isotropic, homogeneous, elastic halfspace subjected to harmonic shear waves with in-plane particle displacements. The seismic wave was represented using the steady-state function, and the analytical solution was obtained using the expansion of wave functions method. The response of underground structure was captured in terms of displacement and shear stress amplitudes along the periphery of one of the tunnels. Liners were assumed to be of concrete and steel with 100 mm and 60 mm thicknesses, respectively. The soil conditions analyzed included soft clay and loess deposits having shear wave velocities of 45 m/s and 260 m/s, respectively. At low frequencies, the displacement amplitude showed no significant change along the tunnel circumference. Also, at this frequency, the single tunnel's displacement amplitude was higher than that of a closely spaced twin tunnel. The above quantity varied along the perimeter for a higher frequency, and its magnitude was higher for a twin tunnel. The above observation was made for any lining and in any soil condition. Further, shear stress amplitudes depended more on the tunnel spacing for soft clay than loess. The maximum shear stress ratio, the ratio of maximum shear stress from twin tunnels to that of a single tunnel, was insignificant after a center-to-center spacing equal to thrice the tunnel radius for a low frequency. On the contrary, the ratio was significant for high-frequency waves, even at larger spacing, indicating that the scattered waves do not decay quickly at such frequencies.

2.3.2.2 Moore and Guan (1996)

Using the successive reflection method, Moore and Guan (1996) analytically studied the three-dimensional response of dual, lined circular tunnels placed in a viscoelastic full space. The medium was subjected to body waves - longitudinal and transverse, considering their incidence angles. The tunnel's response was quantified using normalized displacements and liner stresses. The influence of tunnel spacing was significant for higher frequencies; at such frequencies, the hoop stress increased as the spacing was reduced. The amplification of longitudinal waves, because of scattering from tunnel lining, was not as substantial as for transverse waves. Similarly, the tunnel spacing on the liner stresses was less significant for longitudinal waves than for the other. Finally, it was stated that the seismic analysis of tunnels considering the plane-strain conditions provided conservative estimates compared to a three-dimensional analysis.

2.3.2.3 Liang et al. (2003)

Liang et al. (2003) examined seismic wave amplification due to single and twin circular tunnels in an elastic medium. The Fourier-Bessel series expansion method was used to solve the problem. The medium was isotropic, homogeneous, and subjected to incident SV waves. The depth of the tunnel axis from the ground surface was kept constant throughout the study at 1.5 times the tunnel radius. The amplification effects were studied using the change in the displacement amplitude measured at the ground surface. The interaction between twin tunnels significantly increases the displacement amplitude more than for a single tunnel. It was shown that the displacement amplitude decreases with the tunnel spacing. The ground displacement for twin tunnels was amplified about 2.1 and 8.7 times that of single and no tunnel cases, respectively.

2.3.2.4 Liu and Wang (2012)

Liu and Wang (2012) used the Helmholtz decomposition technique and the complex variable approach to analyze the seismic response of parallel circular tunnels. Like previous studies, tunnels were placed in an isotropic, homogeneous, and elastic medium. The seismic activity was modeled considering plane primary and shear waves (out-of-plane particle displacements), and the effect of its incidence angle was also accounted for. The tunnel response along its periphery was captured using the dynamic stress concentration factor (DSCF), a ratio of the hoop stress and incident wave intensity. This stress concentration parameter was more significant for twin than single tunnels and increased as the spacing reduced. It was reported that the interaction effects between the tunnel could be neglected beyond a horizontal spacing of twenty times the radius. Moreover, for a spacing of about 200 times the tunnel radius, the DSCF distribution closely matched that of the single tunnel.

2.3.2.5 Alielahi and Adampira (2016)

Alielahi and Adampira (2016) studied the amplification of ground surface displacement caused by parallel, unlined circular tunnels using the boundary element method in the time domain. A uniform elastic medium subjected to vertically propagating SV and P waves was considered for the analysis. The incident seismic waves were modeled using the Ricker wavelet with a maximum amplitude of 1 mm. The ground surface displacement amplitude increases sharply for low values of dimensionless frequencies ($2a/\lambda$; a = tunnel radius, and λ = shear wave's incident wavelength) in both single and dual tunnels. Further, the twin tunnels amplify the displacements on the ground surface for both SV and P waves. Meanwhile, the single tunnel intensified the displacements from SV waves more significantly than P waves. A center-to-center spacing of over 20 times the tunnel

radius made the tunnels act independently with their response close to the free-field case. Underground tunnels were found to amplify waves of long periods (low frequency) and de-amplify those with a short period. The displacement was found to be maximum for a shallow tunnel, and the effect of a parallel tunnel reduced as the burial depth increased. It was found that incident waves with wavelengths of twice to eight times the tunnel diameter amplify the ground response more than the free-field condition. Further, it was found that the parallel tunnels cease to cause any change to the ground response if the tunnel diameter is larger than the wavelength.

2.3.2.6 Liu et al. (2016)

The effect of separation distance, liner's relative material parameters, and seismic wave's frequency on the hoop stress and liner displacements of piggyback twin circular tunnels were investigated by Liu et al. (2016). The indirect boundary integration equation method was used along an elastic medium and vertical SV and P waves. The top tunnel's axis was placed at four times its internal radius from the ground surface and kept constant in the parametric study. A decrement in the hoop stress amplitude of the top tunnel was observed for high-frequency SV and P waves due to the shielding effect of the lower tunnel. Contrary to the above, low-frequency P waves increased the top tunnel's hoop stress. The relative rigidity of the liner with the surrounding soil influenced the dual tunnel response. When the liner material was relatively softer, tunnels tended to amplify the ground motion and vice versa.

2.3.2.7 Lin et al. (2017)

Lin et al. (2017) studied the seismic response of parallel, lined circular tunnels in soils to in-plane body waves using the finite/infinite element approach. The east-west (EW) and

up-down (UD) components of the ChiChi earthquake (1999) were used. The parametric study used tunnels with a diameter of 6 m and liner thickness of 0.5 m. It was found that, for the EW component, stress concentrations appeared along the shoulders of the tunnel lining. On the other hand, considering the UD component produced stress concentrations along the tunnel spring line. Further, the variation of acceleration along the tunnel periphery was studied. The maximum acceleration occurred along each tunnel's upper and lower halves for the EW and UD components, respectively. The acceleration magnitude along the tunnel periphery, for both EW and UD components, reduced with the tunnel depth from the ground surface. It was found that the effect of tunnel spacing on the acceleration distribution was more prominent for the UD component.

2.3.2.8 Tsiniadis (2018)

Tsiniadis (2018) extended the work of Pitilakis et al. (2014) to examine the seismic response of single and twin circular tunnels in clay, considering the presence of superstructures using the finite element procedure. The clay deposit of 50 m over an elastic bedrock housed tunnels, each with a diameter of 6 m. The second tunnel in the twin tunnel case was placed at a fixed center-to-center distance of 15 m. The cover depth-to-diameter ratios of 1.167 and 2.833 were considered for the analysis. The segmental tunnel lining was modified to equivalent continuous rings with a thickness of 0.3 m. The cohesive soil deposit conformed to Class B, C, and D of Eurocode 8 (2004), and the elastic bedrock had a shear wave velocity of 1000 m/s. The seismic ground motions of the Friuli (1976), Italy, and the Kobe (1995), Japan, were applied at the base of the numerical model. The ground surface was considered to have two and six numbers of nine-story buildings modeled as single degree of freedom (SDOE) oscillators. The soil was assumed to follow simplified viscoelastic and nonlinear kinematic hardening models. The seismic response was evaluated regarding $R-F$ relations (R = ovaling ratio, and F = flexibility ratio), dynamic earth

pressures and lining forces. The ovaling ratio increased with the number of SDOF oscillators and flexibility ratio. Further, the above increase in R value was more evident for a shallow tunnel. Similarly, the dynamic earth pressure and liner forces were higher for a flexible lining, shallower tunnel, and severe seismic motion. Following this, the case of six SDOF oscillators on the ground surface increased the magnitudes of above quantities than two oscillators. It was observed that the second tunnel did not cause any significant change to the first tunnel's response using the simplified viscoelastic model. On the other hand, minor fluctuations were observed when the nonlinear kinematic hardening model was used.

2.3.2.9 Feizi et al. (2022)

Feizi et al. (2022) employed the finite difference approach to study the amplification effects of single, parallel, and piggyback (vertically aligned) square tunnels subjected to vertical in-plane shear waves. A homogeneous, isotropic, viscoelastic half-space with a shear wave velocity of 400 m/s was considered. The seismic wave was provided as a stress impulse to the model base using the Ricker wavelet. The dimensionless frequency was defined similar to Alielahi and Adampira (2016) ($= 2a/\lambda$, where a = side of the square tunnel). The amplification ratio was defined as the ratio of the horizontal displacement at the ground surface with the tunnel to that for a free-field condition. For both single and dual tunnels, it was found that the horizontal displacements are amplified compared to the free-field case. The parallel tunnel case caused the highest amplification because of entrapped and scattered seismic waves in the soil pillar between them. Like other studies, a shallower tunnel amplified the displacement more than a deeper one due to the entrapped waves between the tunnel surface and the ground. The effect of square tunnels on seismic amplification was negligible if the tunnel's center (the top one for the piggyback case) was higher than twice its size. Also, it was found that the lower tunnel, in the piggyback case,

screened the seismic waves, which reduced the amplification factor. For a lower dimensionless frequency of 0.1, the piggyback tunnels caused substantial ground amplification on the vertical through the tunnel center. On the other hand, for a higher non-dimensional frequency of 1, significant ground amplification occurred at relatively farther points from the tunnel centerline.

2.4 Literature on the finite element limit analysis - lower bound method

2.4.1 Anderheggen and Knöpfel (1972)

Assuming an ideal plastic body, Anderheggen and Knöpfel (1972) computed lower and upper bounds to the collapse load for 2D and 3D solids using the finite element procedure. The revised simplex methodology was used to solve the linear programming problem as a result of linearizing the regular polygonal yield criterion. The procedure was applied to compute the collapse load for stretching and bending of plates.

2.4.2 Bottero et al. (1980)

Solving for the limit bounds for geotechnical problems using the numerical tool of finite elements was initiated by Bottero et al. (1980). The Mohr-Coulomb failure condition was linearized, and the variables were considered to vary linearly within a finite element. This was applied to compute collapse loads in compressive and pull-out modes of foundations, and slope stability of purely cohesive soils.

2.4.3 Pastor and Turgeman (1982)

The Mohr-Coulomb and von Mises criteria in the axisymmetric conditions were implemented into the finite element limit analysis framework by Pastor and Turgeman (1982). Similar to previous studies, the failure surfaces were linearized. The developed formulation was tested for some axisymmetric problems like the circular excavation's stability and to simulate triaxial tests.

2.4.4 Sloan (1988)

Previous researchers solved the linear programming problem using the revised simplex algorithm which was not efficient to solve problems involving large sparse matrices. Sloan (1988) proposed a more robust active set algorithm to compute the lower bound to the limit collapse load using finite elements with linear variation of stresses. Also, statically admissible discontinuities in the stress field were allowed by modeling the discontinuity equilibrium between the shared edges of the adjacent triangular elements. Its efficacy was validated by performing a classical bearing capacity analysis of strip footings.

2.4.5 Lyamin and Sloan (2002)

The sharp edges resulting from the linearization of the yield surfaces poses a lot of numerical problems. Lyamin and Sloan (2002) overcome this issue for the Mohr-Coulomb yield criterion by proposing a hyperbolic approximation to it. Further, a fast quasi-Newton scheme was used to solve the non-linear constrained optimization problem and applied to various geotechnical engineering cases.

2.4.6 Makrodimopoulos and Martin (2006)

Makrodimopoulos and Martin (2006) took advantage of the convex nature of various yield surfaces that are generally used in geotechnical engineering, like the Drucker-Prager and Mohr-Coulomb criteria and proposed to solve for the lower bound using the Second-Order Cone Programming (SOCP) technique. This is an interior-point algorithm, and it was touted to be more efficient than the linear programming problem. The soil was discretized to three noded triangular elements. The concept of infinite elements under the purview of SOCP was also discussed.

2.4.7 Krabbenhøft et al. (2007)

Krabbenhøft et al. (2007) detailed the conic formulations of various yield criteria like the Mohr-Coulomb (plane strain and 3D for geomaterials) and the Nielsen criterion (for reinforced concrete structures). Standard formulations for the elastic and elasto-plastic analysis of structures using the conic expressions were provided. Furthermore, different elements, like the lower bound, upper bound, displacement, mixed elements, were described. These formulations were used to compute circular and square footings' bearing pressure in granular soils, and for cone-shaped excavations in $c - \phi$ soils.

2.4.8 Tang et al. (2014)

The SOCP technique proposed by Makrodimopoulos and Martin (2006) for plane-strain problems was extended by Tang et al. (2014) to axisymmetric problems using the Mohr-Coulomb criterion. The uplift capacity of helical anchors, with single and many plates, driven in undrained clay was studied.

2.5 Summary

The current chapter details major findings from relevant literature on the static and seismic stability of single and dual circular tunnels. These articles provide useful insights into studies already done and the gaps to be filled. Additionally, literature regarding the development of the finite element limit analysis (lower bound) approach considering various optimization schemes has been discussed in application to geotechnical engineering.

3

Finite Element Limit Analysis - Lower bound method

3.1 General

Majority of the problems in soil mechanics are of two types - Stability problems and Elasticity problems. The *stability problems* involve finding the load that the soil mass can withstand at its ultimate failure. Examples include the bearing capacity of foundations, earth pressure, slope stability, tunnel stability, etc. Contrastingly, the *elasticity problems* involve finding the stress and deformation of soil before its yielding (i.e. at working load) like stresses below foundations and behind retaining walls, settlement of foundations, ground settlement due to tunneling, etc. For the design of a structure, a suitable factor of safety is applied against ultimate failure of soil mass to ensure the serviceability requirements at the working load condition. In this thesis, the resistance to be offered by the support systems of tunnels, i.e., tunnel lining against the stresses acting on it at the ultimate failure of surrounding soil. Out of the methods available, the stability of the problems undertaken in this thesis have been solved based on the lower bound theorem of limit analysis.

Solving a stability problem using the limit analysis refers to computing the collapse load for the body using either of the two fundamental theorems of limit analysis - the *lower* and *upper* bound theorems. These theorems provide theoretical bounds to the actual collapse load of the body. The limit analysis relies on some assumptions - (i) the material behaves perfectly plastic; (ii) the normality condition of the plastic strain and the convexity of the yield surface hold true (associated flow rule); (iii) The change in geometry of the material is insignificant at failure. In the lower bound theorem of limit analysis, the magnitude of the collapse load is determined from a statically admissible stress field satisfying the equilibrium and stress boundary conditions without the violation of yield criterion. The computed collapse load is either smaller or at the most equal to the true collapse load's magnitude. Whereas, in the upper bound limit analysis, the magnitude of the collapse load is determined from a kinematically admissible velocity field by equating the rate of work done by the external and body forces to the rate of dissipation of total internal energy. The magnitude of the collapse load obtained from upper bound limit analysis remains always either greater or equal to the magnitude of true collapse load. Thus, limit load computed using lower bound limit analysis remains always safer from the design point of view. The earliest work on the general formulation of limit theorems for a rigid plastic material was carried out by Gvozdev (1938), which was not known to many outside the then Soviet Union until similar research by Prager (1947) and Hill (1951), as reported by Yu et al. (2009). These limit theorems were then extended to a general elastic-perfectly plastic body by Drucker et al. (1951, 1952). Further, Drucker and Prager (1952) and Drucker (1953) extended the idea of limit theorems for soil mechanics applications. In the formative years of the soil mechanics application of lower bound limit analysis, stability problems were solved by assuming a stress field to compute the collapse load. The accuracy of such solution depends on the closeness the assumed stress field to the actual one. Furthermore, conceiving a stress field for problems with complicated geometry and loading conditions is cumbersome. To make the application of lower bound limit

analysis easy to real world problems and avoid assuming a stress field, the finite element method along with different optimization procedures (linear/nonlinear/second order cone programming) was unified with the lower bound approach of limit analysis.

Let Ω represent the domain of a rigid perfectly plastic body marked by the boundary Γ as shown in Fig. 3.1. Here, Γ_u represent the Dirichlet boundary with $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{0}$, Γ_t represents the Neumann boundary with known traction vector $\hat{\mathbf{T}}$ ($\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ is the outward unit normal vector on Γ_t), $\Gamma = \Gamma_u \cup \Gamma_t$, and $\Gamma_u \cap \Gamma_t = \emptyset$.

FIGURE 3.1: Schematic representation of a general domain subjected to boundary conditions.

Theorem 3.1 (Lower bound theorem). *If for a perfectly plastic body, the stress field, σ_{ij} can be found such that it satisfies the equilibrium equation*

$$\nabla \sigma_{ij} = b_i \quad \text{in } \Omega \quad (3.1)$$

the traction boundary condition

$$\sigma_{ij} \hat{n}_j = \hat{T}_i \quad \text{in } \Gamma_t \quad (3.2)$$

and does not violate the yield criterion

$$f(\sigma_{ij}) \leq 0 \quad \text{in } \Omega \quad (3.3)$$

then the body will not collapse due to the loads acting on it.

Such a stress field, σ_{ij} , satisfying the above conditions is called the statically admissible stress field. The collapse load found from σ_{ij} will represent the lower bound to the actual collapse load. Drucker (1953) proposed that considering the stress discontinuities while computing the statically admissible stress field improves the lower bound solution. In Fig. 3.1, let Γ_d represent any stress discontinuity surface within the body Ω . The stress field, σ_{ij} , should additionally satisfy the following discontinuity equilibrium condition

$$\sigma_{ij}^+ \hat{n}_j^+ - \sigma_{ij}^- \hat{n}_j^- = 0 \quad \text{in } \Gamma_d \quad (3.4)$$

Here, σ_{ij}^+ and σ_{ij}^- represent the stress values computed on either side of the discontinuity Γ_d , and \hat{n}_j^+ and \hat{n}_j^- are the unit normal vectors along either side of Γ_d . Several lower bound values of the collapse load are possible, yet the best lower bound estimate to the ultimate failure load is the greatest of these collapse loads.

Above mathematical statements are the continuous formulation of the lower bound limit analysis. For a continuum like soil, these conditions are to be satisfied at infinite locations in the domain. It makes computation of analytical solutions difficult when the problem or the loading conditions or both are complicated. Therefore, the continuous lower bound formulation is made discrete by discretizing the soil domain using the finite element approach. The search for a greatest lower bound eventually leads to a constrained optimization problem. Lysmer (1970) introduced the concept of using the finite element procedure to compute the lower bound collapse load, which was extended by Anderheggen and Knöpfel (1972) and Bottero et al. (1980) to solve geotechnical engineering problems. Sloan (1988) computed the lower bound collapse load for soil mechanics problems using an active set algorithm by introducing the stress discontinuities along the shared element edges. The optimization problem was solved by casting the yield criterion using a polygon of p sides, i.e., using the linear programming problem. The disadvantages of using a polygonal approximation to the yield criterion was initially overcome

by Lyamin and Sloan (2002) who used the non-linear programming problem. The yield criterion was cast using a smoothed-hyperbolic approximation. With the advent of interior point algorithms and efficient conic optimization procedures (Andersen et al., 2003), Makrodimopoulos and Martin (2006) and Krabbenhøft et al. (2007) provided the effective formulations to cast the yield criterion using the second-order cone. This procedure takes advantage of the convex nature of most of the yield surfaces used in soil mechanics; thus, eliminating the need for approximation.

The current chapter explains the steps involved in computing the support pressure for the circular tunnel using the discrete lower bound limit analysis with the finite element procedure. The plane-strain analysis considering the Mohr-Coulomb yield criterion has been carried out. As needed by the statement of the lower bound theorem, the associated flow rule has been used. The stresses have been considered to vary linearly within an element. The computations involving domain discretization, constraint and collapse load matrices generation have been done using MATLAB (2022). The second-order cone programming problem has been solved using MOSEK (2022), the Optimization Toolbox for MATLAB (2022).

3.2 Finite element limit analysis - the lower bound method

3.2.1 General

In the present research, the soil is discretized using triangular elements containing three nodes. Fig. 3.2 represents a typical triangular element used. In general, an i^{th} node in the e^{th} element consists of three unknown stresses - $\sigma_{x_i}^e$, $\sigma_{z_i}^e$, and $\tau_{xz_i}^e$. Further, the stresses are meant to vary linearly within an element. The node numbers are unique to an element;

hence, a node of a given coordinate shall have various numbers depending on the element considered.

FIGURE 3.2: A typical triangular element used in the study

For a typical linear triangular finite element, the shape functions \widehat{N}_i ($i = 1, 2, 3$) can be written as:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \widehat{N}_1 \\ \widehat{N}_2 \\ \widehat{N}_3 \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{1}{2\mathcal{A}^e} \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_1 & \beta_1 & \eta_1 \\ \alpha_2 & \beta_2 & \eta_2 \\ \alpha_3 & \beta_3 & \eta_3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} 1 \\ x \\ z \end{Bmatrix} \quad (3.5)$$

In Eq. 3.5, \mathcal{A}^e is the area of the triangular element = $|\beta_1\eta_2 - \beta_2\eta_1|/2$. Here, $\alpha_i = x_j z_k - x_k z_j$, $\beta_i = z_j - z_k$, and $\eta_i = -(x_j - x_k)$, where $i \neq j \neq k$, and i, j, k permute in natural order. Using the shape functions in Eq. 3.5, the stress components σ_x^e , σ_z^e , and τ_{xz}^e

for a typical element e can be expressed using the nodal stress quantities as

$$\sigma_x^e = \sum_{i=1}^3 \hat{N}_i \sigma_{x_i}^e \quad (3.6a)$$

$$\sigma_z^e = \sum_{i=1}^3 \hat{N}_i \sigma_{z_i}^e \quad (3.6b)$$

$$\tau_{xz}^e = \sum_{i=1}^3 \hat{N}_i \tau_{xz_i}^e \quad (3.6c)$$

Here, $\sigma_{x_i}^e$, $\sigma_{z_i}^e$, and $\tau_{xz_i}^e$ are the stresses at the i^{th} node of the e^{th} element.

3.2.2 Equilibrium conditions

The statically admissible stress field from the lower bound analysis should be under equilibrium. For a plane strain condition, the stress equilibrium equations are

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{xz}}{\partial z} = b_x \quad (3.7a)$$

$$\frac{\partial \tau_{xz}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \sigma_z}{\partial z} = b_z \quad (3.7b)$$

In equations 3.7a and 3.7b, b_x and b_z are the body forces along the horizontal and vertical directions, respectively. For seismic analysis, these body forces are functions of space and time dependent horizontal and vertical seismic accelerations imparted to the soil by harmonic base excitation in the horizontal and vertical directions, which are detailed in the subsequent chapters (4–7) depending upon the parameters of shear and primary waves propagation.

The above equilibrium condition is to be imposed on each element. Thus, for a discretized medium considered in this study, Eq. 3.7 can be expressed in the matrix form

using the elemental stresses in Eq. 3.6, for the e^{th} element, as

$$\mathbf{A}_{\text{eq}}^e \boldsymbol{\sigma}^e = \mathbf{b}_{\text{eq}}^e \quad (3.8)$$

In Eq. 3.8, \mathbf{A}_{eq}^e is the coefficient matrix containing the parameters from the shape functions, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^e$ is the vector of all the nodal stresses for the e^{th} element, and \mathbf{b}_{eq}^e contains the body forces along the X and Z directions.

$$\mathbf{A}_{\text{eq}}^e = \frac{1}{2\mathcal{A}^e} \begin{bmatrix} \beta_1 & 0 & \eta_1 & \beta_2 & 0 & \eta_2 & \beta_3 & 0 & \eta_3 \\ 0 & \eta_1 & \beta_1 & 0 & \eta_2 & \beta_2 & 0 & \eta_3 & \beta_3 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}^e = \left\{ \sigma_{x_1}^e \quad \sigma_{z_1}^e \quad \tau_{xz_1}^e \quad \sigma_{x_2}^e \quad \sigma_{z_2}^e \quad \tau_{xz_2}^e \quad \sigma_{x_3}^e \quad \sigma_{z_3}^e \quad \tau_{xz_3}^e \right\}^T$$

$$\mathbf{b}_{\text{eq}}^e = \left\{ b_x \quad b_z \right\}^T$$

Since the equilibrium conditions impose two equality constraints per element, for E number of elements in the entire domain, $2E$ number of equality constraints would be generated. The global matrices corresponding to the element equilibrium condition shall be expressed as

$$\mathbb{A}_{\text{eq}} = \sum_{e=1}^E \mathbf{A}_{\text{eq}}^e \quad (3.9)$$

$$\mathbb{B}_{\text{eq}} = \sum_{e=1}^E \mathbf{b}_{\text{eq}}^e \quad (3.10)$$

Here, N is the total number of nodes in the domain.

3.2.3 Stress discontinuity equilibrium

Drucker (1953) and Lysmer (1970) stated that considering the stress discontinuity in formulating the statically admissible stress field improves the lower bound solution. The node numbers being distinct for each element in spite of their common coordinate, the statically admissible stress discontinuity in the tangential stress component is allowed along the shared edges of the element. The normal and shear stresses along this common edge should be equal to satisfy the stress discontinuity equilibrium (Sloan, 1988).

FIGURE 3.3: Schematic description of the statically admissible stress discontinuity

Fig. 3.3 shows a typical discontinuity between two elements 'a' and 'b'. The stress discontinuity equilibrium can be stated mathematically as

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{n_1}^a &= \sigma_{n_2}^b; & \sigma_{n_3}^a &= \sigma_{n_4}^b \\ \tau_1^a &= \tau_2^b; & \tau_3^a &= \tau_4^b \end{aligned} \quad (3.11)$$

Referring to Fig. 3.3, the normal (σ_n) and shear (τ) stresses on any plane at an angle Θ from the horizontal can be written in terms of the two-dimensional rectangular stress

components as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_n \\ \tau \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \sin^2 \Theta & \cos^2 \Theta & -\sin 2\Theta \\ -\frac{1}{2} \sin 2\Theta & \frac{1}{2} \sin 2\Theta & \cos 2\Theta \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_z \\ \tau_{xz} \end{Bmatrix} = [\mathfrak{D}] \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_z \\ \tau_{xz} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (3.12)$$

Using equations 3.11 and 3.12, for a typical discontinuity d within the domain, the stress discontinuity equilibrium condition can be written as

$$\mathbf{A}_{dc}^d \boldsymbol{\sigma}^d = \mathbf{b}_{dc}^d \quad (3.13)$$

In Eq. 3.13,

$$\mathbf{A}_{dc}^d = \begin{bmatrix} \mathfrak{D} & -\mathfrak{D} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathfrak{D} & -\mathfrak{D} \end{bmatrix}$$

Here, \mathfrak{D} is the matrix defined in Eq. 3.12. Further,

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\sigma}^d &= \left\{ \sigma_1^a \quad \sigma_2^b \quad \sigma_3^a \quad \sigma_4^b \right\}^T \\ \sigma_l^m &= \left\{ \sigma_{x_l}^m \quad \sigma_{z_l}^m \quad \tau_{xz_l}^m \right\}^T \quad l = 1, 2, 3, 4; \quad m = a, b \\ \mathbf{b}_{dc}^d &= \mathbf{0} \end{aligned}$$

A typical discontinuity imposes four equality constraints; hence D number of discontinuities in the domain gives rise to $4D$ number of equality constraints. Eq. 3.13 is generated for all the discontinuities within and assembled to get the global matrices, i.e.,

$$\mathbb{A}_{dc} = \sum_{d=1}^D \mathbf{A}_{dc}^d \quad (3.14)$$

$$\mathbb{B}_{dc} = \sum_{d=1}^D \mathbf{b}_{dc}^d \quad (3.15)$$

3.2.4 Stress boundary condition

The statically admissible state of stress obtained from the lower bound approach must satisfy the imposed stresses on the domain boundaries. Fig. 3.4 shows a typical node k on the boundary bd which is subjected to known normal and shear stresses, $\sigma_{n_k}^{bd}$ and τ_k^{bd} , respectively. Using Eq. 3.12, the constraint for the stress boundary condition in k can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{A}_{\mathbf{bc}}^{\mathbf{bd}} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\mathbf{bc}}^{\mathbf{bd}} = \mathbf{b}_{\mathbf{bc}}^{\mathbf{bd}} \quad (3.16)$$

Here, $\mathbf{A}_{\mathbf{bc}}^{\mathbf{bd}} = \mathcal{D}$ as given in Eq. 3.12 computed for the boundary node shown in Fig. 3.4. Furthermore,

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{\mathbf{bd}} = \left\{ \sigma_{x_k}^{bd} \quad \sigma_{z_k}^{bd} \quad \tau_{xz_k}^{bd} \right\}^T$$

$$\mathbf{b}_{\mathbf{bc}}^{\mathbf{bd}} = \left\{ \sigma_{n_k}^{bd} \quad \tau_k^{bd} \right\}^T$$

FIGURE 3.4: Schematic description of a typical stress boundary

Eq. 3.16 is generated for all the nodes along the domain boundary imposed with known stresses. Thus, if N_b is the total number of nodes along the boundary, the global

matrices are

$$\mathbb{A}_{bc} = \sum_{bd=1}^{N_b} \mathbf{A}_{bc}^{bd} \quad (3.17)$$

$$\mathbb{B}_{bc} = \sum_{bd=1}^{N_b} \mathbf{b}_{bc}^{bd} \quad (3.18)$$

3.2.5 Yield criterion

The stress state at each point within chosen soil domain should not violate the yield criterion in the lower bound limit analysis. In the present study, the soil medium is modeled using the Mohr-Coulomb yield criterion. For a cohesive-frictional soil, under plane-strain conditions, the Mohr-Coulomb yield criterion at the i^{th} node of the e^{th} element is written as

$$\sqrt{(\sigma_{x_i}^e - \sigma_{z_i}^e)^2 + 4(\tau_{xz_i}^e)^2} \leq 2c \cos \phi - (\sigma_{x_i}^e + \sigma_{z_i}^e) \sin \phi \quad (3.19)$$

The above constraint can be cast as a conic quadratic constraint by introducing the auxiliary variable, χ , governed by the equation of the Lorentz cone or the second-order cone, \mathcal{L}^3 , at each node (Makrodimopoulos and Martin, 2006; Krabbenhøft et al., 2007):

$$\chi \in \mathcal{L}^3, \quad \mathcal{L}^3 = \left\{ \chi \in \mathbb{R}^3 : \chi_1 \geq \sqrt{\chi_2^2 + \chi_3^2} \right\} \quad (3.20)$$

Fig. 3.5 describes the surface of a typical Second Order Cone with $\chi_2, \chi_3 \in [-10, 10]$.

Thus, using χ_j^i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, N; j = 1, 2, 3$) in Eq. 3.19, the yield criterion constraint at the i^{th} node can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{A}_{\text{yield}}^i \boldsymbol{\sigma}_i + \boldsymbol{\chi}_j^i = \mathbf{b}_{\text{yield}}^i \quad (3.21)$$

FIGURE 3.5: A typical second-order cone.

where,

$$\mathbf{A}_{\text{yield}}^i = \begin{bmatrix} \sin \phi & \sin \phi & 0 \\ -1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -2 \end{bmatrix}; \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma}_i = \left\{ \sigma_{x_i}^e \quad \sigma_{z_i}^e \quad \tau_{xz_i}^e \right\}^T$$

$$\boldsymbol{\chi}_j^i = \left\{ \chi_1^i \quad \chi_2^i \quad \chi_3^i \right\}^T; \quad \mathbf{b}_{\text{yield}}^i = \mathbf{0}$$

The global matrices, $\mathbb{A}_{\text{yield}}$ and $\mathbb{B}_{\text{yield}}$, are formed by assembling the local matrices in Eq. 3.21 at all the nodes.

$$\mathbb{A}_{\text{yield}} = \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{A}_{\text{yield}}^i \quad (3.22)$$

$$\mathbb{B}_{\text{yield}} = \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{b}_{\text{yield}}^i \quad (3.23)$$

3.2.6 Soil-tunnel support system (lining) interface modeling

At the ultimate shear failure, the soil *slips* relative to the tunnel lining, and this influences the collapse load's magnitude. The effect of the interface condition between the tunnel lining and the surrounding soil has been considered in terms of the interface friction angle, δ , and the adhesion, c_a . Conceptually, at the state of ultimate failure, the mobilized shear stress's magnitude along the soil-tunnel lining must be less than or equal to the shear strength of the interface. Mathematically,

$$|\tau_{nt}| \leq c_a - \sigma_n \tan \delta \quad (3.24)$$

where τ_{nt} is the mobilized shear stress along the interface of the soil and tunnel lining, and σ_n is the normal stress. Here σ_n is negative due to the assumption of tensile stresses being positive. The modulus, $|\tau_{nt}|$, in Eq. 3.24 indicates the possibility of development of shear stresses in the positive and negative directions depending on the relative movement of surrounding soil at its ultimate failure state. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{nt} &\leq c_a - \sigma_n \tan \delta \\ -\tau_{nt} &\leq c_a - \sigma_n \tan \delta \end{aligned} \quad (3.25)$$

The interface inequality given in Eq. 3.25 applied to the t^{th} node along the tunnel lining-soil interface is expressed as

$$\mathbf{A}_{\text{int}}^t \boldsymbol{\sigma}^t \leq \mathbf{b}_{\text{int}}^t \quad (3.26)$$

$\begin{matrix} 2 \times 3 & 3 \times 1 & 2 \times 1 \end{matrix}$

Here

$$\mathbf{A}_{\text{int}}^t = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\mathfrak{J}}_1 + \tilde{\mathfrak{J}}_2 \\ -\tilde{\mathfrak{J}}_1 + \tilde{\mathfrak{J}}_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\tilde{\mathfrak{J}}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{1}{2} \sin 2\theta_t & \frac{1}{2} \sin 2\theta_t & \cos 2\theta_t \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\tilde{\mathfrak{J}}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} \sin^2 \theta_t & \cos^2 \theta_t & -\sin 2\theta_t \end{bmatrix} \tan \delta$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}^t = \left\{ \sigma_{x_t} \quad \sigma_{z_t} \quad \tau_{xz_t} \right\}^T$$

$$\mathbf{b}_{\text{int}}^t = \left\{ c_{a_t} \quad c_{a_t} \right\}^T$$

Here, for the t^{th} node on the interface, θ_t is the angle made by the radial line from the tunnel center to that node with the horizontal, c_{a_t} is the adhesion magnitude at the node.

Applying the interface condition in Eq. 3.26 to all the N_t number of nodes along the tunnel lining-soil interface, the global matrices are

$$\mathbb{A}_{\text{int}} = \sum_{t=1}^{N_t} \mathbf{A}_{\text{int}}^t \quad (3.27)$$

$$\mathbb{B}_{\text{int}} = \sum_{t=1}^{N_t} \mathbf{b}_{\text{int}}^t \quad (3.28)$$

Even though the interface conditions can be set between smooth and non-smooth using Eq. 3.24, Wang (1993) reported that the seismic analysis of tunnels performed by allowing full-slip (smooth) conditions along the interface, i.e., $\delta = 0$ and $c_a = 0$, provided conservative results. Hence, in the present thesis, $\tau_{nt} = 0$ has been applied at nodes along the tunnel periphery to model a smooth soil-lining interface for brevity and conservative results. Nevertheless, a non-smooth ($\delta > 0$ and $c_a > 0$) interface can be readily modeled using the aforementioned procedure.

3.2.7 Support system modeling

The edges of the elements along tunnel boundary are considered to model the tunnel support systems. The smaller size of elements facilitates lesser error in considering the cord length instead of the arc length for modeling the circular tunnel periphery. Fig. 3.6 shows a typical tunnel arc and the corresponding element along the tunnel periphery.

FIGURE 3.6: A typical tunnel boundary segment and associated stress conditions.

The support pressure, σ_s , required for the stability of the tunnel should be equal to or greater than the maximum of the normal stresses in the nodes along the tunnel boundary. This condition can be expressed as

$$\sigma_s = \max [\sigma_{n_1}, \sigma_{n_2}, \dots, \sigma_{n_i}, \sigma_{n_{i+1}}, \dots, \sigma_{n_{N_t}}] \quad (3.29)$$

In Eq. 3.29, σ_{n_i} and $\sigma_{n_{i+1}}$ are the normal stresses along the i^{th} and $(i+1)^{\text{th}}$ nodes on the tunnel boundary, as shown in Fig. 3.6, and N_t is the total number of nodes along the tunnel periphery.

3.2.8 Objective function

The search the greatest lower bound collapse load while performing the stress-based limit analysis gives rise to the optimization problem. In such problems, the objective function, i.e., the collapse load is maximized and the collapse load is determined by integrating the normal stresses along the tunnel periphery. Since the present study considers the stresses to vary linearly within an element, the collapse load, Q_j , along a typical element edge on the tunnel boundary can be found numerically as

$$Q_j = \frac{\ell_{s_j}}{2} (\sigma_{n_i} + \sigma_{n_{i+1}}) \quad (3.30)$$

where, ℓ_{s_j} is the length ℓ_s of the element edge j , and the normal stresses σ_{n_i} and $\sigma_{n_{i+1}}$ are as defined in Fig. 3.6. Referring to Fig. 3.6, the above equation can be expressed in the matrix form using 3.12 as

$$Q_j = \underset{1 \times 6}{\mathbf{c}_j} \underset{6 \times 1}{\boldsymbol{\sigma}^j} \quad (3.31)$$

$$\mathbf{c}_j = \frac{\ell_{s_j}}{2} \left[\cos^2 \theta_i \quad \sin^2 \theta_i \quad -\sin 2\theta_i \quad \cos^2 \theta_{i+1} \quad \sin^2 \theta_{i+1} \quad -\sin 2\theta_{i+1} \right]$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}^j = \left\{ \sigma_{x_i}^j \quad \sigma_{z_i}^j \quad \tau_{xz_i}^j \quad \sigma_{x_{i+1}}^j \quad \sigma_{z_{i+1}}^j \quad \tau_{xz_{i+1}}^j \right\}^T$$

If $S = N_t/2$ is the total number of edges along the tunnel periphery, the global matrices shall be obtained using Eq. 3.31:

$$\mathbf{Q} = \sum_{j=1}^S Q_j \quad (3.32)$$

$$\mathbf{C} = \sum_{j=1}^S \mathbf{c}_j \quad (3.33)$$

3.2.9 Mathematical formulation of the Second Order Cone Programming problem

The standard format of the Second-Order Cone Programming problem used in this study can be written as

$$\max \mathbf{c}\mathbf{X} \quad (3.34a)$$

$$\mathbf{B}_l \leq \mathbf{A}\mathbf{X} \leq \mathbf{B}_u \quad (3.34b)$$

$$\mathbf{b}_l \leq \mathbf{X} \leq \mathbf{b}_u \quad (3.34c)$$

where, $\mathbf{c} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbb{C} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix}$; $\mathbf{X} = \left\{ \boldsymbol{\sigma} \quad \boldsymbol{\chi} \right\}^T$. Here

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{3N \times 1} = \left\{ \sigma_{x_1} \quad \sigma_{z_1} \quad \tau_{xz_1} \quad \sigma_{x_2} \quad \sigma_{z_2} \quad \tau_{xz_2} \quad \cdots \quad \sigma_{x_N} \quad \sigma_{z_N} \quad \tau_{xz_N} \right\}^T$$

$$\boldsymbol{\chi}_{3N \times 1} = \left\{ \chi_{11} \quad \chi_{21} \quad \chi_{31} \quad \chi_{12} \quad \chi_{22} \quad \chi_{32} \quad \cdots \quad \chi_{1N} \quad \chi_{2N} \quad \chi_{3N} \right\}^T$$

Furthermore, the matrices \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B}_l , and \mathbf{B}_u are formed from the global matrices defined in equations 3.9, 3.14, 3.17, 3.22, and 3.27:

$$\mathbf{A}_{(2E+4D+2N_b+3N+2N_t) \times (3N+3N)} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_{eq} & \mathbf{0} \\ 2E \times 3N & 2E \times 3N \\ \mathbf{A}_{dc} & \mathbf{0} \\ 4D \times 3N & 4D \times 3N \\ \mathbf{A}_{bc} & \mathbf{0} \\ 2N_b \times 3N & 2N_b \times 3N \\ \mathbf{A}_{yield} & \mathbf{I} \\ 3N \times 3N & 3N \times 3N \\ \mathbf{A}_{int} & \mathbf{0} \\ 2N_t \times 3N & 2N_t \times 3N \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.35)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{B}_1 &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbb{B}_{eq} \\ \mathbb{B}_{dc} \\ \mathbb{B}_{bc} \\ \mathbb{B}_{yield} \\ -\text{inf } \mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix} \\
& \begin{matrix} 2E \times 1 \\ 4D \times 1 \\ 2N_b \times 1 \\ 3N \times 1 \\ 2N_t \times 1 \end{matrix} \\
& \begin{matrix} (2E+4D+2N_b+3N+2N_t) \times 1 \end{matrix} \\
\mathbf{B}_u &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbb{B}_{eq} \\ \mathbb{B}_{dc} \\ \mathbb{B}_{bc} \\ \mathbb{B}_{yield} \\ \mathbb{B}_{int} \end{bmatrix} \\
& \begin{matrix} 2E \times 1 \\ 4D \times 1 \\ 2N_b \times 1 \\ 3N \times 1 \\ 2N_t \times 1 \end{matrix} \\
& \begin{matrix} (2E+4D+2N_b+3N+2N_t) \times 1 \end{matrix}
\end{aligned} \tag{3.36}$$

There are no constraints on the independent variable \mathbf{X} ; hence, $\mathbf{b}_1 = \mathbf{b}_u = \emptyset$. Moreover, \mathbf{I} = identity matrix; E and N are the total number of elements and nodes in the domain, respectively; D is the number of discontinuities within the domain; N_b and N_t are the number of nodes along the domain and tunnel boundaries, respectively; $-\text{inf}$ represents negative infinity.

3.3 Optimization procedure

For performing required computations, the pre-processing computer codes were written in MATLAB (2022), and conic optimization was performed with the help of MOSEK (2022), an optimization toolbox available for MATLAB (2022). To solve second-order cone programming using MOSEK (2022), the input data should be assigned in the format as follows

```

prob.c =  $\mathbf{c}^T$ ;
prob.a =  $\mathbf{A}$ ;
prob.blc =  $\mathbf{B}_l$ ;
prob.buc =  $\mathbf{B}_u$ ;
prob.blx = [];
prob.bux = [];
prob.cones = cell (N, 1);
for j = 1:N
prob.cones{j}.type = 'MSK_CT_QUAD';
prob.cones{j}.sub = [3*N+3*j-2, 3*N+3*j-1, 3*N+3*j];
end
res = mosekopt('maximize', prob);

```

Here, `prob.c = c` defines the objective function, `c`, `prob.a = A` refers to the constraint matrix, \mathbf{A} in Eq. 3.35, `prob.blc = Bl` and `prob.buc = Bu` represent the lower (\mathbf{B}_l) and upper (\mathbf{B}_u) bounds for the constraints from Eq. 3.36, respectively. It facilitates the inclusion of equality and inequality constraints in a single global matrix in MOSEK (2022). `prob.blx = []` and `prob.bux = []` are the lower and upper bounds for the independent variable. Using `mosekopt` in MOSEK (2022), the optimization of the objective function can be optimized after simultaneously solving the primal and dual programming. The optimal collapse load value is obtained using the command `res.sol.itr.pobjval`.

3.4 Applicability of present solutions for materials obeying non-associated flow rule

The computation of collapse load based on lower bound limit analysis using finite element formulation as described in section 3.2, is based on the assumption that stresses are related to plastic strain rates by normality condition or associated flow rule. For materials subjected to undrained loading, the implementation of an associated flow rule is appropriate, whereas, in the case of drained loading conditions, the magnitude of the collapse load computed using the associated flow rule is generally higher as compared to the actual value due to enormous dilation. Nonetheless, for a known dilatancy angle, ψ , the shear strength parameters, that is, cohesion, c , and friction angle, ϕ , for associated flow rule can be replaced with the following modified parameters incorporating the non-associativity (Davis, 1968)

$$\tan \phi_{na} = \frac{\cos \psi \sin \phi}{1 - \sin \psi \sin \phi} \quad (3.37)$$

$$c_{na} = c \left(\frac{\cos \psi \sin \phi}{1 - \sin \psi \sin \phi} \right) \quad (3.38)$$

Drescher and Detournay (1993) verified the applicability of above equations in collapse load computations for lateral earth pressure on retaining walls and bearing capacity of footings.

3.5 Summary

The numerical procedure involved in obtaining the greatest lower bound to the collapse load for the stability of lined tunnels using the finite element coupled lower bound limit analysis technique has been discussed. The plane strain conditions were considered for the analysis. The Mohr-Coulomb yield criterion was modeled to be a Second-Order Conic constraint. Further, the interface condition between the tunnel lining and surrounding soil has been modeled to consider the relative slip of soil during ultimate shearing failure. The framework of the Second-Order Cone Programming (SOCP) has been presented in its standard form along with the MATLAB (2022) algorithm to solve SOCP using the MOSEK (2022) Optimization Toolbox. The scheme to obtain results for materials following the non-associated flow rule from the results developed in this thesis, based on associated flow rule, has been detailed.

4

Single tunnels in cohesive frictional soils

4.1 General

In recent days, tunnels in various infrastructure projects have been increasing. The ground surrounding the tunnel tends to deform, causing instability under different loadings, which is restricted by installing a proper support system. Several researchers have reported extensive damage to the tunnel structures due to earthquakes (Sharma and Judd, 1991; Hashash et al., 2001; Pakbaz and Yareevand, 2005; Yasuda et al., 2019). Thus, support systems for tunnels in seismically active regions should be designed to sustain stresses exerted by the ground under static and seismic conditions. Several studies have assessed the effect of seismic forces on the tunnel structure (Stamos and Beskos, 1996; Wang and Munfakh, 2001; Liu and Song, 2005; Shahrour et al., 2010; Huang et al., 2017; Sun and Dias, 2019). Further, using finite element limit analysis, Sahoo and Kumar (2014) studied the effect of seismicity on circular tunnels using the pseudo-static method. However, the pseudo-static method uses a primitive approach to characterize a complex earthquake motion.

The present chapter aims to evaluate the seismic stability of a circular tunnel placed in a dry, isotropic, homogeneous, cohesive-frictional soil. The seismic forces in the soil domain due to the propagation of seismic waves are calculated using the modified pseudo-dynamic approach, which considers the variation of horizontal and vertical seismic accelerations with time and space. The finite element lower bound limit analysis combined with the second-order cone programming has been used to analyze seismic stability. The minimum support pressure to be provided by the tunnel support systems is computed as the maximum normal stress from its distribution around the periphery. The support pressure variation is influenced by the non-dimensional time and frequency of seismic waves. Furthermore, a thorough parametric study has been conducted from which the importance of decisive parameters like the soil friction angle, soil cohesion, horizontal seismic acceleration coefficient, and tunnel cover depth has been ascertained. Using the velocity distribution in the domain, region of collapse has been studied for static and seismic cases. Moreover, the influence of tunnel's presence in altering horizontal and vertical stresses in the soil domain is also studied. The distribution of normal stresses has been presented for some typical input parameters.

4.2 Problem definition

The present problem consists of analyzing the seismic stability of a circular tunnel of diameter, D , placed at a cover depth, C , in a dry, isotropic, and homogeneous cohesive-frictional soil. The soil parameters include cohesion, c , friction angle, ϕ , and unit weight, γ . The soil domain is accelerated in horizontal and vertical directions due to the propagation of shear and primary waves emerging from the harmonic base shaking. Horizontal and vertical seismic accelerations, represented as $a_h(z, t)/g$ and $a_v(z, t)/g$, vary in space

and time. The ultimate collapse of the cohesive-frictional soil is governed by the Mohr-Coulomb yield criterion and an associated flow rule. The soil parameters are assumed to be unaffected by seismicity. Furthermore, the analysis has been performed considering drained strength parameters, i.e., $c = c'$ and $\phi = \phi'$.

FIGURE 4.1: Description of the present problem.

4.3 Analysis

The finite element lower bound limit analysis method, as explained in Chapter 3, has been used to perform the seismic stability analysis of a circular tunnel in cohesive-frictional soils. For this purpose, the soil continuum is discretized into triangular elements with three nodes, where each node consists of three unknown stresses - σ_x , σ_z , and τ_{xz} . These stresses vary linearly over the element. The node numbers are unique to each element and shared the same coordinates for modeling statically admissible discontinuities along the element edges. Fig. 4.2 shows a typical finite element mesh used to discretize the

soil domain, LMNO. The ground surface (LM) is considered stress-free, i.e., the normal and the shear stresses on the ground surface are zero. The distance of other boundaries, MN, NO, and OL, have been fixed such that it satisfied two criteria: (a) further extending the boundary does not significantly improve the solutions, and (b) yielding zones are contained well within the domain. Furthermore, the present study considers the soil-tunnel interface to be smooth for conservative results (Wang, 1993). Thus, $\tau = 0$ has been imposed along the tunnel periphery.

FIGURE 4.2: A typical finite element mesh with the boundary conditions.

The two-dimensional stress equilibrium equations given in Eq. 3.7 of Chapter 3 have been imposed as an elemental constraint at the centroid of each element. These equations, including the seismic body forces, can be written as

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{xz}}{\partial z} = b_x = \gamma \frac{a_h(z, t)}{g} \quad (4.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \tau_{xz}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \sigma_z}{\partial z} = b_z = \gamma \left[1 - \frac{a_v(z, t)}{g} \right] \quad (4.2)$$

Here $a_h(z, t)/g$ and $a_v(z, t)/g$ are the non-dimensional horizontal and vertical seismic accelerations as functions of space (z) and time (t) imparted to the soil by harmonic base excitation in the horizontal and vertical directions.

Several methods are available to characterize seismic accelerations using simple mathematical expressions, each with their pros and cons. The Pseudo-Static (PS) method (Okabe, 1926; Mononobe and Matsuo, 1929) considers a constant seismic inertia force in terms of seismic acceleration coefficients. Despite being simple and popular, it neglects the amplification effects of local soils, material damping, and phase of seismic accelerations. Steedman and Zeng (1990) proposed the Conventional Pseudo-Dynamic (CPD) method considering the amplification and phase of the horizontal seismic acceleration, which was further extended by Choudhury and Nimbalkar (2006, 2007) for vertical accelerations. The amplification of seismic acceleration was accounted for using a linear function considering an amplification ratio. The CPD method is a fair advancement to account for the amplitude and phase changes and amplification effects in the horizontal and vertical acceleration. Despite these, the CPD method suffers from some fundamental setbacks. First, these acceleration expressions do not satisfy the zero-traction condition on the ground surface (Bellezza, 2014). Second, it is well known that the wave propagation in any medium is affected by its inherent material damping, which is not considered in the CPD method. Lastly, assuming a linear amplification to the seismic acceleration and using arbitrary amplification ratios neglecting the actual ground conditions pose disadvantages to the CPD technique.

Initially, Bellezza (2014) computed the horizontal seismic acceleration undergone by the one-dimensional soil column due to the vertical propagation of shear waves by modeling the soil to be a visco-elastic medium over a rigid bedrock. The constitutive equations of the Kelvin-Voigt medium were used. Later, this formulation was extended by Bellezza (2015) to include the vertical seismic acceleration due to vertically propagating primary waves. The method of seismic analysis proposed by Bellezza (2014, 2015) is referred to as the Modified Pseudo-Dynamic (MPD) method. The important assumptions in the MPD analysis include horizontal ground surface, dry soil, and homogeneous and

isotropic soil. Further, the dynamic properties like the shear modulus and the damping ratio were kept at their small strain values. Major advantages of the MPD method are - zero stress boundary conditions are satisfied, material damping, amplitude, and phase changes in the seismic waves are taken into account, and the amplification of the seismic waves from the bedrock to the ground surface is implicitly considered within the mathematical formulation. Therefore, the assumption of arbitrary amplification ratios is not required. Horizontal and vertical seismic accelerations from the MPD analysis are

$$\frac{a_h(z, t)}{g} = \frac{k_h}{C_s^2 + S_s^2} \left[(C_s C_{sz} + S_s S_{sz}) \cos \left(2\pi \frac{t}{T_s} \right) + (S_s C_{sz} - C_s S_{sz}) \sin \left(2\pi \frac{t}{T_s} \right) \right] \quad (4.3)$$

$$\frac{a_v(z, t)}{g} = \frac{k_v}{C_p^2 + S_p^2} \left[(C_p C_{pz} + S_p S_{pz}) \cos \left(2\pi \frac{t}{T_p} \right) + (S_p C_{pz} - C_p S_{pz}) \sin \left(2\pi \frac{t}{T_p} \right) \right] \quad (4.4)$$

where,

$$C_{sz} = \cos \left(\frac{y_{s1}z}{H} \right) \cosh \left(\frac{y_{s2}z}{H} \right) \quad C_{pz} = \cos \left(\frac{y_{p1}z}{H} \right) \cosh \left(\frac{y_{p2}z}{H} \right) \quad (4.5)$$

$$S_{sz} = -\sin \left(\frac{y_{s1}z}{H} \right) \sinh \left(\frac{y_{s1}z}{H} \right) \quad S_{pz} = -\sin \left(\frac{y_{p1}z}{H} \right) \sinh \left(\frac{y_{p1}z}{H} \right) \quad (4.6)$$

$$C_s = \cos(y_{s1}) \cosh(y_{s2}) \quad C_p = \cos(y_{p1}) \cosh(y_{p2}) \quad (4.7)$$

$$S_s = -\sin(y_{s1}) \sinh(y_{s2}) \quad S_p = -\sin(y_{p1}) \sinh(y_{p2}) \quad (4.8)$$

$$y_{s1} = \frac{\omega_s H}{V_s} \sqrt{\frac{\sqrt{1 + 4\xi_s^2} + 1}{2 + 8\xi_s^2}} \quad y_{p1} = \frac{\omega_p H}{V_p} \sqrt{\frac{\sqrt{1 + 4\xi_p^2} + 1}{2 + 8\xi_p^2}} \quad (4.9)$$

$$y_{s2} = -\frac{\omega_s H}{V_s} \sqrt{\frac{\sqrt{1 + 4\xi_s^2} - 1}{2 + 8\xi_s^2}} \quad y_{p2} = -\frac{\omega_p H}{V_p} \sqrt{\frac{\sqrt{1 + 4\xi_p^2} - 1}{2 + 8\xi_p^2}} \quad (4.10)$$

Here z and t are the depth from the ground surface and time, respectively; H is the total depth of the domain from the ground surface ($z = 0$) to the bedrock ($z = H$); $\omega_s = 2\pi/T_s$ and $\omega_p = 2\pi/T_p$ are angular frequencies of shear and primary waves, respectively;

ξ_s and ξ_p are damping ratios for shear and primary waves, respectively. Also, $\omega_s H/V_s$ and $\omega_p H/V_p$ are the dimensionless frequency of shear and primary waves, respectively. Similarly, t/T_s and t/T_p are the dimensionless time of shear and primary waves. It is to be noted that the wave velocities and damping ratios used in the MPD method are space-time invariant.

It is important to note that seismic accelerations provided in equations 4.3 and 4.4 correspond to *free-field* accelerations. Several studies have reported that the presence of a tunnel attenuates the ground surface acceleration (John and Zahrah, 1987; Cilingir and Madabhushi, 2011; Lanzano et al., 2012; Baziar et al., 2014). Therefore, using the free-field seismic accelerations, given in equations 4.3 and 4.4, for the seismic stability of tunnels ensures conservative results.

In the present thesis, it is assumed that $\omega_p = \omega_s$. This assumption is necessitated to make the analysis simple and does not imply any restraint on the method. Because of this assumption, $T_p = T_s = T \Rightarrow t/T_s = t/T_p = t/T$. Similarly, for brevity, $\xi_s = \xi_p = \xi$ is assumed hereafter. For most of the geomaterials, the Poisson's ratio is equal to 0.3 (Kramer, 2007). Hence, the ratio of primary to shear wave velocity, V_p/V_s , can be calculated as 1.87. Using the ratio of angular frequencies of shear and primary waves, and ratio of wave propagation velocities, the non-dimensional frequency of primary waves can be calculated from the known value of the dimensionless frequency of shear waves as

$$\frac{\omega_p H}{V_p} = \frac{(\omega_s H/V_s) \times (\omega_p/\omega_s)}{V_p/V_s} = \frac{(\omega_s H/V_s) \times 1}{1.87} = \frac{\omega_s H/V_s}{1.87} \quad (4.11)$$

Fig. 4.3 illustrates the variation of horizontal, $a_h(0, t)/g$, and vertical, $a_v(0, t)/g$, in the dimensionless frequency-time ($\omega_s H/V_s - t/T$) domain for $k_h = 0.1$, $k_v = k_h/2$, and $\xi = 10\%$. The horizontal seismic acceleration on the ground surface reaches its peak magnitude near $\omega_s H/V_s = \pi/2$, which corresponds to the fundamental frequency of shear

waves. On the other hand, the magnitude of $a_v(0, t)/g$ soars around $\omega_s H/V_s = 0.94\pi$ corresponding to the primary wave's fundamental frequency ($\omega_p H/V_p = \pi/2$) as per Eq. 4.11.

FIGURE 4.3: (a) Horizontal and (b) vertical seismic acceleration on the ground surface varied in the dimensionless frequency-time domain.

4.4 Validation of the present study

4.4.1 Validation of seismic accelerations

The modified pseudo-dynamic method used in the present study has been validated against the results of Annapareddy et al. (2017) and Qin and Chian (2019). Fig. 4.4(a) validates the non-dimensional horizontal acceleration, $a_h(z, t)/g$, versus z/H for different values of $\omega_s H/V_s$ with Annapareddy et al. (2017). Here, $k_h = 0.1$ and $\xi = 10\%$. Furthermore, 4.4(b) compares the horizontal and vertical amplification ratios in the frequency domain for various damping ratios with Qin and Chian (2019). The amplification ratio is defined as the ratio of the maximum seismic acceleration at the ground surface to the base, which depends only on the damping ratio and dimensionless frequency (Bellezza, 2015). Mathematically,

$$\mathcal{F}_h = \left| \frac{a_h(0, t)}{a_h(H, t)} \right| = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\cos^2(y_{s1}) + \sinh^2(y_{s2})}} \quad (4.12)$$

$$\mathcal{F}_v = \left| \frac{a_v(0, t)}{a_v(H, t)} \right| = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\cos^2(y_{p1}) + \sinh^2(y_{p2})}} \quad (4.13)$$

Here, y_{s1} , y_{p1} , and y_{s2} , y_{p2} are given by equations 4.9 and 4.10, respectively.

FIGURE 4.4: Comparison of the dimensionless horizontal acceleration and amplification ratio of the modified pseudo-dynamic (MPD) analysis from the present study with the available studies.

Fig. 4.5 compares the acceleration profile of maximum horizontal acceleration (at any time) from the present study with the results from centrifuge and numerical studies. For Fig. 4.5(a), the centrifuge study by Lanzano et al. (2012) used the base acceleration of amplitude $0.05g$ and frequency of 0.375 Hz at the model scale. The total depth of the model is 23.2 m, and the shear wave velocity was calculated as 130 m/s from the measured values of shear modulus (25.9 MPa) and density (1550 kg/m³). Further, the damping ratio was reported as 7.8% . Tsinidis et al. (2016) used this motion at the base of the numerical model to obtain the acceleration profile shown. Similarly, for Fig. 4.5(b), the amplitude of base acceleration = $0.15g$, frequency = 0.75 Hz, and shear wave velocity

= 297.1 m/s (Lanzano et al., 2012; Khalajzadeh et al., 2023). The apparent differences in the acceleration profiles stem from the discrepancy in characterizing a non-harmonic base acceleration as a harmonic function in the present study. Nevertheless, using a harmonic base excitation is still a powerful tool for a generalized and comprehensive assessment of the seismic stability of geostructures.

FIGURE 4.5: Comparison of maximum horizontal acceleration from the present study with available centrifuge and numerical studies.

4.4.2 Validation of tunnel support pressure

No literature seems to be available to obtain support pressure considering the variation in both magnitude and phase of earthquake accelerations with time and space owing to the propagation of body waves during an earthquake. Though the static and the pseudo-static solutions are available for the support pressure requirement of circular tunnels (Mair, 1979; Sloan and Assadi, 1992; Lee et al., 1999; Wu and Lee, 2003; Lee et al., 2006; Wilson et al., 2011), these solutions were obtained considering the stresses exerted by the surrounding soil around the tunnel is uniform. Thus, computations were performed by imposing the following constraint in the present analysis for the purpose of validation.

$$\sigma_u = \sigma_{n_1} = \sigma_{n_2} = \dots = \sigma_{n_i} = \sigma_{n_{i+1}} = \dots = \sigma_{n_{N_t}} \quad (4.14)$$

Here σ_u is the support pressure computed imposing the equality of normal stresses around the tunnel periphery. Further, σ_{n_i} and $\sigma_{n_{i+1}}$ are the normal stresses along the i^{th} and $(i + 1)^{\text{th}}$ nodes on the tunnel boundary, and N_t is the total number of nodes along the tunnel periphery.

Fig. 4.6 shows the validation of results from the present analysis with that available in literature under static and pseudo-static loadings. For a purely cohesive soil, $\phi = 0$, Lee et al. (2006) defined the overload factor as $OF = (\sigma_{v0} - p_i)/c$, where, σ_{v0} is the vertical earth pressure at the tunnel center without the tunnel, p_i is the support pressure (uniform), and c is cohesion. According to the nomenclature of the present thesis, at the tunnel center, σ_{v0} can be written as $\gamma(C + D/2)$. Similarly, $p_i = \sigma_u$, from Eq. 4.14. Thus, the overload factor can be expressed using the non-dimensional quantities used in the present thesis as

$$\begin{aligned} OF &= \frac{\sigma_{v0} - p_i}{c} = \frac{1}{c} \left[\gamma \left(C + \frac{D}{2} \right) - \sigma_u \right] \\ &= \frac{\gamma D}{c} \left(\frac{C}{D} + \frac{1}{2} \right) - \frac{\sigma_u}{c} \end{aligned} \quad (4.15)$$

Fig. 4.6(a) compares the overload factor from the present study (Eq. 4.15) with lower bound (LB) limit analysis solutions of Sloan and Assadi (1992); Lee et al. (1999), and Wilson et al. (2011), the upper bound (UB) limit analysis solution of Wu and Lee (2003), centrifuge studies of Mair (1979) and Lee et al. (2006), and the finite difference solution of Lee et al. (2006). For this comparison, $\gamma D/c = 2.6$ has been used. Results from the present study, i.e., the finite element lower bound limit analysis, agrees reasonably with the experimental and lower bound solutions.

For $\gamma D/c = 1$ and 3, Fig. 4.6(b) compares the results for $C/D = 1$, $\phi = 10^\circ$ with the results of Sahoo and Kumar (2014) under the pseudo-static loading. It is to be noted that Sahoo and Kumar (2014) have used the finite element upper bound limit analysis in

conjunction with linear programming techniques. In contrast, the present study uses the finite element lower bound method and second-order conic optimization procedure.

FIGURE 4.6: Comparison of support pressure from the uniform stress condition of the present study with experimental and numerical studies available.

4.5 Uniform vs. Non-uniform stress distribution

The results were obtained in the present thesis without including any additional constraint on the magnitude of normal stress along the tunnel periphery. On the other hand, the analysis performed by imposing the uniformity of normal stresses (Eq. 4.14) will deliver equal magnitudes along the tunnel periphery. Fig. 4.7 compares the stress distribution obtained with and without the uniformity constraint for typical problem parameters. Here, dashed lines, indicated as 'Uniform' represent the distribution obtained using Eq. 4.14, and solid lines, mentioned as 'Non-uniform' are obtained without the aforementioned constraint. It is readily evident that the maximum normal stress obtained from an unconstrained analysis (non-uniform) is higher than using an equality constraint on normal stresses. Moreover, because the uniformity constraint is removed, the stress distribution

from the present study (non-uniform) helps in conceiving the stress conditions that prevail at any segment of the tunnel boundary.

FIGURE 4.7: Comparison of the normal stress (σ_n/c) distribution considering the non-uniform and uniform stress constraints.

Fig. 4.7 reveals some interesting portions along the tunnel periphery. Largely, normal stress estimates from uniform and non-uniform conditions are agreeable near tunnel shoulders ($\theta \approx 30^\circ - 60^\circ$ and $120^\circ - 150^\circ$). The normal stress from the equality constraint underestimates that from the present study (non-uniform) around the tunnel crown ($\theta \approx 60^\circ - 120^\circ$) and spring line ($\theta \approx 150^\circ - 210^\circ$ and $330^\circ - 30^\circ$), and overestimates near the invert ($\theta \approx 210^\circ - 330^\circ$). Thus, using Eq. 4.14 as an additional constraint tends to average the normal stress distribution around the tunnel periphery. While this seems to

be mathematically viable, it obfuscates the comprehensive understanding of the normal stress variation that is imposed by the surrounding soil. Furthermore, it is conservative to use the maximum normal stress obtained from present study's stress distribution to design the tunnel support system. In other words, the lining section is designed to withstand the maximum normal stress imposed by the surrounding soil at its ultimate collapse.

4.6 Results and Discussion

In the present analysis, the support pressure is normalized with the cohesion (c) of the soil as σ_s/c . The influence of soil unit weight, γ , tunnel diameter, D , and cohesion, c , has been considered using the dimensionless quantity $\gamma D/c$. For a given γ and D , an increase in $\gamma D/c$ can be inferred as an decrease in soil cohesion, and vice-versa. On the other hand, for a constant soil cohesion, an increase in $\gamma D/c$ indicates an increase in the overburden pressure in terms of γD . Table 4.1 lists various parameters and their values used in this study. Initially, the influence of the dimensionless frequency and time on the tunnel support pressure is analyzed. Following this, a thorough parametric study has been conducted using representative values of frequency and time to study the effect of other problem parameters. A visual examination of soil collapse around the tunnel is studied using velocity patterns for typical input parameters. Furthermore, the normal stress distribution, and horizontal and vertical stress contours have been studied to strengthen the understanding of soil collapse around tunnels.

TABLE 4.1: List of parameters used in this study and their values.

Parameters	Values
Cover-to-diameter ratio of tunnel	$C/D = 1, 3$
Soil friction angle	$\phi = 5^\circ, 10^\circ, 20^\circ$
Dimensionless ratio of unit weight, tunnel diameter, and cohesion	$\gamma D/c = 1, 3, 5$
Horizontal acceleration coefficient	$k_h = 0, 0.1, 0.2$
Vertical acceleration coefficient	$k_v = 0, k_h/2$
Dimensionless time	$t/T = 0$ to 1
Dimensionless frequency of S wave	$\omega_s H/V_s = 0$ to 2π
Dimensionless frequency of P wave	$\omega_p H/V_p = 0$ to 1.07π
Damping ratio	$\xi = 5\%, 10\%, 15\%$

4.6.1 Effect of dimensionless time and frequency on support pressure

From equations 4.3 and 4.4 it is clear that horizontal and vertical seismic accelerations are proportional to the corresponding non-dimensional frequencies ($\omega_s H/V_s, \omega_p H/V_p$) and time (t/T). Therefore, the tunnel support pressure will also be influenced by the above dependence of seismic accelerations on the dimensionless frequency and time. Figures 4.8, 4.9, and 4.10 show contours of normalized support pressure, σ_s/c , in the domain of the non-dimensional shear wave frequency ($\omega_s H/V_s$) and time (t/T). Here, $k_h = 0.1$ and $k_v = k_h/2$ has been used throughout. For brevity only the shear wave's frequency has been shown in the axis. Using Eq. 4.11, the corresponding values of the non-dimensional frequency of primary waves can be obtained. In these figures, the largest support pressure (σ_s/c) for any time, t/T , found for $\omega_s H/V_s = 0$ to 2π has been plotted to the left-hand side of the contour and labeled as "max σ_s/c wrt t/T ". Similarly, the curve "max σ_s/c wrt $\omega_s H/V_s$ ", plotted below the σ_s/c contour, represents the variation of the largest support pressure for any $\omega_s H/V_s$ along the dimensionless time.

FIGURE 4.8: Contours for the support pressure in the domain of non-dimensional time and frequency, highlighting the effect of the damping ratio. Note: RI = Region of Infeasibility.

Fig. 4.8 considers the influence of the damping ratio in the frequency-time variation of the support pressure. This figure is plotted for $C/D = 1$, $\phi = 5^\circ$, $\gamma D/c = 1$, $\xi = 5\%$ and 15% . In Fig. 4.8(a), RI indicates the Region of Infeasibility in which the solutions were infeasible due to very high magnitude of seismic acceleration. For the input parameters considered in Fig. 4.8, the absolute maximum support pressure occurs near the fundamental frequency of the primary wave, i.e., $\omega_p H/V_p = \pi/2 \Rightarrow \omega_s H/V_s \approx 0.94\pi$, and it is not affected by the damping ratio's magnitude.

Fig. 4.9 explores the influence of $\gamma D/c$ on σ_s/c variation in $\omega_s H/V_s - t/T$ space. Comparing Fig. 4.8(b) with 4.9(a), keeping $\gamma D/c$ to be the same, as the friction angle increases, the effect of shear waves on σ_s/c increases. This is evident by the occurrence of a second peak of σ_s/c near the fundamental frequency of shear waves ($\omega_s H/V_s = \pi/2$). On the other hand, there is single peak of σ_s/c near the P-wave's fundamental frequency as shown in Fig. 4.8.

FIGURE 4.9: For $C/D = 1$, influence of $\gamma D/c$ on the support pressure contour in the dimensionless time and space domain.

Between figures 4.9(a) and (b), $\gamma D/c$ increases from 1 to 5, which represents a decrease in soil cohesion for given values of γ and D . Since the friction angle is kept constant, a lower value of cohesion (higher $\gamma D/c$) in Fig. 4.9(b) indicates a reduction in the shear strength of the soil. Hence, it can be hypothesized that shear waves have the most influence on normalized support pressure where the shear strength is low. On the other hand, for soils of higher shear strength (lower $\gamma D/c$ and/or higher ϕ), the peak normalized support pressure occurs near primary wave's fundamental frequency. The frequency-time response observed in Fig. 4.9, for $C/D = 1$, prevails even for a higher tunnel cover depth ($C/D = 3$) in Fig. 4.10.

In figures 4.8, 4.9, and 4.10, it is interesting to note that the absolute maximum support pressure mostly occurs around $t/T = 0.75$. On the contrary, the absolute minimum support pressure occurs near $t/T = 0.25$. This is because, from Eq. 4.4, the vertical acceleration is positive at $t/T = 0.25$. By the sign conventions used in the present study, a positive vertical acceleration acts upwards, reducing the vertical body force, $b_z = \gamma [1 - a_v(z, t)/g]$ and

the support pressure. Whereas, at $t/T = 0.75$, the vertical acceleration is negative, i.e., downwards, which increases b_z and the support pressure.

FIGURE 4.10: For $C/D = 3$, influence of $\gamma D/c$ on the support pressure contour in the dimensionless time and space domain.

One thing that stands out from the above discussion is that the tunnel support pressure is strongly influenced by the dimensionless frequency and time of seismic waves. A prudent selection of a single value of $\omega_s H/V_s$ and t/T is required to proceed further. Frequency values that resulted in the absolute maximum support pressure cannot be selected as they are near the fundamental frequency of a particular wave. Selecting these values to perform the parametric study will make the results lopsided towards a particular seismic wave. Furthermore, as these values are around the respective fundamental values, the support pressure obtained will be enormous, resulting in an over-conservative design. Nevertheless, unlike selecting the dimensionless frequency, fixing a representative value for t/T is not difficult. From equations 4.3 and 4.4, the base acceleration reaches its maximum magnitude at $t/T = 0, 0.5, \text{ and } 1$. For $\omega_s H/V_s < 0.94\pi$, using $t/T = 0.5$ will result in a negative vertical acceleration (higher vertical body force), rendering the solutions conservative. Therefore, fixing $t/T = 0.5$, the support pressure, σ_s/c , is varied

with dimensionless frequencies, $\omega_s H/V_s$ and $\omega_p H/V_p$, as in Fig. 4.11, for typical problem parameters. Fig. 4.11 confirms the former statement that σ_s/c values using $k_v = k_h/2$ and $t/T = 0.5$ will be conservative for $\omega_s H/V_s < 0.94\pi$. In Fig. 4.11, the critical dimensionless frequency resulting in maximum σ_s/c varies from 0.6π (in Fig. 4.11(c)) to 0.9π (in figures 4.11a, b, and d). Therefore, a representative value of $\omega_s H/V_s = 0.75\pi$ ($\omega_p H/V_p = 0.4\pi$) has been selected such that the influence of both shear and primary waves are included in the forthcoming analysis.

FIGURE 4.11: Non-dimensional variation of support pressure with shear and primary wave frequencies for typical input parameters using $t/T = 0.5$.

4.6.2 Parametric study

Fig. 4.12 illustrates results of the parametric study conducted on the normalized support pressure, σ_s/c , using $\omega_s H/V_s = 0.75\pi$, and $t/T = 0.5$. In general, the normalized support pressure increases with an increase in horizontal acceleration coefficient, k_h , and $\gamma D/c$, and a decrease in soil friction angle, ϕ , and damping ratio, ξ . From Fig. 4.12, four parameters are decisive in determining the seismic support pressure for single tunnels in cohesive-frictional soils - (a) soil friction angle, ϕ , (b) $\gamma D/c$, (c) horizontal seismic acceleration coefficient, k_h , and (d) tunnel cover depth-to-diameter ratio, C/D . The effect of these parameters on the normalized support pressure has been discussed individually. These figures have been plotted considering, $\xi = 10\%$, wherever required. In Fig. 4.12(d), σ_s/c values could not be obtained for $k_h = 0.2$ and $\gamma D/c = 5$ because of high seismic acceleration, higher cover depth-to-diameter ratio ($C/D = 3$), and a lower soil shear strength, i.e., lower friction angle ($\phi = 5^\circ$), and higher $\gamma D/c$ or lower cohesion.

Effect of soil friction angle: An increase in the soil friction angle reduces the tunnel support pressure owing to an increase in the soil shear strength. The sensitivity of normalized support pressure, σ_s/c , to ϕ is presented in Fig. 4.13 using the absolute percentage difference in support pressures. Here, $\Delta_\phi(\sigma_s)$ represents the absolute percentage difference in σ_s/c to the change in ϕ between 5° and 20° . The influence of other parameters like $\gamma D/c$, k_h , and C/D is also presented. It can be seen that the influence of friction angle in σ_s/c is maximum for $\gamma D/c = 1$. As per the Mohr-Coulomb yield criterion ($\tau_f = c + \sigma_n \tan \phi$), the shear strength of soils, τ_f , is contributed by cohesion (c) and frictional resistance to the normal stress, σ_n , (due to ϕ). The insets in Fig. 4.13(a) schematically represent the variation in the Mohr-Coulomb failure envelope due to changes in ϕ . For a given unit weight (γ) and tunnel diameter (D), soil cohesion decreases with $\gamma D/c$.

FIGURE 4.12: Parametric study on the variation of normalized support pressure, $\sigma_s/\gamma D$.

For soils of higher cohesion (lower $\gamma D/c$), the variation in ϕ from 5° to 20° drives the material behavior from nearly cohesive (low ϕ) to cohesive-frictional (high ϕ). On the other hand, for soils of lower cohesion, τ_f is mostly contributed by the frictional resistance, which is not an exorbitant variation in the soil behavior as it is for a higher cohesion. The

aforementioned is reflected in $\Delta_\phi(\sigma_s)$ values in Fig. 4.13 where the support pressure is highly sensitive to friction angle changes for a lower value of $\gamma D/c$ (higher cohesion) as the soil behavior varies from being nearly cohesive to cohesive-frictional. The opposite is true for $\Delta_\phi(\sigma_s)$ when $\gamma D/c = 5$ is considered.

FIGURE 4.13: Effect of soil friction angle: Absolute percentage difference in support pressure, $\Delta_\phi(\sigma_s)$, between $\phi = 5^\circ$ and 20° for (a) $C/D = 1$, and (b) $C/D = 3$.

Tunnels placed at a lower cover depth ($C/D = 1$) in $c - \phi$ soils with a higher $\gamma D/c$ value are the least affected by friction angle changes. However, the support pressure for tunnels at a larger cover depth ($C/D = 3$) is affected considerably by ϕ . The reason for this is, for given γ and D , $\gamma D/c = 5$ implies a lower value of cohesion. Hence, changes in the shear strength is primarily governed by variations in soil friction angle. The influence of soil arching on support pressures increases with the cover depth and ϕ , as discussed in section 4.6.4. Therefore, Fig. 4.13(b) shows that, for $C/D = 3$, the change in support pressure with ϕ is higher for $\gamma D/c = 5$ than for $C/D = 1$ in Fig. 4.13(a).

Effect of $\gamma D/c$: Fig. 4.14 shows the influence of $\gamma D/c$ on tunnel support pressures for $C/D = 1$ and 3, including the effect of k_h and ϕ . Here, the absolute percentage difference in σ_s/c between $\gamma D/c = 1$ and 5 is represented as $\Delta_{\gamma D/c}(\sigma_s)$. For a given C/D , k_h , and ϕ , the normalized support pressure (σ_s/c) increases with $\gamma D/c$. This is because of the drop in cohesion magnitude with $\gamma D/c$, for given γ and D , which reduces the soil's shear strength and increases the normalized support pressure requirement. Nevertheless, Fig. 4.14 indicates that this increment is not uniform for every ϕ and C/D considered in the present study.

FIGURE 4.14: Effect of $\gamma D/c$: Absolute percentage difference in support pressure, $\Delta_{\gamma D/c}(\sigma_s)$, between $\gamma D/c = 1$ and 5 for (a) $C/D = 1$, and (b) $C/D = 3$.

In general, the support pressure for tunnels in soils with a lower friction angle are less sensitive to changes in $\gamma D/c$, and vice versa is true for higher friction angles. Insets in Fig. 4.14(a) schematically illustrate variations in the Mohr-Coulomb failure envelope ($\tau_f = c + \sigma_n \tan \phi$) due to the change in soil cohesion for $\phi = 5^\circ$ and 20° . For soils with lower friction angles, contribution of the frictional resistance to τ_f will be less compared to cohesion, which makes the soil behavior mostly cohesive. On the contrary, for soils with higher friction angles, the change in soil cohesion will ensure substantial contribution from cohesion and frictional resistance to τ_f . In other words, for soils with higher friction angles, the change in cohesion takes the material behavior from being nearly frictional

(lower cohesion) to cohesive-frictional (high cohesion). Because of the above-mentioned change in the contributing factors for τ_f , the support pressure shows an increased sensitivity to the change in soil cohesion for a higher ϕ value in Fig. 4.14.

Effect of horizontal acceleration coefficient, k_h : The seismic horizontal acceleration coefficient, k_h , is proportional to the amplitude of seismic horizontal acceleration at the base, i.e., $a_h(H, t) \propto k_h g$. Hence, an increase in k_h increases the horizontal body force throughout the domain. It is to be noted that, in the present study, the vertical acceleration coefficient, k_v , is defined as a function of k_h . Therefore, increment in k_h affects both horizontal and vertical body forces. In general, the tunnel support pressure increases with k_h . The absolute percentage difference in σ_s/c for the variation in k_h from 0 to 0.1, $\Delta_{k_h}(\sigma_s)$, is shown in Fig. 4.15 for $C/D = 1$ and 3 including the effect of ϕ and $\gamma D/c$. Fig. 4.15 can be interpreted as the influence of considering seismic forces in the analysis as k_h is varied between 0 (static) and 0.1 (seismic).

FIGURE 4.15: Effect of k_h : Absolute percentage difference in support pressure, $\Delta_{k_h}(\sigma_s)$, between $k_h = 0$ and 0.1 for (a) $C/D = 1$, and (b) $C/D = 3$.

Largely, the support pressure shows substantial variations to k_h for tunnels in soils with higher friction angles. The hypothesis is that, for lower ϕ values, the shear resistance is dominated by soil cohesion, imparting an increased resistance to seismic forces. Fig.

4.15 shows that, unlike the effect of ϕ , the influence of $\gamma D/c$ is not straightforward, and the tunnel cover depth-to-diameter (C/D) has a role to play. Consider Fig. 4.15(a) for tunnels with a lower C/D . Here, the support pressure shows an increased variation to seismicity for a higher $\gamma D/c$. For any ϕ value, a lower $\gamma D/c$ indicates a higher cohesion, which increases soil's resistance to seismic forces. Thus, from Fig. 4.15(a), the support pressure is not much influenced by seismicity for $\gamma D/c = 1$. Contrary to the above, tunnels in soils with a lower cohesion (higher $\gamma D/c$) are more vulnerable to seismicity. For a higher C/D value, Fig. 4.15(b) shows that the influence of seismicity on tunnel support pressure is maximum for $\gamma D/c = 1$. The reason for an anomalous surge in support pressure's sensitivity to k_h lies in the fact that σ_s/c reduces with C/D for a lower $\gamma D/c$ (refer to Fig. 4.12). This drop in σ_s/c with C/D is maximum for the static case. The implication of this decrement in σ_s/c on the normal stress distribution is discussed in the upcoming paragraph. From Fig. 4.12(a), for $C/D = 1$, $\phi = 5^\circ$, and $\gamma D/c = 1$, σ_s/c increases from 4.14 to 4.40 as k_h varies from 0 to 0.1, i.e., $\Delta_{k_h}(\sigma_s) = 5\%$ (refer to Fig. 4.15(a)). On the other hand, because of the aforementioned reduction in the support pressure with C/D , σ_s/c varies from 2.13 to 3.15 as k_h increases from 0 to 0.1 (refer to Fig. 4.12(d) for $\gamma D/c = 1$). Hence, the corresponding value of $\Delta_{k_h}(\sigma_s)$, from Fig. 4.15(b), is about 50%. For a higher $\gamma D/c$ value, Fig. 4.12 shows that the decrease of σ_s/c with C/D is less. Thus, $\Delta_{k_h}(\sigma_s)$ values for $\gamma D/c = 3$ and 5 from Fig. 4.15(b) are comparable with Fig. 4.15(a).

Effect of tunnel cover depth-to-diameter ratio, C/D : From Fig. 4.12, at large, the normalized support pressure increases with C/D . However, for lower friction angle and $\gamma D/c$ (higher cohesion), σ_s/c drops with C/D . This is noticeable for $k_h = 0$, and the support pressure is "regained" for seismic conditions. Fig. 4.16 investigates the influence of C/D in terms of non-dimensional normal stresses - maximum, $\sigma_{n,max}/c = \sigma_s/c$, minimum, $\sigma_{n,min}/c$, and uniform, σ_u/c (Eq. 4.14). For this demonstration, the tunnel cover depth-to-diameter ratio has been varied as 1, 3, and 5, and $k_h = 0$ has been considered.

FIGURE 4.16: Effect of C/D : Non-dimensional normal stress variations for static loading.

From Fig. 4.16(a), for lower friction angle and higher cohesion ($\gamma D/c = 1$), the maximum normal stress decreases and minimum normal stress increases with C/D , approaching the uniform value obtained by imposing the constraint in Eq. 4.14 along the tunnel periphery. For $\gamma D/c = 1$ and $\phi = 20^\circ$, Fig. 4.16(b) indicates that dimensionless normal stresses are negligibly affected by C/D . This is due to the increased shear strength of the soil because of a higher friction angle and soil cohesion. Contrary to the above, figures 4.16(c) and (d) indicate that all three normal stress magnitudes increase with C/D owing to a higher $\gamma D/c$ (lower cohesion). Thus, it can be said that, when the soil friction angle is low and cohesion is high, i.e., when the shear strength is predominantly contributed by

soil cohesion, the normal stress distribution tends to be equal around the tunnel periphery as C/D increases. The above uniform tending nature of normal stresses decreases with the horizontal acceleration coefficient, k_h and soil friction angle, and vanishes for a higher $\gamma D/c$.

4.6.3 Collapse patterns

Ciria et al. (2008) stated that static and kinematic limit analysis problems have strong duality, and MOSEK (2022) has exploited this duality using an efficient primal-dual interior point algorithm (Andersen et al., 2003). It is to be noted that the primal and dual problems compute stresses and velocities, respectively. The present study uses MOSEK (2022) toolbox to find a statically admissible stress state via the lower bound analysis from which tunnel support pressures were computed. The lower bound theorem leads to a maximization problem where the collapse load is maximized. On the other hand, the upper bound theorem results in a minimization problem. In optimization theory, if the lower bound problem is defined as the primal, then the upper bound problem is dual. The dual problem has characteristics similar to those of a primal problem, and the optimal solution can be obtained by solving either of them (Rao, 2013). Out of several methods to solve an optimization problem, interior-point algorithms are quite efficient in finding the optimal solution. The optimization solver used in the present study, i.e., MOSEK (2022), uses the interior-point algorithm to solve the primal and dual optimization problems at the same time. Because of this, both stress state (primal problem – lower bound theorem) and velocity vectors (dual problem – upper bound theorem) are computed across the soil domain simultaneously. The distribution of velocity vectors over the medium provides a visual indication of the collapse region around tunnels.

Figures 4.17 and 4.18 shows the collapse pattern for static and seismic cases, respectively, enunciating the influence of $\gamma D/c$, soil friction angle (ϕ), and tunnel cover depth-to-diameter ratio (C/D). Fig. 4.17 indicates that the collapse pattern for static loading is symmetric about a vertical through the tunnel center. Furthermore, the extent of soil collapse reduces with the friction angle due to an increase in soil's shear strength.

FIGURE 4.17: Collapse patterns for static loadings using (a) $\phi = 5^\circ$, and (b) 20° .

Contrary to the above, Fig. 4.18 shows that the seismic loading renders the collapse pattern asymmetric, apart from increasing its extent. Moreover, the collapse pattern's extent increases with $\gamma D/c$. The decrement in soil cohesion, thereby the soil shear strength, is the reason for the above increase. Similar to the static case, soil region under imminent collapse reduces with the friction angle. Fig. 4.18(d) illustrates that there is a corresponding increase in the extent of soil collapse for tunnels placed at a higher cover depth-to-diameter ratio.

The reason for right-skewed collapse patterns in Fig. 4.18 can be explained using the resultant acceleration field. Employing the theory of vector algebra, the magnitude and direction of the resultant of horizontal and vertical accelerations can be computed as

$$\text{Magnitude : } \frac{a_r(z, t)}{g} = \sqrt{\left[\frac{a_h(z, t)}{g}\right]^2 + \left[\frac{a_v(z, t)}{g}\right]^2} \quad (4.16)$$

$$\text{Direction : } \vartheta(z, t) = \tan^{-1} \left| \frac{a_v(z, t)/g}{a_h(z, t)/g} \right| \quad (4.17)$$

FIGURE 4.18: Collapse patterns for seismic loadings highlighting the effect of $\gamma D/c$, friction angle, and tunnel cover depth-to-diameter ratio.

Since seismic horizontal and vertical accelerations vary with depth and time, the resultant acceleration's magnitude and direction are also functions of depth and time. Considering the assumption in the present study that the seismic accelerations are invariant along the X-axis, the variation of $a_r(z, t)/g$ and ϑ along the entire domain can be plotted. Such plots offer a succinct representation of the seismic acceleration field prevalent in the medium. Fig. 4.19 shows the resultant acceleration field for $C/D = 1$ and 3 using $k_h = 0.1$, $k_v = k_h/2$, $t/T = 0.5$, $\omega_s H/V_s = 0.75\pi$, and $\xi = 10\%$. Here the contour map of resultant acceleration's magnitude, $a_r(z, t)/g$, is superimposed with streamlines indicating the direction, $\vartheta(z, t)$. By projecting the streamlines in Fig. 4.19 on the horizontal plane, it can be found that the horizontal acceleration acts along the positive X-axis in tunnel's vicinity, which explains the right-skewed collapse patterns in Fig. 4.18.

FIGURE 4.19: Resultant acceleration field for (a) $C/D = 1$, and (b) $C/D = 3$.

4.6.4 Horizontal and vertical stress contours

Figures 4.20 and 4.21 show the non-dimensional horizontal, σ_x/c , and vertical, σ_z/c , stress contours for static and seismic cases highlighting the effect of $\gamma D/c$, soil friction angle, ϕ , and tunnel cover depth-to-diameter ratio, C/D . The corresponding collapse patterns indicating the yielding region is plotted using dashed lines. The vertical stress contours in these figures illustrate the transfer of stresses from the yielding region to the adjoining non-yielding region at ultimate collapse due to soil arching.

FIGURE 4.20: Dimensionless horizontal and vertical stress contours for the static case.

FIGURE 4.21: For $k_h = 0.1$, dimensionless horizontal and vertical stress contours showing the effect of $\gamma D/c$, friction angle, and tunnel cover depth-to-diameter ratio.

Horizontal and vertical stress contours in Fig. 4.20 are symmetrical about a vertical through tunnel center because of static loading. Here, the maximum horizontal stress decreases with soil friction angle, whereas the magnitude of σ_z/c in the non-yielding portion increases with ϕ . Thus, the influence of soil arching increases with the friction angle. On the other hand, Fig. 4.21 show that seismicity skews the stress distribution along the predominant direction of seismic horizontal acceleration (refer to Fig. 4.19). Fig. 4.21(b) illustrates that aberrations in horizontal and vertical stresses due to tunnel's presence is

less compared to Fig. 4.21(a). This is because both soil friction angle and cohesion (high $\gamma D/c$) are low in Fig. 4.21(b). Furthermore, figures 4.21(c) and (d) indicate that the magnitude of vertical stress transferred to the non-yielding region increases with soil friction angle and tunnel cover depth.

4.6.5 Distribution of normal stresses around the tunnel periphery

The current section discusses the distribution of normal stress around tunnel periphery for typical input parameters under static and seismic loadings, as shown in figures 4.22 and 4.23. The representation has been made using polar plots with normal stress as the radius. The angle in these figures indicate the angle subtended by radial lines emanating from the tunnel center with horizontal. Due to the symmetric nature of the static loading, normal stress distributions in Fig. 4.22 are symmetric about the vertical through tunnel center. On the other hand, Fig. 4.23 plotted for seismic cases indicate that the location of maximum normal stress is aligned with the horizontal acceleration's direction in tunnel's vicinity, and distributions are lopsided. It can be inferred from figures 4.22(a), 4.22(c), 4.23(a), and 4.23(c) that, for a lower soil friction angle, the maximum normal stress occurs around the crown for $C/D = 1$ and spring line for $C/D = 3$. Contrary to the above, from figures 4.22(b), 4.22(d), 4.23(b), and 4.23(d), tunnel section around the springline is vulnerable for higher friction angles under any C/D value. Fig. 4.23 highlights that the role of seismicity in making the normal stress distribution asymmetric is noticeable for a higher friction angle and $\gamma D/c$ (lower cohesion). In connection to the above, the distribution in Fig. 4.23(a) says that the normal stress distribution for tunnels placed in a cohesive-frictional soil with a lower friction angle and a higher cohesion (lower $\gamma D/c$) is negligibly altered from its static distribution due to seismicity. This is in-line with the observation made in Fig. 4.15 that a high soil cohesion and low friction angle reduces the seismic impact on support pressure.

FIGURE 4.22: Normal stress distribution, σ_n/c for static loadings highlighting the effect of friction angle, $\gamma D/c$, and tunnel cover depth.

4.7 Summary

The present chapter analyzed the seismic stability of circular tunnels in isotropic, homogeneous, cohesive-frictional soils using the finite element lower bound limit analysis method and second-order cone programming. The seismic body forces were accounted for using the modified pseudo-dynamic method in which shear and primary waves propagating in a homogeneous medium due to harmonic base shaking are considered. The maximum normal stress occurring anywhere along the tunnel periphery was reported as the support pressure that the lining systems should resist at ultimate state. The support pressure was normalized using soil cohesion and expressed as σ_s/c . Further, the interplay

of soil unit weight, cohesion, and tunnel diameter was accounted for using $\gamma D/c$. It was found that the normalized support pressure was most affected by shear waves for high $\gamma D/c$ (low cohesion) and primary waves, otherwise. Largely, σ_s/c increased with the horizontal acceleration coefficient, k_h , and $\gamma D/c$, and decreased with soil friction angle, ϕ and damping ratio, ξ . For tunnels in soils with high cohesion and low friction angle, the normal stress distribution tended to be equal throughout the tunnel periphery as the cover depth-to-diameter ratio (C/D) increased. Typical collapse patterns, horizontal and vertical stress contours, and normal stress distributions were shown for static and seismic cases.

FIGURE 4.23: Effect of seismicity on the normal stress distribution, σ_n/c , around the tunnel periphery including the influence of friction angle, $\gamma D/c$, and tunnel cover depth.

5

Single tunnels in anisotropic granular soils with ground surcharge

5.1 General

After many field investigations it has been established that tunnels suffer severe damages because of earthquakes (Wang et al., 2001; Li, 2012; Yu et al., 2016). Also, several researchers have studied the devastating effects of earthquake events on the stability of underground tunnels in various soil conditions using experimental and numerical techniques (Wang and Munfakh, 2001; Cilingir and Madabhushi, 2011; Sahoo and Kumar, 2014; Tsinidis et al., 2016; Sun and Dias, 2019). The literature shows no investigations on support pressure for tunnel stability in granular soil under seismic forces. Granular soil layers behave anisotropically (Casagrande and Carrillo, 1944; Meyerhof, 1978; Yamada and Ishihara, 1979; Xiong et al., 2015), and its response under static loading has been examined (Kumar and Sahoo, 2020). However, the effect of anisotropy under seismic loading needs to be explored. Studies have been established considering surcharge loading on the ground surface under static conditions (Yamamoto et al., 2011, 2013; Yang et al., 2017; Xiao et al., 2019b). However, seismic stability analysis with surcharge is

missing. Thus, an investigation is needed to estimate the support pressure of circular tunnels in anisotropic granular soil with applied ground surcharge under seismic loading.

The present chapter analyzes circular tunnel's seismic stability in anisotropic granular soil with surcharge loading at the ground surface. Horizontal and vertical seismic accelerations imposed due to in-plane vertically propagating shear and primary waves from the modified pseudo-dynamic method have been used. After studying the influence of dimensionless time and frequency of seismic waves on the support pressure, a comprehensive parametric study has been performed to analyze the effect of tunnel cover depth, soil friction angle, anisotropic coefficient, magnitude of surcharge, and seismic acceleration coefficients. Collapse patterns, and horizontal and vertical stress contours have been presented to visualize the extent of soil collapse and soil arching for typical input parameters. Furthermore, the normal stress distribution around tunnel periphery has been plotted. An attempt has been made to compare the seismic stability of tunnels in granular and cohesive-frictional soils to establish the influence of soil cohesion.

5.2 Problem description

Fig. 5.1 shows the schematic representation of the present problem, i.e., the seismic stability of a circular tunnel of diameter D at a cover depth C from the ground surface. The surrounding granular soil is dry, homogeneous and anisotropic with respect to its friction angle, ϕ , and its unit weight is denoted as γ . The ground surface is subjected to a continuous surcharge of magnitude q . Based on a plane strain analysis, the support pressure, σ_s , to be provided by the tunnel support systems at the ultimate collapse of the surrounding soil is estimated. The support pressure, σ_s , is found as the maximum normal stress imposed by the surrounding soil on the tunnel periphery. The horizontal and vertical seismic accelerations, $a_h(z, t)/g$ and $a_v(z, t)/g$, respectively, are generated due

to propagation of shear and primary waves vary in space and time. These horizontal and vertical seismic accelerations vary in space-time. In the present study, the soil yielding is governed by the Mohr-Coulomb failure criterion following the associated flow rule. The soil parameters are assumed not to be affected by seismic loading.

FIGURE 5.1: Schematic representation of a circular tunnel in a granular medium of anisotropic friction angle with a ground surcharge and subjected to seismic body waves.

5.3 Analysis

Following the general procedure explained in Chapter 3, the present study utilizes the finite element lower bound limit analysis method to study the seismic stability of tunnels in granular medium. Here, soil is discretized to linear triangular elements with three unknown stresses at each node, σ_x , σ_z , and τ_{xz} . Fig. 5.2 shows a typical finite element mesh that discretizes the chosen soil domain LMNO along with the boundary conditions. In the current study, the boundaries of the domain, that is, MN, NO, and OL, have been kept far apart from the tunnel such that the following conditions are met: the boundaries do not

interfere with the collapse zone, and a further relocation of the edges does not improve the solution. The ground surface, LM, is subjected to normal and shear boundary conditions as shown in Fig. 5.2. Furthermore, the present study considers the soil-tunnel interface to be smooth for conservative results (Wang, 1993). Thus, $\tau = 0$ has been imposed along the tunnel periphery.

FIGURE 5.2: A typical finite element mesh with boundary conditions for $C/D = 3$.

Bellezza (2014, 2015) computed horizontal and vertical seismic accelerations assuming a stress-free ground surface. These have been incorporated into horizontal and vertical body forces in the equilibrium constraint, as given in equations 4.1 and 4.2. Kokane et al. (2021) showed that the acceleration profile of propagating waves is independent of the surcharge. At the i^{th} node on the ground surface, the normal and shear stresses owing to the inertia of the dimensionless surcharge ($q/\gamma D$) have been imposed as follows:

$$\sigma_{n_i} = \frac{q}{\gamma D} \times \left[1 - \frac{a_v(0, t)}{g} \right] \quad (5.1)$$

$$\tau_i = \frac{q}{\gamma D} \times \left[\frac{a_h(0, t)}{g} \right] \quad (5.2)$$

where $q/\gamma D =$ dimensionless ground surcharge; $a_h(0, t)$ and $a_v(0, t)$ are dimensionless horizontal and vertical acceleration values calculated at the ground surface ($z = 0$), respectively. Referring to Eq. 3.16 of Chapter 3, for a horizontal ground surface, the local coefficient matrix \mathbf{A}_{bc}^{bd} at a typical node along the horizontal boundary bd can be expressed as follows:

$$\mathbf{A}_{bc}^{bd} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.3)$$

Similarly, the vector \mathbf{b}_{bc}^{bd} in Eq. 3.16 is formed using σ_{n_i} and τ_i from equations 5.1 and 5.2.

The soil experiences an induced anisotropy condition resulting from changing the principal stress direction during shearing under different loading directions. Even though the friction angle changes with the major principal stress direction, Meyerhof (1978) suggested an equivalent friction angle (ϕ), which remains constant in all directions, in terms of the maximum and minimum friction angle values ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 , respectively, as follows

$$\phi = \frac{1}{3} (2 + m) \phi_1 \quad (5.4)$$

where $m = \phi_2/\phi_1 =$ anisotropic coefficient; and ϕ_1 and $\phi_2 =$ maximum and minimum friction angle values, respectively. The maximum friction angle ϕ_1 shall be obtained from the drained triaxial test with the deviatoric stress along the vertical direction that is perpendicular to the bedding plane. Similarly, the minimum friction angle ϕ_2 can be obtained by conducting the drained triaxial test with deviatoric stress parallel to the bedding plane (Meyerhof, 1978).

5.4 Validation of support pressure

To the best of authors' knowledge there exists no study to estimate the seismic stability of circular tunnels in granular soils. Thus, the results obtained from the current analysis under static loadings for isotropic soil condition are compared with the theoretical (lower and upper bound methods) and centrifuge results of Atkinson and Potts (1977) as shown in Fig. 5.3(a). The present results are in between theoretical lower and upper bounds and are coherent with centrifuge results of Atkinson and Potts (1977). Furthermore, the anisotropic formulation used in the present study to evaluate tunnel stability has been validated with the results of Kumar and Sahoo (2020) under static condition, as shown in Fig. 5.3(b), and found to be consistent. It needs to be noted that the solutions of Atkinson and Potts (1977) and Kumar and Sahoo (2020) were obtained considering the stresses exerted by the surrounding soil around the tunnel is uniform. Thus, the present solutions were obtained by imposing the constraint given in Eq. 4.14 of Chapter 4 in the analysis for validation purposes. The parameter $\sigma_u/\gamma D$ in Fig. 5.3 represents the non-dimensional support pressure obtained by imposing the aforementioned equality constraint.

FIGURE 5.3: Comparison of support pressure from the uniform stress distribution, $\sigma_u/\gamma D$, from the present study with the available results.

5.5 Uniform and non-uniform stress distribution

Fig. 5.4 explores the consequence of utilizing the equality constraint (Eq. 4.14) to compute the support pressure under seismicity. Let $\sigma_u/\gamma D$ and $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ be the normalized support pressure obtained based on the uniform and non-uniform stress conditions, respectively. The effect of the anisotropy parameter, m , normalized surcharge, $q/\gamma D$, and maximum friction angle, ϕ_1 , is studied in figures 5.4(a) and (b). It is evident from figures 5.4(a) and (b) that the support pressure, $\sigma_s/\gamma D$, computed without any constraint is higher than that using the equality constraint, $\sigma_u/\gamma D$.

Fig. 5.4(c) shows the normal stress distribution for $m = 1$ and $\phi_1 = 30^\circ$, considering the effect of $q/\gamma D$, from uniform and non-uniform stress conditions. The uniform stress condition assumes normal stresses along the tunnel periphery to be constant, which is evident in Fig. 5.4(c). On the other hand, normal stresses from the present study without any constraints are not equal. For the input parameters considered in Fig. 5.4(c), there exists three zones of interest - Zone 1, where the uniform stress estimate seems to match with the non-uniform near tunnel shoulders, i.e., $\theta = 30^\circ - 60^\circ$ and $\theta = 120^\circ - 150^\circ$. In Zone 2, the uniform stress condition underestimates the normal stresses imposed near the tunnel crown ($\theta \approx 90^\circ$) and spring line ($\theta \approx 0^\circ$ and 180°). On the other hand, in Zone 3, the uniform condition overestimates the normal stresses in the vicinity of the tunnel haunch and invert ($\theta = 210^\circ - 330^\circ$). A schematic representation of these zones around the tunnel perimeter is also provided in Fig. 5.4(c).

FIGURE 5.4: Variation of support pressure based on the (a) uniform, and (b) non-uniform stress condition; (c) Comparison of normal stress distribution with (uniform) and without (non-uniform) the equality constraint.

5.6 Results and Discussion

The support pressure, σ_s , from the present study is normalized with soil unit weight, γ , and tunnel diameter, D , which is expressed as $\sigma_s/\gamma D$. Table 5.1 lists parameters and values used in the present study. As stated in section 4.3 of Chapter 4, the following are assumed - shear and primary waves have equal angular frequencies ($\omega_s = \omega_p \Rightarrow t/T_s = t/T_p = t/T$), ratio of the primary to shear wave velocity, V_p/V_s , is 1.87, and damping ratios for shear and primary waves are same ($\xi_s = \xi_p = \xi$).

Initially, the effect of non-dimensional time (t/T) and frequencies ($\omega_s H/V_s$ and $\omega_p H/V_p$) on the normalized support pressure $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ has been analyzed. Utilizing a representative value of t/T and $\omega_s H/V_s$, a comprehensive parametric study has been made to understand the effect of C/D , ϕ_1 , $q/\gamma D$, m , and k_h on $\sigma_s/\gamma D$. Collapse patterns and soil arching are studied to understand the effect of tunnel cover depth, ground surcharge, friction angle's anisotropy, and seismicity. Later, the normal stress variation around the tunnel periphery has been visualized for typical input parameters. Furthermore, an attempt has been made to compare seismic stability of tunnels in granular and cohesive-frictional soils for typical cases, establishing the effect of soil cohesion.

TABLE 5.1: List of parameters used in the present study.

Parameter	Values
Cover-to-diameter ratio of tunnel	$C/D = 1$ and 3
Maximum friction angle	$\phi_1 = 30^\circ, 35^\circ, 40^\circ, 45^\circ$
Anisotropic coefficient	$m = 0.6, 0.8, 1$
Normalized surcharge	$q/\gamma D = 0, 0.5, 1$
Horizontal acceleration coefficient	$k_h = 0, 0.1, 0.2$
Vertical acceleration coefficient	$k_v = 0, k_h/2$
Dimensionless time	$t/T = 0 - 1$
Dimensionless frequency of S wave	$\omega_s H/V_s = 0 - 2\pi$
Dimensionless frequency of P wave	$\omega_p H/V_p = 0 - 1.07\pi$
Damping ratio	$\xi = 10\%$

5.6.1 Effect of the dimensionless time and frequency on support pressure

The support pressure depends on seismic accelerations, which are influenced by the dimensionless time, t/T , and frequency $\omega_s H/V_s$ and $\omega_p H/V_p$. Figures 5.5 and 5.6 show the variation of normalized support pressure, $\sigma_s/\gamma D$, in the $\omega_s H/V_s - t/T$ domain. In

these figures, $k_h = 0.1$, and $k_v = k_h/2$ have been used. Owing to extreme seismic accelerations, the numerical model resulted in infeasible results near shear wave's fundamental frequency for some cases due to dynamic shear fluidization of sands (Richards et al., 1990), and these regions have been mentioned as the Region of Infeasibility (RI) in figures 5.5 and 5.6. Here, $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ contours have been plotted considering only the dimensionless shear wave frequency, $\omega_s H/V_s$, for brevity. However, for a known value of $\omega_s H/V_s$, the non-dimensional primary wave frequency can be found using Eq. 4.11. Thus, $\omega_p H/V_p = \pi/2$ correspond to the fundamental mode for primary waves, and the corresponding value of $\omega_s H/V_s = 0.94\pi$. Furthermore, the curve "max $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ wrt t/T " provides the variation of maximum support pressure, for any t/T , with the dimensionless frequency, $\omega_s H/V_s$. Similarly, the curve "max $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ wrt $\omega_s H/V_s$ " is plotted using the maximum value of $\sigma_s/\gamma D$, for any $\omega_s H/V_s$, along the non-dimensional time.

Fig. 5.5 illustrates support pressure contours for the tunnel cover depth-to-diameter ratio, $C/D = 1$, highlighting the effect of anisotropy ratio (m), and maximum friction angle (ϕ_1). Here, $q/\gamma D = 0$ has been used. Fig. 5.5(a) shows that, for $\phi = 30^\circ$ and $m = 1$ (isotropic soil), the peak magnitude of support pressure occurs near the shear wave's fundamental frequency, $\omega_s H/V_s = \pi/2$. Moreover, the second peak of $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ occurs near the fundamental vibration mode of primary waves, i.e., $\omega_s H/V_s = 0.94\pi \Rightarrow \omega_p H/V_p = \pi/2$ (refer to Eq. 4.11). Comparing figures 5.5(a) and (b), the anisotropy ratio has been reduced from $m = 1$ to 0.6, and the first or global peak of $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ is near shear wave's fundamental frequency. However, Fig. 5.5(b) shows that the second peak of $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ occurs not around P-wave's fundamental frequency but near the second natural frequency of S-waves ($\omega_s H/V_s = 3\pi/2$). Fixing the anisotropy ratio, $m = 0.6$, the maximum friction angle has been increased from $\phi_1 = 30^\circ$ to 45° in Fig. 5.5(c). Here, first and second peaks of the support pressure occurs near the fundamental frequency of shear and primary waves, respectively. Thus, it can be inferred that, for $C/D = 1$, the support pressure is

most affected by shear waves, and primary wave's influence is considerable for a higher value of the equivalent friction angle, ϕ (higher ϕ_1 and/or m).

FIGURE 5.5: Support pressure variation in the dimensionless time-frequency domain for $C/D = 1$ highlighting the effect of anisotropy ratio and maximum friction angle.

Fig. 5.6 has been plotted considering $C/D = 3$, and it highlights the influence of maximum friction angle and ground surcharge. From figures 5.5(b) and 5.6(a), even though the tunnel cover depth-to-diameter ratio increases, support pressure's global peak is around

shear wave's fundamental frequency, i.e., still shear waves are influential for support pressure determination. On the other hand, primary wave's influence on $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ has increased in Fig. 5.6(a) compared to Fig. 5.5(b). This is due to the occurrence of a second peak near $\omega_s H/V_s = 0.94\pi$ in Fig. 5.6(a). Fig. 5.6(b) shows that increasing the ground surcharge magnitude does not alter the type of seismic wave that influences the support pressure. In other words, for $q/\gamma D = 1$, the peak support pressure is still near shear wave's fundamental frequency. Figures 5.6(c) and (d) say that primary waves influence $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ the most for tunnels placed at a larger cover depth in granular soils with a higher equivalent friction angle (ϕ).

In summary, while shear waves are dominant in seismic stability of tunnels with shallower cover depth, the primary wave's influence cannot be ignored for tunnels placed at a higher cover depth in soils with a higher equivalent friction angle. Table 5.2 provides a succinct information on the above-said summary. The observation from the present study that the support pressure for shallow tunnels is highly influenced by shear waves is in accordance with previous findings (Sharma and Judd, 1991; Luco and Barros, 1994; Lanzano et al., 2012; Moghadam and Baziar, 2016). For tunnels at a greater cover depth, the soil shear strength, in terms of equivalent friction angle, plays an important role. Thus, the support pressure for tunnels in granular soils with a low ϕ value is influenced by shear waves, whereas P-waves have a higher influence for higher equivalent friction angles.

TABLE 5.2: Summary of the dominance of seismic waves on the support pressure of tunnels in granular soils.

Equivalent friction angle, ϕ	Cover depth-to-diameter ratio, C/D	
	Low	High
Low	S-wave	S-wave
High	S-wave	P-wave

FIGURE 5.6: Support pressure variation in the dimensionless time-frequency domain for $C/D = 3$ highlighting the effect of ground surcharge.

It is evident from figures 5.5 and 5.6 that support pressure is substantially affected by the value of $\omega_s H / V_s$ and t/T used for the analysis. The critical value of the dimensionless frequency from figures 5.5 and 5.6 that resulted in peak $\sigma_s / \gamma D$ cannot be used for the parametric study as they are close to one of the fundamental frequency. On the other hand, figures 5.5 and 5.6 show that, for many cases, the critical dimensionless time that resulted in a peak support pressure is near $t/T = 0.25$ or 0.75 . From equations 4.3 and

4.4, the base seismic acceleration reach near zero magnitudes around $t/T = 0.25$ and 0.75 . On the other hand, Fig. 4.3 indicates that ground acceleration magnitudes surge near the aforementioned dimensionless times, which represent "resonance". Therefore, using $t/T = 0.25$ and 0.75 along with critical dimensionless frequencies from figures 5.5 and 5.6 will exacerbate the support pressure estimation due to very high seismic accelerations. Nonetheless, selection of a representative value of $\omega_s H/V_s$ and t/T for the parametric study is very important as they are decisive in "representing" the influence of each seismic wave. It should also be ensured that these representative values provide feasible solutions. For this purpose, $t/T = 0.5$ has been selected as it ensures a maximum base acceleration ($-k_{h,v}$). Another advantage of using $t/T = 0.5$ is that the vertical acceleration is negative throughout the domain for $\omega_p H/V_p < \pi/2 \Rightarrow \omega_s H/V_s < 0.94\pi$. By sign conventions of the present study, a negative vertical acceleration acts downwards, increasing the vertical body force, b_z (refer to Eq. 4.2). Fig. 5.7 illustrates the variation of normalized support pressure, $\sigma_s/\gamma D$, with dimensionless shear and primary wave frequencies, $\omega_s H/V_s$ and $\omega_p H/V_p$, using $t/T = 0.5$ for typical input parameters. Thus, a representative value of $\omega_s H/V_s = 0.75\pi$ has been selected. This is because the above-said frequency is almost equidistant from the fundamental frequency of shear and primary waves, ensuring the contribution of both. Furthermore, from Fig. 5.7, $\omega_s H/V_s = 0.75\pi$ results in a considerably higher support pressure.

5.6.2 Parametric study

Figures 5.8 and 5.9 show the results of a thorough parametric study conducted on the normalized support pressure, $\sigma_s/\gamma D$. Here, the influence of horizontal acceleration coefficient, k_h , anisotropy ratio, m , maximum friction angle, ϕ_1 , and dimensionless ground surcharge, $q/\gamma D$, have been investigated. The normalized support pressure increases with an increase in k_h and $q/\gamma D$, and decreases with an increase in ϕ_1 and m .

FIGURE 5.7: Variation of normalized support pressure with dimensionless frequency using $t/T = 0.5$.

From figures 5.8 and 5.9, the support pressure increases with C/D for tunnels in soils with a lower maximum friction angle. Contrary to the above, for a higher ϕ_1 value, the support pressure drops with the tunnel cover depth. The reason is an increased influence of soil arching for tunnels with a larger cover depth in soils with higher friction angles. It has been observed from the parametric study that the influence of ground surcharge on the support pressure decreases with tunnel cover depth-to-diameter ratio. In order to investigate this, support pressure has been varied with $q/\gamma D$ for $C/D = 5$, as shown in Fig. 5.10. It is evident that the influence of ground surcharge magnitude is insignificant in support pressure estimation for tunnels placed at a larger cover depth as stresses redistribute within the soil mass such that no additional stress is transferred to the tunnel periphery.

$$\omega_s H / V_s = 0.75\pi, t/T = 0.5$$

FIGURE 5.8: Parametric study on the support pressure for tunnels with $C/D = 1$.

$$\omega_s H / V_s = 0.75\pi, t/T = 0.5$$

FIGURE 5.9: Parametric study on the support pressure for tunnels with $C/D = 3$.

FIGURE 5.10: Vanishing influence of ground surcharge magnitude on tunnel support pressure for $C/D = 5$.

A meta-analysis has been conducted using parametric study's results to investigate the influence of individual parameters, i.e., maximum friction angle, anisotropy ratio, ground surcharge, and the coefficient of horizontal acceleration on tunnel support pressure. Results of this are discussed in the forthcoming paragraphs.

Effect of maximum friction angle, ϕ_1 : The tunnel support pressure decreases with an increase in the maximum friction angle, ϕ_1 . From Eq. 5.4, given m , the equivalent friction angle increases with ϕ_1 . Thus, the support pressure decreases with soil shear strength. Fig. 5.11 shows the absolute percentage difference in normalized support pressure, $\Delta_{\phi_1}(\sigma_s)$, between $\phi_1 = 30^\circ$ and 45° , including the influence of m , $q/\gamma D$, k_h , and C/D . It is readily evident that the support pressure is sensitive to ϕ_1 when the tunnel has a larger cover depth-to-diameter ratio. The influence of soil arching in reducing the stresses along tunnel periphery increases with friction angle and cover depth. Thus, for $C/D = 3$, reduction of support pressure with ϕ_1 is higher. In other words, from Fig. 5.11(b), the support pressure for tunnels with $C/D = 3$ is comparatively sensitive to friction angle changes than those with $C/D = 1$. Furthermore, given other input parameters, the relative change of $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ with ϕ_1 is higher for $m = 1$ than $m = 0.6$. Again, the reason is attributed to soil arching.

For a constant ϕ_1 , an increase in m indicates an increase in the equivalent friction angle, which increases the influence of soil arching.

FIGURE 5.11: Effect of ϕ_1 : Absolute percentage difference in support pressure, $\Delta_{\phi_1}(\sigma_s)$, between $\phi_1 = 30^\circ$ and 45° for (a) $C/D = 1$, and (b) $C/D = 3$.

Effect of anisotropy ratio, m : Given the value of ϕ_1 , the equivalent friction angle (Eq. 5.4) increases with the anisotropy ratio, m . Therefore, the support pressure decreases with m , due to an increase in soil shear strength. Fig. 5.12 investigates the effect of m on normalized support pressure using the absolute percentage difference, $\Delta_m(\sigma_s)$, between $m = 0.6$ and 1. As stated above, a change in m changes the equivalent friction angle, and its effect on support pressure can be reasoned using the soil arching phenomenon. Thus, figures 5.11 and 5.12 are complementary to each other since the change in either ϕ_1 or m alters the equivalent friction angle. Complementary to the effect of m in Fig. 5.11, Fig. 5.12 shows that the support pressure is highly sensitive to m for a larger maximum friction angle. Similarly, the anisotropy ratio has a heightened influence on support pressure for tunnels placed at a larger cover depth.

Effect of ground surcharge, $q/\gamma D$: Fig. 5.13 shows the influence of ground surcharge magnitude, $q/\gamma D$, on $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ using the absolute percentage difference, $\Delta_{q/\gamma D}(\sigma_s)$, between $q/\gamma D = 0$ and 1. It is obvious that the support pressure magnitude increases with

FIGURE 5.12: Effect of m : Absolute percentage difference, $\Delta_m(\sigma_s)$, between $m = 0.6$ and 1 for (a) $C/D = 1$, and (b) $C/D = 3$.

applied ground surcharge. But the amount of increase in $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ is dependent on other input parameters. For $C/D = 1$, Fig. 5.13(a) shows that, largely, the change in support pressure with ground surcharge is higher for a lower m and ϕ_1 . This is because of a reduction in the equivalent friction angle with m and/or ϕ_1 . Thus, the effect of ground surcharge on support pressure is noticeable for tunnels in soils with a lower shear strength. Comparing figures 5.13(a) and (b), for $\phi_1 = 30^\circ$, $\Delta_{q/\gamma D}(\sigma_s)$ reduces with C/D . Thus, the effect of ground surcharge drops with the tunnel cover depth. On the other hand, Fig. 5.13(b) suggests that support pressure is highly sensitive to the ground surcharge for tunnels in soils with higher m or ϕ_1 . As stated earlier, the support pressure decreases with C/D for a higher ϕ_1 value. This decrement is prominent for the no-surcharge condition than $q/\gamma D = 1$. In other words, $\sigma_s/\gamma D$, for $C/D = 1$, $m = 0.6$, $\phi_1 = 45^\circ$, and $k_h = 0$, increases from 1.12 to 1.33 (refer to figures. 5.8(a) and (c)). However, for the above-mentioned input parameters, $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ increases from 1.07 to 1.54 for $C/D = 3$ (refer to figures 5.9(a) and (c)). Because of the above-said "regain" of support pressure for an increased magnitude of ground surcharge for tunnels with a larger cover depth, Fig. 5.13(b) shows a surge in $\Delta_{q/\gamma D}(\sigma_s)$ for $\phi_1 = 45^\circ$.

FIGURE 5.13: Absolute percentage difference, $\Delta_{q/\gamma D}(\sigma_s)$, between $q/\gamma D = 0$ and 1 for (a) $C/D = 1$, and (b) $C/D = 3$.

Effect of horizontal acceleration coefficient, k_h : Fig. 5.14 highlights the effect of horizontal acceleration coefficient, k_h , on the dimensionless support pressure, including the influence of other input parameters. Here, the effect of k_h is studied using the absolute percentage difference in $\sigma_s/\gamma D$, i.e., $\Delta_{k_h}(\sigma_s)$, between $k_h = 0$ and 0.1. Fig. 5.14 illustrates the influence of seismicity on tunnel stability as k_h is varied between static and seismic conditions. For $t/T = 0.5$, the base seismic acceleration is given as $a_h(z, t) = k_h g$. Thus, increasing the magnitude of k_h increases the horizontal acceleration's magnitude along the depth, which rises the support pressure requirement. Since, $k_v = k_h/2$, the magnitude of vertical seismic acceleration also increases with k_h . From Fig. 5.14, the effect of k_h in increasing the support pressure is high for a lower anisotropy ratio and maximum friction angle, i.e., a lower equivalent friction angle. This obvious because of a reduced soil shear strength for lower m and ϕ_1 values. Furthermore, the sensitivity of support pressures to k_h decreases with C/D . Therefore, tunnels placed at a larger cover depth are less prone to seismic catastrophes, similar to that in literature (Sharma and Judd, 1991; Luco and Barros, 1994; Lanzano et al., 2012; Moghadam and Baziar, 2016).

FIGURE 5.14: Effect of k_h : Absolute percentage difference, $\Delta_{k_h}(\sigma_s)$, between $k_h = 0$ and 0.1 for (a) $C/D = 1$, and (b) $C/D = 3$.

5.6.3 Collapse pattern

Nodal velocity patterns plotted over the domain aid in visualizing the region of soil collapse around the tunnel periphery. Figures 5.15, 5.16, and 5.17 show collapse patterns highlighting the effect of problem parameters under static and seismic loadings. The extent of soil region in which the length of velocity vectors is significant has been marked. Fig. 5.15 indicate that the region of soil collapse increases for an increase in ground surcharge magnitude. Moreover, since the loading is static, collapse patterns in Fig. 5.15 are symmetrical with the vertical through tunnel center.

FIGURE 5.15: Collapse patterns highlighting the effect of ground surcharge under the static loadings.

Comparing figures 5.15(b) and 5.16(a), seismicity skews the collapse pattern towards the predominant direction of seismic horizontal acceleration. From Fig. 4.19 of Chapter 4, for $\omega_s H/V_s = 0.75\pi$ and $t/T = 0.5$, the horizontal acceleration acts towards the right-hand side of tunnel center (positive X axis) in its vicinity. Thus, the collapse pattern is right-skewed in Fig. 5.16. Furthermore, seismicity also increases the extent of soil collapse around tunnels. From figures 5.16(a) and (b) it can be inferred that the collapse pattern's extent increases for an anisotropic soil than an isotropic one.

FIGURE 5.16: For $C/D = 1$, collapse patterns highlighting the effect of anisotropy ratio under seismic loadings.

Fig. 5.17 illustrates the effect of maximum friction angle, ϕ_1 , on the collapse pattern for $C/D = 3$. Comparing figures 5.16(b) and 5.17(a), the region of ultimate collapse increases corresponding to the cover depth for tunnels in soils with a lower ϕ_1 value. Fig. 5.17(b) illustrate that, the soil collapse is confined around the periphery for tunnels placed at a larger cover depth in soils with a higher maximum friction angle. Furthermore, the lateral extent of collapse in tunnel's vicinity reduces with ϕ_1 .

5.6.4 Horizontal and vertical stress contours

Figures 5.18, 5.19, and 5.20 show the dimensionless horizontal, $\sigma_x/\gamma D$, and vertical, $\sigma_z/\gamma D$, stress contours for static and seismic cases. These figures have been provided with the respective collapse pattern to indicate the region of soil failure. The phenomenon

FIGURE 5.17: For $C/D = 3$, collapse patterns highlighting the effect of maximum friction angle under seismic loadings.

of soil arching involves the transfer of vertical stresses from the yielding to non-yielding region over the tunnel, and vertical stress contours in these figures are indicative of the phenomenon. Fig. 5.18 highlight the effect of $q/\gamma D$ on stress contours under the static loading. An increase in the magnitude of vertical ground surcharge increases $\sigma_z/\gamma D$ throughout the domain. This increment in vertical stress magnitudes near the tunnel periphery is accompanied by an increase in the horizontal stress, which increases the support pressure requirement.

FIGURE 5.18: Horizontal and vertical stress contours showing the effect of ground surcharge under static loading.

It has been said in the previous section that seismicity skews the collapse pattern, and Fig. 5.19 shows that the stress distribution around tunnels is also skewed due to seismicity. Furthermore, the magnitude of $\sigma_x/\gamma D$ and $\sigma_z/\gamma D$ in tunnel's vicinity increases in Fig. 5.19(a) compared to Fig. 5.18(b), which increases the support pressure. From figures 5.19(a) and (b), the influence of soil arching in vertical stress transfer reduces for a lower anisotropy ratio. In essence, magnitude of $\sigma_z/\gamma D$ in the non-yielding portion near tunnel periphery reduces for a lower m value. The reason is attributed to the reduction in equivalent friction angle, given ϕ_1 , for a lower anisotropy ratio. It is known that soil arching is prominent in soils with a higher shear strength.

FIGURE 5.19: Effect of anisotropy ratio: Horizontal and vertical stress contours for seismic loadings using $C/D = 1$.

Figures 5.19(b) and 5.20(a) illustrate that the soil arching phenomenon increases with tunnel cover depth. Nevertheless, this is notable for tunnels placed in soils with a higher friction angle, i.e., Fig. 5.20(b) than in Fig. 5.20(a). The aforementioned occurrence of prominent soil arching explains the reduction in support pressure with an increase in C/D for higher ϕ_1 values in figures 5.8 and 5.9.

FIGURE 5.20: For $C/D = 3$, effect of maximum friction angle in horizontal and vertical stress contours for seismic loadings.

5.6.5 Normal stress distribution around tunnel periphery

Figs. 5.21, 5.22, and 5.23 show the distribution of normal stress along the tunnel periphery. These figures are plotted as polar plots, with the angles calculated as the angle subtended by radial lines through the tunnel's center with respect to the positive X-direction. Whereas, the radii are normal stresses at the corresponding tunnel node, expressed in the non-dimensional form as $\sigma_n/\gamma D$. Fig. 5.21(a) depicts the normal stress variation for static loading with $C/D = 1$. As $q/\gamma D$ increases, the normal stress along the tunnel periphery increases. Therefore, the maximum of these normal stresses, i.e., $\sigma_s/\gamma D$, also increases. Moreover, the normal stress varies symmetrically about the tunnel center for the static load. Figures 5.21(b) and (c) show how the seismic analysis is more conservative when the effect of the primary wave is considered. Apart from the effect of $q/\gamma D$, the value of normal stress for $k_v = 0$ is less than that for $k_v = k_h/2$.

FIGURE 5.21: Normal stress distribution, $\sigma_n/\gamma D$, for (a) static, and seismic loading with (b) $k_v = 0$, and (c) $k_v = k_h/2$.

Fig. 5.22 compares the effect of anisotropy ratio on the normal stress distribution using $\phi_1 = 30^\circ$ and 45° . From Fig. 5.22(a), as the anisotropic parameter, m , decreases, the normal stress on the tunnel node increases, thereby increasing the support pressure. Comparing figures 5.22(a) and (b), for a given value of m , the normal stress around the tunnel's periphery decreases with ϕ_1 .

Figures 5.23(a) and (b) show the effect of anisotropy ratio, m , and dimensionless surcharge magnitude, $q/\gamma D$, respectively, using $C/D = 3$. From Fig. 5.22(a), as m increases, $\sigma_n/\gamma D$ increases. Comparing Figs. 5.22(a) and 5.23(a), as C/D increases,

FIGURE 5.22: Normal stress distribution, $\sigma_n/\gamma D$, for seismic loadings highlighting the effect of anisotropy ratio for (a) $\phi_1 = 30^\circ$, and (b) $\phi = 45^\circ$.

the normal stresses around the tunnel periphery increase, leading to a rise in the support pressure. Furthermore, from Fig. 5.22(b), the normal stress along the tunnel boundary increases with $q/\gamma D$. But comparing Fig. 5.23(b) with Fig. 5.21(c), the rate of increase in the maximum normal stress with $q/\gamma D$ is less for $C/D = 3$ than $C/D = 1$. This reinforces that the effect of $q/\gamma D$ on $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ reduces with the rise in C/D and ceases for C/D greater than 3.

5.7 A comparative study for tunnels in granular and cohesive-frictional soils

The present chapter focused on the seismic stability analysis of circular tunnels in granular soils, whereas Chapter 4 was for tunnels in cohesive-frictional soils. The current section aims to compare the results of Chapter 4 and 5 to understand the effect of soil cohesion on seismic stability of circular tunnels. In order to maintain a level ground for comparison, both soils have been considered dry, homogeneous, and isotropic ($m = 1$ for granular

FIGURE 5.23: For $C/D = 3$, normal stress distribution, $\sigma_n/\gamma D$, showing the effect of (a) anisotropy ratio, and (b) ground surcharge.

soils). Furthermore, $\phi = 30^\circ$ has been assumed, and the ground surface is devoid of any surcharge ($q/\gamma D = 0$). The results have been compared for a typical case of $C/D = 1$, $k_v = k_h/2$, $t/T = 0.5$, $\omega_s H/V_s = 0.75\pi$, and $\xi = 10\%$. The support pressure is expressed as $\sigma_s/\gamma D$, where γ and D are the soil unit weight and tunnel diameter, respectively. The magnitude of soil cohesion, c , has been taken into account using the non-dimensional quantity $c/\gamma D$. Initially, the influence of soil cohesion on support pressure contours in the dimensionless frequency-time domain is evaluated. This is followed by the variation of $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ with k_h for different $c/\gamma D$ values. The effect of soil cohesion on seismic stability has been conceived using collapse patterns, stress contours, and normal stress distributions.

5.7.1 Support pressure in dimensionless frequency-time domain

Fig. 5.24 explores the influence of soil cohesion on the normalized support pressure variation in the dimensionless frequency-time domain. Here, $k_h = 0.1$ and $k_v = k_h/2$ are used. The discussion retains only the non-dimensional frequency of shear waves, $\omega_s H/V_s$,

since the respective quantity for primary waves can be obtained from Eq. 4.11 using $\omega_p/\omega_s = 1$, and $V_p/V_s = 1.87$. In Fig. 5.24, the curve $\max \sigma_s/\gamma D$ wrt t/T indicates the variation of maximum support pressure, for any t/T , with the dimensionless frequency. Similarly, the curve $\max \sigma_s/\gamma D$ wrt $\omega_s H/V_s$ has been plotted considering the maximum support pressure, for any $\omega_s H/V_s$, along the dimensionless time.

The value of $c/\gamma D$ increases from 0 to 1 for Fig. 5.24(a) to Fig. 5.24(d), which indicates an increasing magnitude of soil cohesion (given γ and D). From Fig. 5.24(a), the peak $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ occurs near the fundamental frequency of shear waves, $\omega_s H/V_s = \pi/2$ for $c/\gamma D = 0$. However, as the magnitude of soil cohesion increases, Fig. 5.24 shows that the occurrence of peak support pressure gradually shifts near the fundamental frequency of primary waves ($\omega_p H/V_p = \pi/2 \Rightarrow \omega_s H/V_s = 0.94\pi$). The above-said shift in critical frequency can be understood quantitatively using the ratio of peak support pressures near the fundamental frequency of shear and primary waves, i.e.,

$$\varepsilon_{S-P} = \frac{\max \sigma_s/\gamma D \text{ for any } t/T \text{ around } \omega_s H/V_s = \pi/2}{\max \sigma_s/\gamma D \text{ for any } t/T \text{ around } \omega_s H/V_s = 0.94\pi} \quad (5.5)$$

Here, $\omega_s H/V_s = 0.94\pi$ corresponds to the fundamental vibration mode of primary waves ($\omega_p H/V_p = \pi/2$, from Eq. 4.11). Fig. 5.24(e) shows the variation of ε_{S-P} with $c/\gamma D$ for the cases investigated here. The influence of shear waves in support pressures is higher for $\varepsilon_{S-P} > 1$, and vice-versa for $\varepsilon_{S-P} < 1$. Moreover, $\varepsilon_{S-P} = 1$ indicates that the support pressure is equally influenced by shear and primary waves. Theoretically, ε_{S-P} varies from 0 to ∞ , where $\varepsilon_{S-P} \rightarrow 0$ when the peak support pressure near P-wave's fundamental frequency is enormous, and $\varepsilon_{S-P} \rightarrow \infty$ when the peak support pressure surges near S-wave's fundamental frequency. It is clear from Fig. 5.24(e) that the support pressure is increasingly influenced by primary waves as the magnitude of soil cohesion increases. This supports the observation made in section 4.6.1 of Chapter 4 that the peak

support pressure does not to occur near S-wave's fundamental frequency because of an increased shear strength for soils with substantial cohesion and friction angle.

FIGURE 5.24: Influence of soil cohesion on the normalized support pressure in dimensionless frequency-time domain.

5.7.2 Support pressure variation with k_h

The influence of soil cohesion regarding the variation of support pressure with horizontal acceleration coefficient, k_h , is given in Fig. 5.25(a). Following the dimensionless frequency and time values fixed for parametric study in chapters 4 and 5, $t/T = 0.5$ and $\omega_s H/V_s = 0.75\pi$ are used here. It is readily inferred from Fig. 5.25(a) that the presence of soil cohesion reduces the support pressure for tunnels. This is attributed to the additional shear strength imparted because of soil cohesion, apart from the frictional resistance due to soil friction angle. In other words, tunnels placed in soils with a higher cohesion could withstand a relatively larger amplitude of seismic force than those in granular soils. Fig. 5.25(b) shows the normal stress distribution, $\sigma_n/\gamma D$, concerning the influence of soil cohesion using $k_h = 0.1$. The normal stress magnitude along the tunnel periphery is lower for higher values of $c/\gamma D$, which reasons the drop in support pressure with soil cohesion in Fig. 5.25(a).

FIGURE 5.25: Influence of soil cohesion on (a) support pressure variation with horizontal acceleration coefficient, and (b) normal stress distribution for $k_h = 0.1$.

5.7.3 Collapse pattern and stress contours

The effect of soil cohesion on the region of soil collapse and dimensionless stress contours (horizontal and vertical) is investigated in figures 5.26 and 5.27, respectively. Collapse patterns in Fig. 5.26 are largely skewed to horizontal acceleration's direction in tunnel's vicinity. From Fig. 4.19, seismic horizontal acceleration is along the positive X axis near the tunnel. Hence, collapse patterns are lopsided towards the right-hand side of tunnel center. However, a careful examination of Fig. 5.26 highlight that the extent to which a collapse pattern is skewed depends on the magnitude of soil cohesion. As $c/\gamma D$ increases, the collapse pattern tends to be more symmetric around the tunnel. It is to be understood that the collapse pattern is skewed mainly because of the horizontal seismic acceleration, and a higher skew in collapse pattern might indicate an increased influence of shear waves on soil collapse. Thus, from Fig. 5.26, it can be inferred that the influence of shear wave on soil collapse around tunnels reduces with the cohesion magnitude, as observed in section 4.6.1 of Chapter 4 with respect to tunnel support pressure.

FIGURE 5.26: Influence of soil cohesion on the collapse pattern.

Fig. 5.27 illustrate the influence of soil cohesion on dimensionless horizontal ($\sigma_x/\gamma D$) and vertical ($\sigma_z/\gamma D$) stress contours for $C/D = 1$ under seismic loadings. Vertical stress contours in Fig. 5.27 indicate the occurrence of soil arching over the tunnel. It is readily evident that the magnitude of $\sigma_z/\gamma D$ transferred to non-yielding regions is higher in soils with a higher cohesion magnitude. Chen et al. (2022a) provided analytical solutions for soil arching over trapdoors in cohesive-frictional soils in terms of the soil arching ratio defined as the ratio of vertical stress after arching to that before arching. It was found that the soil arching ratio reduces with cohesion magnitude, i.e., at a given depth from the ground surface, the vertical stress magnitude over the tunnel reduces with soil cohesion, which indicates an increased influence of soil arching in transferring the vertical stress from yielding to non-yielding zone. The above-said can be used to justify the stress contour changes with soil cohesion from the present study, as shown in Fig. 5.27, under the pretext that stress distribution over a tunnel is similar to that in a trapdoor (Khandouzi and Khosravi, 2023). Furthermore, one of the important conditions for soil arching to occur is the availability of shear strength to be mobilized, that is, the higher the soil shear strength, the higher is the shear strength available for mobilization (Terzaghi, 1943). In other words, the soil arching is stronger in soils with high cohesion due to an increased shear strength. This increased transfer of vertical stresses from the yielding to non-yielding region for soils with a higher cohesion value causes the reduction in normal stress magnitudes across the tunnel periphery (refer to Fig. 5.25(b)). Another important observation from Fig. 5.27 is the "regain" of a near-symmetric stress distribution with $c/\gamma D$, which indicates the reduced influence of shear waves in the stress distribution when soil cohesion is large.

FIGURE 5.27: Influence of soil cohesion on dimensionless horizontal and vertical stress contours

5.8 Summary

The analysis in the present chapter focused on the seismic stability of circular tunnels placed in dry granular medium subjected to ground surcharge. The granular soil is homogeneous but anisotropic with respect to its friction angle. An equivalent friction angle, as a function of the maximum friction angle and anisotropy ratio, was used. The vertically traveling in-plane shear and primary waves accelerate the medium in horizontal and vertical directions, respectively, which are modeled using the modified pseudo-dynamic method. The maximum normal stress from the distribution along tunnel periphery is considered as the support pressure. The dimensionless frequency and time were found to have a strong influence on the support pressure variation with shear waves impacting tunnels with a lower cover depth. The support pressure increased with an increase in horizontal acceleration coefficient and ground surcharge magnitude, and a decrease in maximum friction angle and anisotropy ratio. The support pressure for tunnels with larger cover depth was more resistant to changes in the seismic acceleration coefficient. Typical collapse patterns and stress contours were obtained to analyze the region of ultimate failure and stress distribution. Normal stress distributions were also obtained to show the effect of typical input parameters. Finally, a comparative study for the stability of tunnels in granular and cohesive-frictional soils was performed.

6

Stability of piggyback dual tunnels in granular soils

6.1 General

Due to the space constraints in urban areas, the provision of dual tunnels that are vertically separated from one another becomes indispensable (Do et al., 2014; Liu et al., 2016; Do et al., 2022; Feizi et al., 2022). The effect caused by the seismic waves propagating in a soil medium with a single tunnel is completely different from that of the dual tunnels. It has been found that placing another tunnel below an existing tunnel affects the stability of the existing one. Many studies have been performed on the ground amplification, seismic wave amplification and dynamic stress concentration of seismic waves owing to interaction of dual tunnels (Fotieva, 1980; Balendra et al., 1984; Liu and Wang, 2012; Alielahi and Adampira, 2016; Tsinidis, 2018; Feizi et al., 2022). Furthermore, literature is abundantly available on the stability analysis of dual tunnels for static loading rather than seismic and very few studies are present on the stability of vertically separated tunnels. Based on the assessment of the tunnel damages caused by various earthquakes around the world, it has been noted that the major form of seismic damage to the tunnel is due

to the failure of tunnel lining systems (Wang et al., 2001; Li, 2012; Yu et al., 2016). Hence, analysis of the stresses exerted by the surrounding earth on the tunnel lining due to earthquakes is crucial for the safe design of tunnel lining.

The present chapter attempts to study the influence of the presence of another tunnel on the tunnel seismic response. For the present analysis, piggyback dual circular tunnels of equal diameter, having a common center-line, is considered to be placed in granular soils. The seismic body forces that arise due to the propagation of in-plane shear and primary waves have been accounted for using the modified pseudo-dynamic method. The seismic stability analysis has been performed using the finite element lower bound limit analysis. The minimum stress exerted by the tunnel support systems should be greater than or equal to the maximum normal stress imposed anywhere on the tunnel periphery. The effect of the dimensionless frequency, time, tunnel cover depth, center-to-center separation distance between tunnels, seismic acceleration coefficient and soil friction angle on the support pressure for top and bottom tunnels have been thoroughly investigated. Based on the collapse patterns, typical failure modes for piggyback tunnels have been proposed. Furthermore, three zones of soil arching above top and bottom tunnels have been identified. At last, typical variations of normal stresses around top and bottom tunnel peripheries are provided.

6.2 Problem description

The present study assesses the seismic stability of vertically separated dual circular tunnels in dry, isotropic, and homogeneous granular soil subjected to vertically propagating shear and primary waves. Both the top and bottom tunnels are of diameter D , and the center lines of both tunnels align, as shown in Fig. 6.1. The top tunnel is placed at a cover depth C from the ground surface, and the center of the bottom tunnel is at a distance of

S from the top tunnel's center. The unit weight and friction angle of the soil are γ and ϕ , respectively. The horizontal and vertical seismic accelerations, $a_h(z, t)$ and $a_v(z, t)$, respectively, varied along the depth z and time t . The length of tunnels is substantially higher than the other dimensions, facilitating the use of plane strain analysis. Furthermore, the soil strength parameters were assumed to be unaffected by seismic action.

FIGURE 6.1: Description of the present problem.

6.3 Analysis

The analysis was performed using the lower bound limit analysis approach combined with the finite element procedure and the second-order cone programming technique and its general formulation has been described in section 3.2 in the Chapter 3. Fig. 6.2 shows the finite element discretization taken up for the domain LMNO. Here, linear triangular elements with three unknown stresses at each node has been considered. The nodes have

been numbered unique to a particular element; therefore, several nodes have the same coordinate but different node numbers. This assists the provision of statically admissible stress discontinuity between the shared element edge. The ground surface, LM, is stress-free ($\sigma_n = 0$ and $\tau = 0$). The other boundaries, MN, NO, and OL, were fixed such that the failure patterns fall within the domain and the support pressure values are unaffected. The soil-lining interface has been considered smooth, i.e., $\tau = 0$ is imposed along top and bottom tunnel periphery. Fig. 6.2 illustrates a typical finite element mesh for dual tunnels with $C/D = 1$ and $S/D = 5$. It was observed that the number of elements was dependent on the tunnel cover depth-to-diameter ratio (C/D), center-to-center distance (S/D), seismic acceleration coefficients (k_h and k_v), and soil friction angle (ϕ).

FIGURE 6.2: Typical finite element mesh for dual tunnels with $C/D = 1$ and $S/D = 5$.

The support pressures for top (σ_{s_1}) and bottom (σ_{s_2}) tunnels are defined as the maximum normal stress on the respective tunnel periphery. Mathematically,

$$\sigma_{s_1} = \max \left[\sigma_{n_1^1}, \sigma_{n_2^1}, \dots, \sigma_{n_i^1}, \sigma_{n_{i+1}^1}, \dots, \sigma_{N_t^1} \right] \quad (6.1)$$

$$\sigma_{s_2} = \max \left[\sigma_{n_1^2}, \sigma_{n_2^2}, \dots, \sigma_{n_i^2}, \sigma_{n_{i+1}^2}, \dots, \sigma_{N_t^2} \right] \quad (6.2)$$

Here σ_{s_1} and σ_{s_2} are the support pressures for top and bottom tunnels, respectively; $\sigma_{n_i^1}$ and $\sigma_{n_i^2}$ are the normal stresses at the i^{th} node for top and bottom tunnels. Similarly, $\sigma_{n_{i+1}^1}$ and $\sigma_{n_{i+1}^2}$ are the normal stresses at the $(i+1)^{\text{th}}$ node for top and bottom tunnels. Further, N_t^1 and N_t^2 are the total number of nodes along the top and bottom tunnels, respectively.

6.4 Validation of the present study

To the best of authors' knowledge, no study is available to assess the seismic stability of piggyback dual tunnels. The OptumG2 software could perform the finite element lower bound limit analysis for underground tunnels. While OptumG2 is useful to assess the static stability by constraining normal stresses to be equal along the tunnel periphery, it cannot be used to determine the normal stress distribution around the tunnel boundary combined with the modified pseudo-dynamic method. Therefore, the collapse load, P_u , from the present study for the static case is compared with that from OptumG2 to validate the finite element lower bound limit analysis framework used. Fig. 6.3 shows the validation of P_u for a typical case of $C = D = 8$ m, $\gamma = 17$ kN/m³, and $k_h = 0$ (static) with different center-to-center separation distances and ϕ values. It suggests that the present numerical framework conforms well with that of the software.

FIGURE 6.3: Comparison of collapse load with OptumG2 for static conditions.

6.5 Results and Discussion

Support pressures for top and bottom tunnels are expressed in non-dimensional forms using the unit weight, γ , and tunnel diameter (D) as $\sigma_{s1}/\gamma D$ and $\sigma_{s2}/\gamma D$, respectively. Table 6.1 enlists the parameters and their ranges used in the current study. The center-to-center separation between the tunnels is normalized using the tunnel diameter, S/D , and has been varied till there is no appreciable change in support pressures. After analyzing the effect of dimensionless frequency and time on the support pressure variation for top and bottom tunnels, a comprehensive parametric study has been performed to study the influence of other problem parameters. The extent of soil in the proximity of plastic collapse has been studied using the velocity patterns for typical cases. An investigation on the soil arching phenomenon, pertaining to piggyback dual tunnels, is also taken up in the present study.

TABLE 6.1: Description of the problem parameters and values used in this study.

Parameter	Notation	Range
Cover-to-diameter ratio of tunnel	C/D	1, 3
Friction angle of soil	ϕ	30°, 35°, 40°, 45°
Horizontal acceleration coefficient	k_h	0, 0.1, 0.2
Vertical acceleration coefficient	k_v	$k_h/2$
Dimensionless time	t/T	0 – 1
Dimensionless frequency of S wave	$\omega_s H/V_s$	0 to 2π
Dimensionless frequency of P wave	$\omega_p H/V_p$	0 to 1.07π
Damping ratio	ξ	7%

6.5.1 Effect of dimensionless frequency and time on support pressures

It is well known, from previous chapters, that dimensionless frequency and time of shear and primary waves have a strong influence on the seismic acceleration. Hence, it is important to investigate the variation of tunnel support pressures, $\sigma_{s1}/\gamma D$ and $\sigma_{s2}/\gamma D$, with the dimensionless frequency of shear waves, $\omega_s H/V_s$, and dimensionless time, t/T . Knowing the value of $\omega_p H/V_p$, the corresponding value of $\omega_s H/V_s$ can be found as $\omega_s H/V_s = \omega_p H/V_p \times 1.87$. Therefore, this discussion retains only the dimensionless frequency of shear waves for simplicity. Figures 6.4 and 6.5 show the support pressure variation for top and bottom tunnels for two cases of center-to-center spacing - $S/D = 1.5$ (a closer spacing) and $S/D = 5$ (a larger spacing), respectively. Here, $C/D = 3$ and $k_h = 0.1$ has been used throughout. Furthermore, the effect of soil friction angle is also included in these figures. In figures 6.4 and 6.5, the region in the dimensionless frequency-time domain for which the numerical model resulted in infeasible solutions are indicated as RI, i.e., Region of Infeasibility. Also, in these figures, the curve labeled as "max $\sigma_{s_i}/\gamma D$ wrt t/T " ($i = 1, 2$) is plotted by considering the maximum value of support pressure for any t/T using a particular $\omega_s H/V_s$ value. Similarly, "max $\sigma_{s_i}/\gamma D$ wrt $\omega_s H/V_s$ " indicates the curve of the maximum support pressure for any $\omega_s H/V_s$ evaluated at a given t/T value.

FIGURE 6.4: Variation of support pressures for top and bottom tunnels in the dimensionless frequency-time domain considering a close spacing of $S/D = 1.5$.

Fig. 6.4 illustrates that, when two tunnels are close to each other, the support pressure of top and bottom tunnels are strongly influenced by shear waves for any value of ϕ . This is evident from the occurrence of a global value of peak support pressure around the shear wave's fundamental frequency ($\omega_s H/V_s = \pi/2$). Local peaks are also noticeable around the fundamental frequency of primary waves ($\omega_p H/V_p = \pi/2 \Rightarrow \omega_s H/V_s = 0.94\pi$) and second natural frequency of shear waves ($\omega_s H/V_s = 1.5\pi$). Further, from Fig. 6.4(b), for

$\phi = 45^\circ$, it seems that the contribution of primary waves has increased compared to Fig. 6.4(a). This increment is more noticeable for the bottom tunnel than the top.

FIGURE 6.5: For $S/D = 5$, Variation of support pressures for top and bottom tunnels in the dimensionless frequency-time domain.

On the other hand, for a larger center-to-center distance of $S/D = 5$ in Fig. 6.5, the shear wave dominates the support pressure variation for soils of lower friction angle. The primary wave has a strong influence for soils of higher friction angles. Here, too, due to a larger S/D value, the participation of primary waves is substantially higher, especially for

bottom tunnels. The generalized trend of the seismic response discussed above was found to be applicable for any value of tunnel cover depth. Thus, for piggyback dual tunnels, the center-to-center separation distance, S/D , and the soil friction angle governs the support pressure variation in the dimensionless frequency-time domain.

The above-mentioned observation on the influence of shear or primary wave is quantitatively investigated using the ratio of the support pressure near shear and primary wave fundamental frequencies, and it is defined as

$$\text{Top tunnel : } \varepsilon_{S-P}^1 = \frac{\max \sigma_{s_1}/\gamma D \text{ for any } t/T \text{ around } \omega_s H/V_s = \pi/2}{\max \sigma_{s_1}/\gamma D \text{ for any } t/T \text{ around } \omega_s H/V_s = 0.94\pi} \quad (6.3)$$

$$\text{Bottom tunnel : } \varepsilon_{S-P}^2 = \frac{\max \sigma_{s_2}/\gamma D \text{ for any } t/T \text{ around } \omega_s H/V_s = \pi/2}{\max \sigma_{s_2}/\gamma D \text{ for any } t/T \text{ around } \omega_s H/V_s = 0.94\pi} \quad (6.4)$$

Note that, referring to Eq. 4.11, the dimensionless shear wave frequency corresponding to the primary wave's fundamental frequency is calculated as $\omega_p H/V_p = \pi/2 \Rightarrow \omega_s H/V_s = \pi/2 \times 1.87 = 0.94\pi$ ($\because V_p/V_s = 1.87$ and $\omega_p/\omega_s = 1$).

The value of ε_{S-P}^j ($j = 1, 2$) = 1 indicates that the maximum support pressure around the fundamental frequencies of shear and primary waves are the same, i.e., shear and primary waves equally influence the support pressure. On the other hand, the effect of shear waves increases with $\varepsilon_{S-P}^j > 1$, and vice-versa for $\varepsilon_{S-P}^j < 1$. It is interesting to note that, theoretically, the range of ε_{S-P}^j is from 0 to ∞ . As the maximum support pressure near the primary wave's fundamental frequency shoots up, $\varepsilon_{S-P}^j \rightarrow 0$, and when the maximum support pressure near the S-wave's fundamental frequency is extremely high, $\varepsilon_{S-P}^j \rightarrow \infty$. Based on the variation of support pressures for different input parameters in the present study, it has been observed that the support pressure magnitude at any non-dimensional frequency and time is limited by the corresponding support pressure in the static case. This is because the medium is subjected to a near-zero net seismic acceleration at high values of $\omega_s H/V_s$ (Kramer, 2007) for which support pressures tend towards their

static values. Therefore, ε_{S-P}^j can go closer to its bounds only when the necessary support pressure increases. In other words, $\varepsilon_{S-P}^j \rightarrow 0$ cannot be justified by a near-zero support pressure magnitude near the shear wave's fundamental frequency. Similarly, reasoning $\varepsilon_{S-P}^j \rightarrow \infty$ by a vanishing support pressure around the fundamental frequency of primary waves is not viable.

Table 6.2 lists the values of ε_{S-P}^1 and ε_{S-P}^2 for the input parameters in figures 6.4 and 6.5. From Table 6.2, ε_{S-P}^1 and ε_{S-P}^2 are the highest for $S/D = 1.5$ and $\phi = 30^\circ$. Thus, it can be inferred that piggyback dual tunnels placed close to each other in granular soils of low friction angle are predominantly influenced by the shear wave. For a given friction angle, as S/D increases, values of ε_{S-P}^1 and ε_{S-P}^2 drops, which indicate the increased impact of primary waves on the support pressure. Similarly, fixing S/D , ε_{S-P}^1 and ε_{S-P}^2 drop with soil friction angle.

TABLE 6.2: Values of support pressure ratios for top and bottom tunnels near shear and primary wave's fundamental frequency.

		ε_{S-P}^1	ε_{S-P}^2
$S/D = 1.5$	$\phi = 30^\circ$	2.522	4.110
	45°	2.185	1.476
$S/D = 5$	$\phi = 30^\circ$	2.152	1.167
	45°	0.910	1.035

The values of $\omega_s H/V_s$ and t/T that resulted in the peak support pressure in figures 6.4 and 6.5 correspond to the fundamental vibration mode of shear or primary waves. Using these in the parametric study might render the solutions infeasible and over-conservative. But there is a need to use a representative value of the non-dimensional frequency and time to study the variation of other problem parameters. It is clear from equations 4.3 and 4.4 that the magnitude of the base acceleration is maximum ($= k_h g$ and $k_v g$, respectively) at $t/T = 0, 0.5$, and 1 . Hence, $t/T = 0.5$ will ensure that the base acceleration is at its maximum, immaterial of its direction. However, the magnitude of the acceleration at the

ground surface at a particular value of t/T depends on the non-dimensional frequency of the corresponding wave, apart from the known value of the damping ratio.

FIGURE 6.6: Variation of normalized support pressures for top and bottom tunnels with dimensionless frequencies using $t/T = 0.5$.

From Fig. 4.3, magnitudes of $a_h(0,t)/g$ and $a_v(0,t)/g$ are highest for $\omega_s H/V_s = \pi/2$ and 0.94π , respectively, near $t/T = 0.25$ and 0.75 . But, from equations 4.3 and 4.4, base seismic accelerations near $t/T = 0.25$ and 0.75 , for any dimensionless frequency measured, will be minuscule, indicating resonance. Using these values in the analysis may lead to unrealistically high values of support pressure. Hence, $t/T = 0.25$ (or 0.75) has been avoided. Using $t/T = 0.5$, the dimensionless support pressure was varied with the non-dimensional frequency of shear and primary waves ($\omega_s H/V_s$ and $\omega_p H/V_p$) for typical parameters like C/D , S/D , ϕ , and k_h , which is shown in Fig. 6.6. From this, the value of $\omega_s H/V_s$ at which the support pressure value reached its peak has been selected as the critical $\omega_s H/V_s$, which is 0.4π .

6.5.2 Parametric study

Fig. 6.7 presents the results of a thorough parametric study conducted to investigate the influence of C/D , S/D , k_h , and ϕ on the tunnel support pressures, $\sigma_{s_1}/\gamma D$ and $\sigma_{s_2}/\gamma D$. From the previous investigation of the effect of the non-dimensional frequency and time, $t/T = 0.5$ and $\omega_s H/V_s = 0.4\pi$ have been used. The parametric study indicates that three factors stand-out in determining the seismic stability - soil friction angle (ϕ), horizontal acceleration coefficient (k_h), and center-to-center distance (S/D). The interplay of these parameters has been analyzed using the absolute percentage difference in the normalized support pressure in figures 6.8, 6.9, and 6.10. In Fig. 6.7, the support pressure values for higher k_h and lower ϕ values could not be obtained owing to the dynamic shear fluidization of sands (Richards et al., 1990).

FIGURE 6.7: Parametric study on the support pressure variation for top and bottom tunnels.

Effect of soil friction angle: In general, the increase in the soil friction angle, ϕ , increases the soil's shear strength to resist the destructive forces, and hence the support pressure requirement decreases for both tunnels. Fig. 6.8 depicts the variation of absolute percentage differences in the support pressure computed at $\phi = 30^\circ$ and 45° for different S/D and k_h values. Here, $\Delta_\phi(\sigma_{s1})$ and $\Delta_\phi(\sigma_{s2})$ denote absolute percentage differences for top and bottom tunnels, respectively, pertaining to the change in ϕ between 30° and 45° . From Fig. 6.8, it is evident that the drop in the support pressure with soil friction angle is not uniform for any C/D , S/D and k_h .

FIGURE 6.8: Effect of soil friction angle: Absolute percentage difference in support pressure values, $\Delta_\phi(\sigma_{s1})$ and $\Delta_\phi(\sigma_{s2})$ between $\phi = 30^\circ$ and 45° for (a) $C/D = 1$, and (b) $C/D = 3$.

For top and bottom tunnels, the change in the support pressure with ϕ is prominent when two tunnels are close to each other. This is because of the increased interference of one tunnel over the other that renders their support pressures to be highly sensitive to friction angle changes. On the other hand, Fig. 6.8 indicates that $\Delta_\phi(\sigma_{s1})$ and $\Delta_\phi(\sigma_{s2})$ reduce for a larger S/D value. Since the interference effects are negligible at a higher S/D , the sensitivity of support pressures to the change in ϕ decreases. The above is true for any value of C/D and k_h . Furthermore, for a given S/D , ϕ has a strong influence on the bottom tunnel's support pressure than the top. At any S/D , the bottom tunnel has a higher cover depth from the ground surface. It is well known that soil arching is more

prominent in tunnels with a larger cover depth placed in granular soils of higher friction angles. Because of this, the bottom tunnel's support pressure is highly influenced by the change in the soil friction angle.

Effect of horizontal acceleration coefficient: The support pressure increases with the horizontal acceleration coefficient, k_h . The k_h value represents the amplitude of horizontal seismic acceleration at the base of the domain, that is, $k_h = a_h(H, t)/g$. By its dependence on k_h and the depth from the ground surface, an increase in k_h value increases the magnitude of $a_h(z, t)/g$, increasing the seismic body force. An increase in the seismic body force decreases the tunnel's stability, thus increasing the support pressure. Fig. 6.9 plots the absolute percentage difference in top and bottom tunnel support pressures as k_h increases from 0 to 0.1. The role of C/D , and S/D are also depicted considering $\phi = 30^\circ$. Here, $\Delta_{k_h}(\sigma_{s1})$ and $\Delta_{k_h}(\sigma_{s2})$ are the absolute difference magnitudes for top and bottom tunnels, respectively, concerning the change in k_h . Fig. 6.9 can be conceived as the effect of seismicity on the tunnel support pressure as it is plotted by varying the condition from static ($k_h = 0$) to seismic ($k_h = 0.1$).

FIGURE 6.9: Effect of k_h : Absolute percentage difference in support pressure values, $\Delta_{k_h}(\sigma_{s1})$ and $\Delta_{k_h}(\sigma_{s2})$, between $k_h = 0$ and 0.1 for (a) $C/D = 1$, and (b) $C/D = 3$.

As seen in Fig. 6.9, the change in k_h has a little effect on the support pressure of tunnels placed far apart (higher S/D). The reason is due to the decrement in the interference effect between the two tunnels with S/D . The above drop in the effect of k_h on support pressure with S/D is noticeable since $\phi = 30^\circ$. It has been observed that for a friction angle, the higher is the soil shear strength, and more rigid is the change in support pressures with k_h . Comparing figures 6.9(a) and (b), it can be seen that k_h influences the support pressure the most for a lower C/D . This is due to the non-linear decrease in the seismic acceleration with depth which reduces the body force magnitude in the vicinity of the tunnel at a larger cover depth. Hence, seismicity has a strong influence on the top tunnel's stability than the bottom.

Effect of center-to-center distance between tunnels: As the center-to-center separation distance between the tunnels, S/D , increases, support pressure magnitudes for top and bottom tunnels decrease. When two tunnels are far apart, the interference of one tunnel over the other decreases, decreasing the support pressure requirement. The variation of support pressures in Fig. 6.7 with S/D enunciates the influence of soil arching on the seismic stability. For any C/D , k_h , and ϕ , there exists a critical value of S/D till which the support pressure for bottom tunnel is higher than the top, and it plummets thereafter. The hypothesis is that the effect of overburden on $\sigma_{s_2}/\gamma D$ is prevalent till the critical S/D beyond which the soil arching takes over. Hence, the bottom tunnel's support pressure for S/D greater than the aforementioned critical value is lower than the top tunnel's support pressure.

Fig. 6.10 plots the absolute difference in top and bottom tunnel support pressure due to increment in S/D for different C/D , k_h and ϕ values. Here, $\Delta_{S/D}(\sigma_{s_1})$ and $\Delta_{S/D}(\sigma_{s_2})$ refer to the absolute difference the support pressure for the change in S/D for top and bottom tunnels, respectively. From Fig. 6.10, for any C/D , k_h , and ϕ , the bottom tunnel's

FIGURE 6.10: Effect of S/D : Absolute percentage difference in support pressure values, $\Delta_{S/D}(\sigma_{s1})$ and $\Delta_{S/D}(\sigma_{s2})$, between the extreme S/D values considered in the parametric study for (a) $C/D = 1$, and (b) $C/D = 3$.

support pressure is strongly affected by the change in S/D than the top one. Since it is the bottom tunnel that shifts its position with S/D , its support pressure is highly sensitive to the center-to-center distance. The above effect is prominent for a lower value of soil friction angle. Further, as k_h increases, the support pressure for top and bottom tunnels is increasingly sensitive to the change in S/D , as evident from the increase in $\Delta_{S/D}(\sigma_{s1})$ and $\Delta_{S/D}(\sigma_{s2})$ with k_h in Fig. 6.10.

6.5.3 Collapse patterns

Utilizing the primal-dual interior point algorithm of MOSEK (2022), nodal velocity patterns have been obtained for various combinations of problem parameters to observe the collapse patterns of soil surrounding piggyback twin tunnels and consequent interaction effects. Figures 6.11 and 6.12 illustrate the influence of center-to-center separation distance between the tunnels, S/D , and soil friction angle, ϕ , considering static and seismic conditions, respectively. The extent of velocity vectors with a significant length has been marked in these figures. Here, $C/D = 1$ has been used. For a static loading, Fig. 6.11 depict a symmetric collapse pattern for any S/D and ϕ . For piggyback tunnels with a

close center-to-center spacing, Fig. 6.11(a) illustrate the formation of a global or *unified* collapse pattern encompassing both tunnels. As the bottom tunnel moves farther, i.e., as S/D increases, figures 6.11(b) and (c) depict the gradual separation of collapse pattern indicating a more localized soil failure around each tunnel. The velocity pattern in Fig. 6.11(b) indicate the intermediate stage of S/D where the separation distance is neither large for a individual soil collapse nor small for a unified pattern. The soil friction angle influences the aforementioned localization of the collapse pattern. In essence, the higher the friction angle, lower is the extent of soil collapse; thus, more "local" is the collapse pattern.

FIGURE 6.11: Velocity patterns highlighting the effect of center-to-center distance and soil friction angle for static loading ($k_h = 0$).

Fig. 6.12 shows the velocity patterns for seismic loadings with $k_h = 0.1$, $k_v = k_h/2$, $t/T = 0.5$, and $\omega_s H/V_s = 0.4\pi$. Compared to Fig. 6.11, the extent of collapse patterns in Fig. 6.12 is higher for seismic cases for obvious reasons. Moreover, velocity patterns in Fig. 6.12 are not symmetric owing to the asymmetric seismic loading and lopsided along the horizontal acceleration's direction. As mentioned in section 6.5.1, the direction

of base horizontal acceleration is along the negative X axis for $t/T = 0.5$. Since $\omega_s H/V_s = 0.4\pi < \pi/2$, horizontal acceleration's direction is *preserved* from the base to the ground surface. Therefore, the direction of $a_h(z, t)/g$ is along the negative X axis throughout the soil domain, which is reflected in the left-sided collapse patterns in Fig. 6.12. Similar to the static case, an independent failure mode occurs as S/D increases. But the minimum value of S/D for which an independent failure occurs (critical S/D) is higher for a seismic loading than the static case. For example, Fig. 6.11(c) shows that an independent failure occurs for static condition using $S/D = 6$. On the other hand, for the same parameters, Fig. 6.12(c) illustrates that the integrated failure cannot be ignored for $k_h = 0.1$. Fig. 6.12(d) highlights that the effect of seismicity on soil failure drops with soil friction angle. This is significant for the lower tunnel, whereas the failure mode for the top tunnel is still skewed. Moreover, the critical S/D required for an independent failure decreases with friction angle. Thus, an integrated failure in Fig. 6.12(c) for $\phi = 30^\circ$ evolved to an independent failure configuration in Fig. 6.12(d) for $\phi = 45^\circ$, even though S/D is the same. Insets in Fig. 6.12 also depict that a small portion of soil tends to move out of the domain due to large horizontal seismic forces at $\omega_s H/V_s = 0.4\pi$, which is due to the proximity of the selected frequency to shear wave's fundamental frequency. The region of this impending upward soil movement reduces with S/D and ϕ due to a reduced interaction of bottom tunnel over the top.

Based on the failure surfaces observed from nodal velocity patterns, some of the common failure modes of piggyback twin tunnels under seismic loading are represented schematically in Fig. 6.13. It highlights the effects of C/D , S/D , ϕ , and k_h . Failure surface encompasses both tunnels for a lower S/D , C/D and ϕ under static and seismic loadings. When C/D increases, keeping S/D constant, a deep tunnel failure occurs as the failure surface's contour meets itself and does not reach to the ground surface. A lop-sided failure occurs under seismic loadings and the extent of the failure surface reduces

FIGURE 6.12: Velocity patterns showing the effect of center-to-center distance and soil friction angle for seismic loadings ($k_h = 0.1$).

with soil friction angle value. For S/D greater than the critical center-to-center distance, both tunnels fail independently. The magnitude of this critical S/D depends mainly on the values of k_h and ϕ . The critical S/D increases with k_h but reduces with ϕ . Failure modes under seismic conditions contained a small portion of soil moving out of the domain indicating a heave. The occurrence and extent of this region is dependent on C/D , S/D , k_h , ϕ , and $\omega_s H/V_s$. The region of heave reduces with increase in C/D , S/D and ϕ , and increases with increase in k_h . Its extent increases when S-wave's dimensionless frequency is close to its fundamental frequency.

FIGURE 6.13: Schematic representation of various failure modes in piggyback dual tunnels.

6.5.4 Horizontal and vertical stress contours

The current subsection discusses the effect of S/D , k_h , and ϕ on the normalized horizontal ($\sigma_x/\gamma D$) and vertical ($\sigma_z/\gamma D$) stress contours as shown in figures 6.14 and 6.15. Fig. 6.14 has been plotted for static cases and Fig. 6.15 for seismic conditions using $C/D = 1$. Here, wherever required, $k_h = 0$ (or) 0.1 , $k_v = k_h/2$, $t/T = 0.5$, and $\omega_s H/V_s = 0.4\pi$. The symmetric nature of stress contours in Fig. 6.14 is due to the absence of seismic loading. On the other hand, the contours Fig. 6.15 are lopsided towards the direction of $a_h(z, t)/g$. For any input parameters, the magnitude of horizontal stress increases with depth and drops near the tunnel periphery. On the other hand, the vertical stress reduces

with depth, and this decrease is transferred to the adjacent portion on either side of both tunnels by an arch mechanism. This increment in vertical stress is momentary and it is unaffected by tunneling at farther sections from dual tunnels. From figures 6.14 and 6.15, as S/D increases, stress magnitudes over the bottom tunnel momentarily tend towards their initial distribution up to a certain distance from the top tunnel. Beyond this depth, the arching effect of the bottom tunnel comes into play, thus, reducing the stress magnitudes. Furthermore, figures 6.14 and 6.15 show that dual tunnels tend to act as a single entity when $S/D = 1.5$ and this behavior reduces with S/D . Nonetheless, the effect of soil arching is more prominent in the bottom tunnel than the top as it is placed at a higher depth from the ground surface. This explains the decrease in bottom tunnel's support pressure at greater S/D values (refer to Fig. 6.7).

Based on the stress contours examined in the present study, the soil surrounding the tunnels can be categorized into several zones depending on the stress distribution. Fig. 6.16 shows a schematic representation of zones around the tunnels because of soil arching. Zones over the top tunnel comprise an undisturbed zone followed by arch and loosened zones. The stress variations in the undisturbed zone are not affected by tunneling. In the arch zone, the horizontal stress increases with depth, often beyond its magnitude without a tunnel. The vertical stress increases with depth in the arch zone, but its magnitude is less than γz . The loosened zone is characterized by the decrease in $\sigma_x/\gamma D$ and $\sigma_z/\gamma D$. The above-said characteristics of soil arching zones over the top tunnel is similar to that of a single circular tunnel at the same depth (Chen et al., 2022b; Lin et al., 2022).

FIGURE 6.14: Contours of normalized horizontal and vertical stresses for a static loading with the effect of separation distance and soil friction angle.

--- Collapse pattern

$C/D = 1, k_h = 0.1, k_v = k_h/2, t/T = 0.5, \omega_s H/V_s = 0.4\pi, \zeta = 7\%$

FIGURE 6.15: For seismic loadings, contours of normalized horizontal and vertical stresses showing the effect of separation distance and soil friction angle.

FIGURE 6.16: Schematic representation of zones due to soil arching.

6.5.5 Normal stress distribution around the tunnel periphery

Normal stress distribution around the tunnel periphery is studied for typical variations in problem parameters, as shown in figures 6.17 and 6.18. In these figures, the normal stress is represented in the dimensionless form, normalized with the unit weight γ and tunnel diameter D . Thus, the normalized normal stresses on the top and bottom tunnels are defined as $\sigma_{n1}/\gamma D$ and $\sigma_{n2}/\gamma D$, respectively. Also, the angles represent the angle made by the radial lines from the tunnel's center to the nodes along the tunnel periphery, measured from the positive direction of the X-axis. Fig. 6.17 shows the variation of the normal stresses for $C/D = 1$ and 3 under static loading with $\phi = 30^\circ$ and 45° . Since the static loading is symmetric, the normal stresses are observed to be symmetric about the vertical plane through the tunnel's center. From Fig. 6.17, the normal stresses for both tunnels reduce as the value of S/D increases. This explains the reduction in the support pressure values for the top and bottom tunnels in Fig. 6.7 as S/D increases. Similarly, it can be inferred that an increase in the soil friction angle reduces the normal stresses.

FIGURE 6.17: Normal stress distribution around the tunnel periphery for static conditions highlighting the effect of cover depth, separation distance, and soil friction angle.

FIGURE 6.18: Normal stress distribution around the tunnel periphery for seismic conditions highlighting the effect of cover depth, separation distance, and soil friction angle.

Moreover, the change in the normal stress as S/D increases is more significant for the bottom tunnel than the top one. Comparing figures 6.17(a) and (b), the normal stresses increase for static loading as the tunnel cover depth-to-diameter ratio increases. From Fig. 6.17, while for all other S/D values, the normal stress on the top tunnel's invert is near zero, for $S/D = 1.5$ alone, its magnitude is significant. This increase in the magnitude of the normal stress is due to the interference of the bottom tunnel on the top one. On the other hand, the normal stress magnitude for the bottom tunnel is higher near its crown, for $S/D = 1.5$, than in other locations owing to the interference from the top tunnel. Such changes in the normal stresses are not significant for $\phi = 45^\circ$ (refer to Fig 6.17(c)).

Fig. 6.18 illustrates the normal stress distribution for the top and bottom tunnels under seismic loading. Fig. 6.18(a) is plotted for $C/D = 1$, and figures 6.18(b) and (c) for for $C/D = 3$. Here, $\phi = 30^\circ, 45^\circ$, $k_h = 0.1$, $t/T = 0.5$, and $\omega_s H/V_s = 0.4\pi$ are used. The seismic loading is directional and reflected in the lopsided normal stress distribution. Since $\omega_s H/V_s = 0.4\pi$, the normal stresses on the left-hand side of the tunnel periphery are higher than on the right-hand side. Similar to the static loading, it can be seen in Fig. 6.18 that the normal stress on the top tunnel's invert is significant for $S/D = 1.5$. The maximum normal stress on the top tunnel is higher for $C/D = 1$ (Fig. 6.18(a)) than for $C/D = 3$ (Fig. 6.18(b)). Thus, for a tunnel with a low S/D value, the seismic forces cause the maximum normal stress on the top tunnel for $C/D = 1$ than $C/D = 3$, which aligns with the explanation provided in subsection 6.5.2. From the normal stress distributions of the top and bottom tunnels in Fig. 6.18, it is clear that the rate of decrease in the normal stresses with S/D is more significant for the bottom tunnel than the top one. Also, comparing figures 6.17(a) and 6.18(a), the increase in the normal stress, for both tunnels, due to an increase in k_h is more significant for $S/D = 1.5$. This effect ceases more quickly for the top tunnel than the bottom tunnel as S/D increases. The observation mentioned above are consistent at higher friction angles.

6.6 Summary

The present chapter analyzed the seismic stability of piggyback dual circular tunnels in dry, isotropic, and homogeneous granular soils. The vertically propagating, in-plane shear and primary waves were accounted for in the body forces using the modified pseudo-dynamic method. The greatest lower-bound solutions for the problem were found using the second-order cone programming technique. The normalized support pressure for top and bottom tunnels reduced with the center-to-center separation distance because of the drop in the interference of one tunnel over the other. Piggyback dual tunnels placed close to each other induced a unified soil collapse, whereas an individual collapse was observed for higher separation distances. Three zones of soil arching were observed concerning the horizontal and vertical stress variations over each tunnel - undisturbed, arch, and loose zones over the top tunnel, and disturbed, arch, and loosened zones over the bottom tunnel.

7

Single tunnels in granular media with heterogeneous wave velocities

7.1 General

From Chapter 2, several studies consider the seismic wave propagation velocities to be uniform throughout the depth. But the actual wave velocity profile is not necessarily homogeneous everywhere. Analytical solutions for the dynamic characteristics of the soil with a continuously varying shear wave velocity have been reported by Gazetas (1982). Here, the shear wave velocity was proportional to $V_0 (1 + mz)^\kappa$, where V_0 is the shear wave velocity at the ground surface, z is the depth from the ground surface, and m and κ are coefficients determining the nature of the shear wave velocity variation. Dakoulas and Gazetas (1985) used the depth-varied shear modulus, defined as $G(z) = G_b (z/H)^m$, to study the seismic response of dams and embankments by developing analytical solutions for the amplification function, natural frequencies, and mode shapes. Here, G_b is the shear modulus at the base ($z = H$), and m is the heterogeneity parameter. Analytical solutions were developed by Vrettos (1990) for bounded and unbounded inhomogeneity in the shear modulus for soil subjected to SH waves, where two types of inhomogeneous variation

were considered - exponentially decaying and as a third root of the depth from the ground surface. Towhata (1996) produced analytical solutions on the one-dimensional shear wave propagation in a soil medium considering the shear modulus to vary as $G(z) = A(z+G_0)^l$, G_0 is the shear modulus at the ground surface ($z = 0$), and the parameters A and l govern the variation of the shear modulus, with A controlling the overall magnitude of $G(z)$. Travasarou and Gazetas (2004) studied the seismic response of soils whose shear wave velocity varies continuously with depth as $V_s(z) = \eta z^{m/2}$ including the case of vanishing wave velocity at the ground surface. The parameters η and m govern the overall wave velocity distribution through depth. Rovithis et al. (2011) proposed analytical solutions to the amplification function, natural frequency, and mode shape for a single and a layered heterogeneous soil medium by modeling it to be a visco-elastic solid. The continuous shear wave velocity was modeled using the generalized power-law function. Using the different definitions of the shear wave velocity, numerous studies are available to assess the stability of geotechnical structures like shallow and deep foundations (Gazetas, 1981; Laora and Rovithis, 2015; Medina et al., 2020; Anoyatis et al., 2023), and retaining walls (Psarropoulos et al., 2005; Vrettos et al., 2016; Brandenberg et al., 2017).

Very few studies are available for determining the dynamic response of tunnel lining considering inhomogeneity in shear velocity of soil deposits (Amorosi and Boldini, 2009; Tsinidis et al., 2016; Huang et al., 2020, 2021; Abate et al., 2023). Amorosi and Boldini (2009) numerically evaluated the loads in the transverse direction of the circular tunnel's lining due to seismicity using the finite element procedure where the shear modulus was considered a continuous function of the mean stress. Tsinidis et al. (2016) studied the dynamic responses of a circular tunnel in dry sand using the complete dynamic analysis with the consideration that the shear modulus is a function of the mean effective stress. Huang et al. (2020, 2021) proposed the seismic fragility curves for the transverse dynamic response of a circular tunnel embedded in soft soil deposits where the shear wave velocity

profiles varied with depth but not as a continuous function. Recently, Abate et al. (2023) studied the influence of wave velocity heterogeneity in the seismic behavior of a circular tunnel considering the shear wave velocity vary linearly with depth.

In this chapter, closed-form solutions to the governing equations of the seismic body wave propagation in a medium with heterogeneous wave velocities are derived, and then applied to obtain the support pressure for stability of a circular tunnel in granular soils. The heterogeneous wave velocity profile has been characterized using the generalized power-law function. Earlier, Rovithis et al. (2011) obtained the analytical solution for the horizontal displacement amplitude considering this mathematical model, and the solution is incomplete. This is because the solution satisfies only the zero-traction boundary condition on the ground surface, and it contains an integration constant suggesting the closed-form solution is yet to be found. Furthermore, Rovithis et al. (2011) only solved the space dependency of horizontal seismic acceleration while the temporal effect as well as the vertical acceleration effect was unattended. On the other hand, seismic accelerations from the present study satisfy all the boundary conditions of the problem, i.e., zero shear and normal tractions on the ground surface, and displacement compatibility at the domain base. As a result of this, the formulations proposed in this chapter are complete and include both space and time variations in seismic accelerations. Using the developed formulations based on the spatiotemporal variation of horizontal and vertical seismic accelerations, the influence of in-homogeneity in wave velocities on the stability of circular tunnels placed in granular soils was studied in detail.

7.2 Problem description

Fig. 7.1 illustrates a circular tunnel of diameter, D , placed at a cover depth C in a dry, isotropic granular medium. The granular medium of depth H is subjected to harmonic base shaking giving rise to the propagation of in-plane shear and primary waves. The wave propagation velocities of these body waves are considered depth dependent, characterized using the generalized power-law function. The soil friction angle (ϕ) and unit weight (γ) are considered invariant with depth and direction and deemed not affected by the seismic loading. Furthermore, none of the parameters have been considered to vary with the harmonic loading and shear strain of the soil. Similar to previous chapters, plane-strain conditions prevail, and the soil-tunnel lining interface is considered smooth. The normal stresses from the surrounding soil will vary around the tunnel support systems owing to the primary and shear seismic wave propagation in the soil. The maximum of these stresses along the tunnel periphery is considered the minimum resistance, i.e., support pressure σ_s to be provided by the lining material for the tunnel stability.

FIGURE 7.1: Schematic description of the present problem of circular tunnels placed in a medium of inhomogeneous wave velocities.

7.3 Analysis

7.3.1 Mathematical formulations for spatiotemporal variation of seismic accelerations

The mathematical formulations to obtain the variations of seismic horizontal and vertical accelerations with space and time for an inhomogeneous soil layer with thickness H over a rigid bedrock have been derived, considering the heterogeneous variation in the wave velocities. The density of soil mass (ρ) and damping ratio (ξ) are considered constant with depth. The wave propagation velocities of the shear and primary waves were considered continuous functions of depth governed by a generalized power-law function. Further, the soil is dry and isotropic.

7.3.1.1 Horizontal seismic acceleration

The generalized power-law function that governs the variation of shear wave velocity, V_s , with depth (z) is given as (Rovithis et al., 2011)

$$V_s(z) = V_{sH} \left(b_s + q_s \frac{z}{H} \right)^{n_s} \quad (7.1)$$

In Eq. 7.1, $b_s = (V_{s0}/V_{sH})^{1/n_s}$ and $q_s = 1 - b_s$. Here, V_{s0} and V_{sH} are the shear wave velocities recorded at the ground surface ($z = 0$) and base ($z = H$), respectively. Further, the variation in the shear modulus with depth is governed by the heterogeneity parameter n . If $n_s \rightarrow 0$, the variation of $V_s(z)$ tends to be uniform with depth, and when $n_s \rightarrow 1$, $V_s(z)$ tends to be linear.

The governing differential equation for a vertically propagating shear wave can be written as (Kramer, 2007)

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left[G(z) \frac{\partial u(z, t)}{\partial z} \right] = \rho \frac{\partial^2 u(z, t)}{\partial t^2} \quad (7.2)$$

Assuming that the soil is subjected to harmonic excitation, the horizontal displacement, $u(z, t)$, can be written as follows (Towhata, 1996; Kramer, 2007)

$$u(z, t) = \mathcal{U}(z) \cdot e^{i\omega_s t} \quad (7.3)$$

Here, $\mathcal{U}(z)$ is the amplitude of the horizontal displacement, varied with depth, z . Substituting Eq. 7.3 in Eq. 7.2 the differential equation can be expressed as

$$\frac{d}{dz} \left[G(z) \cdot \frac{d\mathcal{U}(z)}{dz} \right] + \rho\omega_s^2 \mathcal{U}(z) = 0 \quad (7.4)$$

In Eq. 7.4, $G(z)$ is the depth-dependent shear modulus. For a soil of constant density ρ and shear wave velocity $V_s(z)$ (refer to Eq. 7.1), $G(z) = \rho V_s(z)^2 = \rho V_{sH}^2 \left(b_s + q_s \frac{z}{H} \right)^{2n_s}$. Substituting for $G(z)$ in Eq. 7.4,

$$\frac{d}{dz} \left[\rho V_{sH}^2 \cdot \left(b_s + q_s \frac{z}{H} \right)^{2n_s} \cdot \frac{d\mathcal{U}}{dz} \right] + \rho\omega_s^2 \mathcal{U}(z) = 0 \quad (7.5)$$

Simplifying Eq. 7.5 and using the wave number for shear wave at the base, $k_{sH} = \omega_s/V_{sH}$,

$$\frac{d^2 \mathcal{U}}{dz^2} + \frac{2n_s q_s}{H} \frac{1}{\left(b_s + q_s \frac{z}{H} \right)} \frac{d\mathcal{U}}{dz} + \left[\frac{k_{sH}}{\left(b_s + q_s \frac{z}{H} \right)^{n_s}} \right]^2 \mathcal{U}(z) = 0 \quad (7.6)$$

Using a linear transformation, $X_s = b_s + q_s \frac{z}{H}$, and applying the chain rule twice, Eq. 7.6 can be simplified as

$$\frac{d^2\mathcal{U}}{dX_s^2} + \frac{2n_s}{X_s} \frac{d\mathcal{U}}{dX_s} + \left(\frac{k_{sH}H}{qX_s^{n_s}} \right)^2 \mathcal{U}(z) = 0 \quad (7.7)$$

which is in the standard form of Bessel's differential equation. Considering the most common case of $0 < n_s < 1$ (Towhata, 1996; Rovithis et al., 2011), the general solution of Eq. 7.7 can be written as

$$\mathcal{U}(X_s) = (X_s)^{\mu_s} [A_1 \mathcal{J}_{\nu_s}(\lambda_s X_s^{\ell_s/2}) + A_2 \mathcal{Y}_{\nu_s}(\lambda_s X_s^{\ell_s/2})] \quad (7.8)$$

where $\mathcal{J}_{\nu_s}(\cdot)$ and $\mathcal{Y}_{\nu_s}(\cdot)$ are the Bessel functions of the first and second kind, respectively, and of order ν_s ; A_1 and A_2 are the integration constants, to be found from the known boundary conditions. The dimensionless parameter ℓ_s denotes the step of the associated power-series solutions (Wylie and Barrett, 1982). Furthermore, the parameters μ_s and ν_s are obtained from the asymptotic behavior near the origin, and the definition of the parameter k_{sH} should satisfy the asymptotic behavior of the solution at large values of X_s . Based on these, the parameters in Eq. 7.8 could be listed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_s &= \frac{1 - 2n_s}{2} \\ \lambda_s &= \frac{2k_{sH}H}{q_s \ell_s} = \frac{2}{q_s \ell_s} \left(\frac{\omega_s H}{V_{sH}} \right) \\ \ell_s &= 2(1 - n_s) \\ \nu_s &= \frac{2n_s - 1}{2(1 - n_s)} \end{aligned}$$

According to Towhata (1996), the shear stress varies harmonically in space-time as

$$\tau(z, t) = \mathcal{T}(z) \cdot e^{i\omega_s t} \quad (7.9)$$

Here, $\mathcal{T}(z)$ is the shear stress amplitude varied with depth. We know, $\tau = G(z)du/dz \implies \mathcal{T}(z) = G(z)d\mathcal{U}/dz$. One of the boundary conditions to solve Eq. 7.8 is that, at the ground surface, $z = 0$, the shear stress, $\tau(0, t)$, should vanish. Therefore, from Eq. 7.9, $\tau(0, t) = 0 \implies \mathcal{T}(0) = G(0)d\mathcal{U}/dz = 0$. From the linear transformation, $d\mathcal{U}/dz = (q_s/H)d\mathcal{U}/dX_s$. Considering a finite shear modulus at the ground surface, i.e., $b_s \neq 0$, for $\mathcal{T}(0) = 0$ to hold, $\left. \frac{d\mathcal{U}}{dz} \right|_{z=0}$ should vanish to obtain the following relationship between A_1 and A_2 .

$$A_2 = -A_1 \frac{\mathcal{J}_{\nu_s+1}(\lambda_s \cdot b_s^{\ell_s/2})}{\mathcal{Y}_{\nu_s+1}(\lambda_s \cdot b_s^{\ell_s/2})} \quad (7.10)$$

Substituting Eq. 7.10 to Eq. 7.8, and rearranging the terms we get

$$\mathcal{U}(X_s) = \frac{A_1(X_s)^{\mu_s}}{\mathcal{Y}_{\nu_s+1}(\lambda_s b_s^{\ell_s/2})} \left[\mathcal{J}_{\nu_s}(\lambda_s X_s^{\ell_s/2}) \cdot \mathcal{Y}_{\nu_s+1}(\lambda_s b_s^{\ell_s/2}) - \mathcal{J}_{\nu_s+1}(\lambda_s b_s^{\ell_s/2}) \cdot \mathcal{Y}_{\nu_s}(\lambda_s X_s^{\ell_s/2}) \right] \quad (7.11)$$

At this stage, Rovithis et al. (2011) changed the independent variable in Eq. 7.11 from X_s to z . Thus, the final expression of the horizontal seismic displacement by Rovithis et al. (2011) depended only on depth, z . But, it is well-known that seismic accelerations vary with time and space. In the present study, the spatial and temporal variations in the seismic acceleration are considered by equating the horizontal displacement amplitude at the base to the known base excitation amplitude. By doing this, the constant A_1 in Eq. 7.11 has been eliminated, and the complete solution to the differential equation, Eq. 7.2, has been found.

Let the harmonic excitation at the base of the domain be $u(H, t) = \mathcal{U}_{hb} \cdot e^{i\omega_s t}$. Employing the boundary condition $\mathcal{U}(H) = \mathcal{U}_{hb}$, the constant A_1 can be written as

$$A_1 = \frac{\mathcal{U}_{hb} \cdot \mathcal{Y}_{\nu_s+1}(\lambda_s b_s^{\ell_s/2})}{(b_s + q_s)^{\mu_s}} \frac{1}{\left[\begin{array}{l} \mathcal{J}_{\nu_s}(\lambda_s (b_s + q_s)^{\ell_s/2}) \cdot \mathcal{Y}_{\nu_s+1}(\lambda_s b_s^{\ell_s/2}) \\ - \mathcal{J}_{\nu_s+1}(\lambda_s b_s^{\ell_s/2}) \cdot \mathcal{Y}_{\nu_s}(\lambda_s (b_s + q_s)^{\ell_s/2}) \end{array} \right]} \quad (7.12)$$

Substituting for A_1 , from Eq. 7.12, in Eq. 7.11, and changing the dependent variable back to z using the relation $X_s = b_s + q_s \frac{z}{H}$, the complete solution for the horizontal displacement amplitude can be written as

$$\mathcal{U}(z) = \mathcal{U}_{hb} \cdot TF_h(z) \quad (7.13)$$

where, \mathcal{U}_{hb} is the horizontal displacement amplitude at the base, and $TF_h(z)$ is the transfer function. The transfer function for the shear wave is given as

$$TF_h(z) = \frac{\mathcal{U}(z)}{\mathcal{U}(H)} = \left(\frac{b_s + q_s \frac{z}{H}}{b_s + q_s} \right)^{\mu_s} \cdot \left[\frac{B_{sz}}{B_{sH}} \right] \quad (7.14)$$

Here,

$$B_{sz} = \mathcal{J}_{\nu_s} \left(\lambda_s \left(b_s + q_s \frac{z}{H} \right)^{\ell_s/2} \right) \cdot \mathcal{Y}_{\nu_s+1} (\lambda_s b_s^{\ell_s/2}) - \mathcal{J}_{\nu_s+1} (\lambda_s b_s^{\ell_s/2}) \cdot \mathcal{Y}_{\nu_s} \left(\lambda_s \left(b_s + q_s \frac{z}{H} \right)^{\ell_s/2} \right) \quad (7.15)$$

$$B_{sH} = \mathcal{J}_{\nu_s} \left(\lambda_s (b_s + q_s)^{\ell_s/2} \right) \cdot \mathcal{Y}_{\nu_s+1} (\lambda_s b_s^{\ell_s/2}) - \mathcal{J}_{\nu_s+1} (\lambda_s b_s^{\ell_s/2}) \cdot \mathcal{Y}_{\nu_s} \left(\lambda_s (b_s + q_s)^{\ell_s/2} \right) \quad (7.16)$$

The space-time variation of the horizontal displacement could be obtained by substituting $\mathcal{U}(z)$ from Eq. 7.13 to Eq. 7.3 as

$$u(z, t) = \mathcal{U}_{hb} \cdot TF_h(z) \cdot e^{i\omega_s t} \quad (7.17)$$

By differentiating Eq. 7.17 twice with respect to time, the horizontal acceleration in space-time can be obtained as follows

$$a_h(z, t) = \ddot{u}(z, t) = -\omega_s^2 \cdot \mathcal{U}_{hb} \cdot TF_h(z) \cdot e^{i\omega_s t} \quad (7.18)$$

Here, $-\omega_s^2 \cdot \mathcal{U}_{hb}$ is the amplitude of horizontal seismic acceleration at the base. Let k_h be the seismic acceleration coefficient in the horizontal direction; hence $k_h \cdot g$ denotes the horizontal seismic acceleration's amplitude at the base. Using this, $a_h(z, t)$ can be expressed as

$$a_h(z, t) = \Re [\mathcal{A}_h(z) \times e^{i\omega_s t}] = \Re [\mathcal{A}_h(z) \times e^{i(\omega_s t - 2\pi t/T_s)}] \quad (7.19)$$

$$\mathcal{A}_h(z) = k_h \times g \times TF_h(z)$$

In Eq. 7.19, \Re denotes the real part, $\mathcal{A}_h(z)$ denotes the depth varied horizontal seismic acceleration amplitude with $\mathcal{A}_h(H) = k_h \times g$, ω_s and T_s are the angular frequency and period of the shear wave, respectively. In these equations, g is the acceleration due to gravity. To account for the soil damping due to shear wave propagation, ξ_s , in the above equations, $G(z)$ and $V_s(z)$ could be replaced with $\tilde{G}(z) = G(1 + 2i\xi_s)$ and $\tilde{V}_s(z) = V_s(z)\sqrt{1 + 2i\xi_s}$, respectively (Kramer, 2007; Rovithis et al., 2011). The amplification factor for the horizontal acceleration, \mathcal{F}_h , is defined as the ratio of the horizontal acceleration at the ground surface to that at the base, that is,

$$\mathcal{F}_h = \frac{u(0, t)}{u(H, t)} = \frac{a_h(0, t)}{a_h(H, t)}$$

Substituting the corresponding expressions, the horizontal amplification ratio can be expressed as

$$\mathcal{F}_h = \frac{(b_s)^{\mu_s}}{(b_s + q_s)^{\mu_s}} \left[\frac{B_{s0}}{B_{sH}} \right] \quad (7.20)$$

$$B_{s0} = \mathcal{J}_{\nu_s} \left(\lambda_s (b_s)^{\ell_s/2} \right) \cdot \mathcal{Y}_{\nu_s+1} \left(\lambda_s b_s^{\ell_s/2} \right) - \mathcal{J}_{\nu_s+1} \left(\lambda_s b_s^{\ell_s/2} \right) \cdot \mathcal{Y}_{\nu_s} \left(\lambda_s (b_s)^{\ell_s/2} \right)$$

Here B_{s0} is obtained by substituting $z = 0$ in Eq. 7.15, and B_{sH} is as given in Eq. 7.16.

7.3.1.2 Vertical seismic acceleration

The expression for a space-time varied vertical seismic acceleration has been derived in a similar process as that for the horizontal acceleration. The primary wave velocity profile has been considered to follow the generalized power-law function as

$$V_p(z) = V_{pH} \left(b_p + q_p \frac{z}{H} \right)^{n_p} \quad (7.21)$$

Here, $b_p = (V_{p0}/V_{pH})^{1/n_p}$, $q_p = 1 - b_p$, and n_p is the power parameter for the primary wave. Similar to the shear wave velocity parameters, V_{p0} and V_{pH} are the primary wave velocities measured at the ground surface and base of the domain, respectively. A near constant primary wave velocity can be modeled by considering n_p closer to zero, and a linear variation by using n_p closer to unity. In order to solve the governing equation for a one-dimensional primary wave propagation in a heterogeneous soil, the constrained modulus, $E_c(z) = V_p^2(z) \times \rho$, has been substituted using the continuously varying primary wave function from Eq. 7.21. Similar to the harmonic propagation of the shear wave, the harmonic vertical displacement, $v(z, t)$, with an amplitude $\mathcal{V}(z)$, can be written as $v(z, t) = \mathcal{V}(z) \cdot e^{i\omega_p t}$ where, ω_p is the angular frequency of the primary wave. Proceeding in the similar fashion, the general solution to the standard Bessel's differential equation has been obtained. One of the boundary conditions to solve this equation is that the normal stress at the ground surface should vanish. The normal stress has been defined as a harmonic function of space and time, similar to the shear stress, i.e., $\sigma_{zz}(z, t) = \mathcal{S}(z) \cdot e^{i\omega_p t}$. For a primary wave propagating vertically along the z direction, $\sigma_{zz} = E_c(z)dv/dz \Rightarrow \mathcal{S}(z) = E_c(z)d\mathcal{V}/dz$ (Kramer, 2007). Assuming a non-zero primary wave velocity at the ground surface, and taking advantage of the linear transformation, a relation could be obtained between the constants in the general solution. The spatiotemporal vertical displacements has been derived by invoking the other boundary

condition at the domain base, that is the harmonic base excitation $v(H, t) = \mathcal{V}_{vb} \cdot e^{i\omega_p t}$. Following the similar procedure, the amplitude of the vertical acceleration, $\mathcal{V}(z)$ shall be written as

$$\mathcal{V}(z) = \mathcal{V}_{vb} \cdot TF_v(z) \quad (7.22)$$

Correspondingly, \mathcal{V}_{vb} is the vertical displacement amplitude at the base, and $TF_v(z)$ is the transfer function for the primary wave which is given as

$$TF_v(z) = \frac{\mathcal{V}(z)}{\mathcal{V}(H)} = \left(\frac{b_p + q_p \frac{z}{H}}{b_p + q_p} \right)^{\mu_p} \cdot \left[\frac{B_{pz}}{B_{pH}} \right] \quad (7.23)$$

Here,

$$B_{pz} = \mathcal{J}_{\nu_p} \left(\lambda_p \left(b_p + q_p \frac{z}{H} \right)^{\ell_p/2} \right) \cdot \mathcal{Y}_{\nu_p+1} (\lambda_p b_p^{\ell_p/2}) - \mathcal{J}_{\nu_p+1} (\lambda_p b_p^{\ell_p/2}) \cdot \mathcal{Y}_{\nu_p} \left(\lambda_p \left(b_p + q_p \frac{z}{H} \right)^{\ell_p/2} \right) \quad (7.24)$$

$$B_{pH} = \mathcal{J}_{\nu_p} \left(\lambda_p (b_p + q_p)^{\ell_p/2} \right) \cdot \mathcal{Y}_{\nu_p+1} (\lambda_p b_p^{\ell_p/2}) - \mathcal{J}_{\nu_p+1} (\lambda_p b_p^{\ell_p/2}) \cdot \mathcal{Y}_{\nu_p} \left(\lambda_p (b_p + q_p)^{\ell_p/2} \right) \quad (7.25)$$

Also, $\mu_p = (1 - 2n_p) / 2$, $\lambda_p = (2/q_p \ell_p) \times (\omega_p H / V_{pH})$, $\ell_p = 2(1 - n_p)$, and $\nu_p = (2n_p - 1) / 2(1 - n_p)$. By substituting $\mathcal{V}(z)$ from Eq. 7.22 to the expression $v(z, t) = \mathcal{V}(z) \cdot e^{i\omega_p t}$, the vertical displacement as a function of depth and time could be obtained.

Let the amplitude of vertical acceleration at the base be defined using the vertical seismic acceleration coefficient, k_v . Hence, the spatiotemporal variation of vertical acceleration in the soil domain can be expressed as

$$a_v(z, t) = \Re [\mathcal{A}_v(z) \times e^{i\omega_p t}] = \Re [\mathcal{A}_v(z) \times e^{(i \cdot 2\pi \cdot t / T_p)}] \quad (7.26)$$

$$\mathcal{A}_v(z) = k_v \times g \times TF_v(z)$$

Here, \Re denotes the real part, $\mathcal{A}_v(z)$ is the vertical acceleration's amplitude as a function

of depth with $\mathcal{A}_v(H) = k_v \times g$ being the value at the base of the domain, and ω_p and T_p are the angular frequency and period of the primary wave, respectively. The damping ratio for the propagation of the primary wave, ξ_p , can be included into the above equations using the correspondence principle of viscoelasticity (Kramer, 2007). The amplification ratio for the vertical acceleration, \mathcal{F}_v , is defined as

$$\mathcal{F}_v = \frac{v(0, t)}{v(H, t)} = \frac{a_v(0, t)}{a_v(H, t)}$$

Upon substitution \mathcal{F}_v can be written as

$$\mathcal{F}_v = \frac{(b_p)^{\mu_p}}{(b_p + q_p)^{\mu_p}} \left[\frac{B_{p0}}{B_{pH}} \right] \quad (7.27)$$

$$B_{p0} = \mathcal{J}_{\nu_p} \left(\lambda_p (b_p)^{\ell_p/2} \right) \cdot \mathcal{Y}_{\nu_p+1} \left(\lambda_p b_p^{\ell_p/2} \right) - \mathcal{J}_{\nu_p+1} \left(\lambda_p b_p^{\ell_p/2} \right) \cdot \mathcal{Y}_{\nu_p} \left(\lambda_p (b_p)^{\ell_p/2} \right)$$

B_{p0} is obtained by substituting $z = 0$ in the equation for B_{pz} (Eq. 7.24), and B_{pH} is given in Eq. 7.25.

7.3.2 Analysis for computation of support pressure

For computing the support pressure of the circular tunnel, the numerical methodology of the finite element procedure combined with the lower bound theorem of limit analysis and second order conic optimization techniques has been used; the general formulation of this analysis has already been described in section 3.2 in the Chapter 3. The spatiotemporal seismic accelerations $a_h(z, t)/g$ and $a_v(z, t)/g$ along the horizontal and vertical directions as derived in section 7.3.1, was incorporated into the body forces (b_x and b_z) per unit volume of soil for satisfying the element equilibrium condition given in Eq. 3.7. Note that equations 7.19 and 7.26 correspond to free-field seismic accelerations. Since the presence of tunnels has been reported to reduce the seismic ground acceleration (John

and Zahrah, 1987; Cilingir and Madabhushi, 2011; Lanzano et al., 2012; Baziar et al., 2014), it is conservative to use the acceleration functions developed in section 7.3.1 for seismic stability analysis of tunnels. Fig. 7.2 shows a typical finite element mesh used in the present study along with the boundary conditions. Here, LMNO is the domain with LM as the ground surface. The boundaries, LO, MN, and NO were placed such that further changes in their position do not influence the support pressures. Furthermore, $\tau = 0$ has been considered for all nodes along the tunnel periphery for a smooth tunnel-lining interface.

FIGURE 7.2: Typical finite element mesh with boundary conditions.

7.4 Validation of seismic accelerations

The validity of mathematical formulations developed in the previous section is examined by comparing (i) the various seismic quantities from the present study with that of theoretical studies available in the literature Rovithis et al. (2011); Bellezza (2015); Qin and Chian (2020) in subsection 7.4.1, (ii) the seismic responses in frequency domain as well as time and space domains considering a continuous wave velocity with depth in the present analysis against the actual i.e., discrete site data in subsections 7.4.2 and 7.4.3.

7.4.1 Comparison of seismic responses with the previous theoretical studies

In this subsection, various seismic quantities from the present study are validated with the results available in the literature, as shown in Fig. 7.3. Fig. 7.3(a) compares $a_h(z, t)/g$ vs. dimensionless period, t/T , from the present study and of Bellezza (2015). The study by Bellezza (2015) considered the shear wave velocity of the soil to be constant with depth. In the present study, due to the condition $0 < n < 1$, n is taken close to zero ($n = 0.01$), representing a near-uniform wave velocity distribution ($V_s = V_{sH} = V_H$). Here, the acceleration values calculated at the base, $z = H$, and the ground surface, $z = 0$, are compared at three dimensionless frequencies of the shear wave, $\omega_s H/V_s = 0.4\pi, 0.6\pi$, and 1.5π . From Fig. 7.3(b), for $n = 0.01$ of the present study, the amplification factors for horizontal and vertical accelerations (\mathcal{F}_h and \mathcal{F}_v , respectively), varied with $\omega_s H/V_{sH}$, have been found to match well with the results for a uniform wave velocity condition from Qin and Chian (2020).

Thus, from figures 7.3(a) and (b), using $n = 0.01$ closely resembles the soil with a constant wave velocity. The amplification factor for the horizontal acceleration, \mathcal{F}_h , from the present study (for a damping ratio of 5%), was validated with the results available from Rovithis et al. (2011) and found to be in good agreement. Fig. 7.3(c) shows the validation for $V_0/V_H = 0.3$ for different n values. On the other hand, Fig. 7.3(d) gives the validation for $n = 0.6$ with varying values of V_0/V_H . In both Fig. 7.3(c) and Fig. 7.3(d), the abscissa is the input frequency of the shear wave, f , normalized with the fundamental frequency of the heterogeneous soil, f_{1soil} . In all the above discussion, wherever required, consider $n_s = n_p = n$, $V_{s0}/V_{sH} = V_{p0}/V_{pH} = V_0/V_H$, and $V_{pH}/V_{sH} = 1.87$.

FIGURE 7.3: Validation of dimensionless seismic accelerations, $a_h(z, t)/g$ and $a_v(z, t)/g$, and amplification factors, \mathcal{F}_h and \mathcal{F}_v , in various domains from the present study with the results available.

7.4.2 Comparison of seismic response in the frequency domain using the discrete site data

The horizontal amplification factor obtained from Eq. 7.20 of the present study based on a continuous wave velocity profile is validated with those obtained from discrete site data using classical numerical procedures. Figures 7.4 and 7.5 compare the continuous power-law fit to the discrete field data and the frequency domain response, i.e., the horizontal amplification factor (\mathcal{F}_h), from Kaklamanos et al. (2015) and Garcia-Suarez et al. (2021), respectively.

Fig. 7.4(a) shows the generalized power-law fit, performed by varying n to obtain the least Normalized Root Mean Square Error (NRMSE), over the actual discrete data reported in Kaklamanos et al. (2015) for the KiK-net station situated at Nemuro, Japan (NMRH04). Kaklamanos et al. (2015) obtained the amplification ratio as shown in Fig. 7.4(b) for the field data in Fig. 7.4(a) using the Thomson-Haskell matrix method (Thomson, 1950; Haskell, 1953), a classic numerical procedure. From Fig. 7.4(b), it can be inferred that the frequency domain response from the continuous fit of the present study is in reasonable agreement with that reported by Kaklamanos et al. (2015) using the numerical procedure.

FIGURE 7.4: Comparison of the seismic response in the frequency domain using the discrete shear wave velocity data of Kaklamanos et al. (2015).

Another numerical method to obtain transfer functions using discrete field data has been given in Kramer (2007). Employing this method, Garcia-Suarez et al. (2021) computed the amplification ratio for a known field data based on a continuous power-law fit using $n = 0.092$. Fig. 7.5(a) compares the shear wave velocity data, in the dimensionless form, from the continuous fits of Garcia-Suarez et al. (2021) and the present study.

FIGURE 7.5: Comparison of the seismic response in the non-dimensional frequency domain using the discrete shear wave velocity data of Garcia-Suarez et al. (2021).

Further, Fig. 7.5(b) indicates that the amplification ratio computed using the present continuous fit compares well with that reported by Garcia-Suarez et al. (2021) using the algorithm of Kramer (2007) for discrete field data. Here, $f_{1,hom}$ represents the fundamental frequency of a homogeneous deposit. The coherence in frequency domain responses of the site data and the present formulation in figures 7.4 and 7.5 corresponds to the fact that there is no steep impedance gradient in the discrete field data. In such cases, the continuous wave velocity profile can be used to characterize the discrete site data to reasonably estimate the frequency domain response of the site (Garcia-Suarez et al., 2021, 2022).

7.4.3 Comparison of seismic response in time and space domains using discrete site data

7.4.3.1 Seismic response in the time domain

To the best of authors' knowledge, no study is available to compare the seismic response of a site for a heterogeneous wave velocity profile in the time domain. Therefore, the time

domain response of a typical site data reported in Zhao et al. (2021) has been examined using the DEEPSOIL software (Hashash et al., 2020). The seismic response obtained using the DEEPSOIL software from the discrete site data is compared with that from the continuous wave velocity fit of the present study. Fig. 7.6(a) shows the actual site data from Zhao et al. (2021) and the best fit to this data from the present study. Knowing V_0/V_H for the site, $n_s = n = 0.4$ has been fixed since it provided the least NRMSE of 0.015.

FIGURE 7.6: Comparison of seismic horizontal seismic accelerations in time and space domains using the field data from Zhao et al. (2021).

The horizontal acceleration in the time domain from the current research has been validated with that from DEEPSOIL considering $k_h = 0.10$ and a frequency of 0.80 Hz that is close to the fundamental frequency of this deposit ($= 0.84$ Hz) while assuming the constant damping ratio of 7%. With the help of these, the horizontal acceleration time

history acting at the base of the domain was obtained. The total duration of the seismic acceleration was 50 seconds, matching the Type B earthquake motion given by Jennings et al. (1968). Considering a rigid half-space below the site, this waveform was given as the base excitation to the soil profile in DEEPSOIL. The site response analysis was run to obtain $a_h(z, t)/g$ at the ground surface ($z = 0$) as shown in Fig. 7.6(b) and at the mid-depth ($z = H/2$) as shown in Fig. 7.6(c). These quantities were compared with those obtained from the present study. Out of the entire 50 seconds duration of the earthquake motion, the first 15 seconds is shown in figures 7.6(b) and (c), and similar variations were observed till the 50th second. The horizontal accelerations from the current study and DEEPSOIL compare well with each other, albeit with some differences in their magnitude. This anomaly could be attributed to the approximation of the actual shear wave velocity profile by a general power law. Nevertheless, these differences are impractical, and the advantages offered by considering the analytical formulation in the present study outweigh the accuracy of using the actual wave velocity profile. Figures 7.6(b) and (c) validate the analytical formulation derived in this study considering the temporal variation in seismic acceleration.

7.4.3.2 Seismic response in the space domain

Fig. 7.6(d) compares the seismic response in the space domain using the absolute maximum value of the horizontal acceleration, $|a_h(z, t)/g|_{\max}$, at any time computed at various depths from the present study with that from DEEPSOIL. The present research slightly overestimates the maximum acceleration, especially at the ground surface, which may be due to the differences in the manner of wave velocity considerations. Nonetheless, the maximum difference in the magnitudes of $|a_h(z, t)/g|_{\max}$ in Fig. 7.6(d) is only about 12.62%.

Finally, from figures 7.4, 7.5, and 7.6, a continuous power-law of the present study can be used to fit the discrete field data to reasonably estimate the seismic response of a site in frequency, time and space domains.

7.5 Results and Discussion

The support pressure, σ_s , has been presented in the non-dimensional form by normalizing σ_s with the unit weight γ , and the tunnel diameter, D , represented as $\sigma_s/\gamma D$. Table 7.1 lists the parameters and their ranges used for the present study.

TABLE 7.1: Parameters and their ranges used.

Parameter	Notation	Range
Cover depth-to-tunnel diameter	C/D	1, 3
Soil friction angle	ϕ	30° to 45°
Horizontal acceleration coefficient	k_h	0, 0.1, 0.2
Vertical acceleration coefficient	k_v	$k_h/2$
Wave velocity ratio (ground surface/base)	V_0/V_H	0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8
Power parameter	n	0.01, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6
Damping ratio	ξ	7%

The ratio of the primary wave velocity to the shear wave velocity considering their heterogeneity is given as

$$\frac{V_p(z)}{V_s(z)} = \frac{V_{pH} \left[b_p + q_p \frac{z}{H} \right]^{n_p}}{V_{sH} \left[b_s + q_s \frac{z}{H} \right]^{n_s}} \quad (7.28)$$

In the present study, for simplicity, $n_s = n_p = n$ and $b_s = b_p$ (or $V_{s0}/V_{sH} = V_{p0}/V_{pH} = V_0/V_H$). Under these assumptions, $q_i = 1 - b_i$ ($i = s, p$) will be the same for shear and primary waves. Therefore, Eq. 7.28 simplifies to $V_p(z)/V_s(z) = V_{pH}/V_{sH}$, for a given z/H . Assuming a constant Poisson's ratio of 0.3 (Kramer, 2007), for any z/H , $V_p(z)$ is 1.87 times $V_s(z)$. In other words, $V_{pH}/V_{sH} = 1.87$ was used throughout the study.

Based on the parameters mentioned above, the effect of dimensionless frequency and time on the normalized support pressure is initially assessed. Following this, a thorough parametric study is performed to analyze the influence of inhomogeneity parameters (V_0/V_H and n), horizontal acceleration coefficient (k_h), tunnel cover depth-to-diameter ratio (C/D), and soil friction angle (ϕ). The influence of wave velocity heterogeneity on the collapse patterns and soil arching have been studied.

7.5.1 Discussion on amplification ratios

Fig. 7.7 depicts the variation of the amplification factors for horizontal and vertical accelerations, \mathcal{F}_h and \mathcal{F}_v , respectively, with dimensionless frequencies, $\omega_s H/V_{sH}$ and $\omega_p H/V_{pH}$, for different V_0/V_H and n values. The amplification factor is a function of the dimensionless frequency of the seismic wave, damping ratio, and the heterogeneity parameters (V_0/V_H and n). For a damped soil with uniform wave velocity over a rigid bedrock, represented in this study by $n = 0.01$, the fundamental frequency for the shear wave is at $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = \pi/2$ (Kramer, 2007). On the other hand, for the primary wave, the fundamental frequency is $\omega_p H/V_{pH} = \pi/2$. Using, $\omega_p/\omega_s = 1$ and $V_{pH}/V_{sH} = 1.87$, the value of $\omega_s H/V_{sH}$ corresponding to the fundamental frequency of the primary wave is $= (0.5\pi \times 1.87)/1 \approx 0.94\pi$. For a heterogeneous wave velocity profile with a given V_0/V_H , as the value of n increases, the natural frequencies are shifted to frequencies lower than that of a uniform velocity profile. Furthermore, from Fig. 7.7, the shift of the natural frequencies with n also depends on the wave velocity ratio V_0/V_H . The effect of n on the wave velocity profile reduces with an increase in V_0/V_H , and it is reflected in the magnitudes of the natural frequencies of shear and primary waves. Moreover, the magnitudes of \mathcal{F}_h and \mathcal{F}_v increases with increase in n at any V_0/V_H value. Like the shift in the natural frequencies, for any value of n , the increment in the amplification ratio's magnitude diminishes for a higher V_0/V_H .

FIGURE 7.7: Horizontal and vertical amplification ratios for various inhomogeneity parameters.

Here, $\mathcal{S}_s^{V_0/V_H}$ represents the set of all shear wave fundamental frequencies for a given V_0/V_H . Similarly, $\mathcal{S}_p^{V_0/V_H}$ represents the primary wave's fundamental frequency set. The width of shaded regions in Fig. 7.7 represents the corresponding set's range, $r(\cdot)$. For $V_0/V_H = 0.2$ and n values used here, from Fig. 7.7(a), $\mathcal{S}_s^{0.2} = \{0.5\pi, 0.46\pi, 0.41\pi, 0.38\pi\}$ with $\omega_s H / V_{sH} = 0.5\pi$ for $n = 0.01$ and 0.38π for $n = 0.6$. Similarly, $\mathcal{S}_p^{0.2} = \{0.5\pi, 0.46\pi, 0.41\pi, 0.38\pi\}$ with $\omega_p H / V_{pH} = 0.5\pi$ and 0.38π for $n = 0.01$ and 0.6 , respectively. Thus, the range $r(\mathcal{S}_s^{0.2}) = r(\mathcal{S}_p^{0.2}) = 0.12\pi$. On the contrary, from Fig. 7.7(b), for $V_0/V_H = 0.8$, $\mathcal{S}_s^{0.8} = \mathcal{S}_p^{0.8} = \{0.5\pi, 0.48\pi, 0.47\pi, 0.47\pi\}$ with $r(\mathcal{S}_s^{0.8}) = r(\mathcal{S}_p^{0.8}) = 0.03\pi$. Therefore, as V_0/V_H increases, the distribution of the fundamental frequencies with n reduces, indicating a lower influence of the power parameter in seismic accelerations.

7.5.2 Effect of dimensionless frequency and time on support pressure

Figures 7.8, 7.9, and 7.10 explore the influence of dimensionless frequency ($\omega_s H/V_{sH}$) and time (t/T) on the normalized support pressure. The impact of the inhomogeneous parameters (V_0/V_H and n), soil friction angle (ϕ), and tunnel cover depth-to-diameter ratio (C/D) are analyzed. Furthermore, in figures 7.8, 7.9, and 7.10, the amplification ratios (\mathcal{F}_h and \mathcal{F}_v) are also plotted alongside the variation of maximum support pressure with frequency ($\max \sigma_s/\gamma D$ wrt t/T). In these figures, $k_h = 0.1$, $k_v = k_h/2$, and $\xi = 7\%$ are considered. Here, RI represents the Region of Infeasibility where the results were infeasible due to dynamic shear fluidization of sands (Richards et al., 1990).

Fig. 7.8 highlights the impact of V_0/V_H and n using $C/D = 1$ and $\phi = 30^\circ$. Here, the absolute maximum support pressure occurs around the shear wave's fundamental frequency of the respective heterogeneity condition. Thus, for the input parameters considered in Fig. 7.8, it can be said that the shear wave dominates the seismic response. As the level of inhomogeneity increases, i.e., as n increases for a fixed V_0/V_H , the fundamental frequency of shear and primary waves reduces, and this reduction is more noticeable for a lower V_0/V_H value (Rovithis et al., 2011). It is evident from Fig. 7.8 that the magnitude of $\omega_s H/V_{sH}$ at which the absolute maximum support pressure occurs reduces with n . This shift in the critical frequency is noticeable in figures 7.8(a) and (b) (for $V_0/V_H = 0.2$) than figures 7.8(c) and (d) (for $V_0/V_H = 0.8$). Unlike the support pressure for single tunnels in granular soils with homogeneous wave velocities, local peaks of support pressure are noticeable in the subsequent natural frequencies of shear and primary waves. This enunciates the strong influence of wave velocity's heterogeneity on the support pressure of tunnels.

FIGURE 7.8: Influence of V_0/V_H and n on support pressure variations in the dimensionless frequency-time space.

Fig. 7.9 investigates the effect of soil friction angle for $C/D = 1$ and $V_0/V_H = 0.2$. It is evident that the support pressure's trend for tunnels at a shallow cover depth is dominated by the shear waves than the primary waves. For any n and ϕ value, the absolute maximum support pressure occurs near the shear wave's fundamental frequency. However, it is interesting to notice that the impact of the primary waves in figures 7.9(c) and (d), for $\phi = 45^\circ$, have increased compared to $\phi = 30^\circ$. For example, considering $\phi = 30^\circ$ and $n = 0.6$

(Fig. 7.9(b)), the magnitude of support pressure (maximum for any t/T) near the P-wave fundamental frequency is about 0.63 times that near the S-wave's fundamental frequency. On the other hand, from Fig. 7.9(d), for $\phi = 45^\circ$ and $n = 0.6$, $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ corresponding to P-wave fundamental frequency is about 0.92 times $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ for the S-wave fundamental frequency.

FIGURE 7.9: For $C/D = 1$, the influence of the soil friction angle (ϕ) on support pressure variations in the dimensionless frequency-time space.

FIGURE 7.10: For $C/D = 3$, the influence of the soil friction angle (ϕ) on support pressure variations in the dimensionless frequency-time space.

Fig. 7.10 shows that primary waves have a stronger influence on the support pressure for tunnels placed at a higher cover depth. This influence is found to be unaffected by the value of soil friction angle. The aforementioned effect of P-waves is different from that observed for homogeneous wave velocity conditions, and it enunciates the necessity for including the primary wave propagation in the analysis. From figures 7.8, 7.9, and 7.10, it could be observed that S-waves predominantly influence the support pressure at lower

cover depth-to-diameter ratio (C/D), whereas the influence of P-waves is predominant at higher C/D values.

The representative values of t/T and $\omega_s H/V_{sH}$ are required for the parametric study, and the values of frequency and time corresponding to the maximum support pressure in figures 7.8, 7.9, and 7.10 cannot be considered as they lie around fundamental frequencies and critical t/T values. Fig. 7.11 highlights the effect of wave velocity inhomogeneity on the variation of normalized horizontal, $a_h(0, t)/g$, and vertical, $a_v(0, t)/g$, accelerations at the ground surface, $z/H = 0$, with non-dimensional time, t/T , and S-wave frequency, $\omega_s H/V_{sH}$. It is evident that seismic accelerations on the ground surface reach their peak magnitude near the fundamental frequency. Furthermore, maximum magnitude of $a_h(0, t)/g$ and $a_v(z, t)/g$ occurs near $t/T = 0.25$ and 0.75 . On the other hand, equations 7.19 and 7.26 reveal that the base accelerations reach near-zero values around $t/T = 0.25$ and 0.75 . An exorbitant ground acceleration accompanied by a negligible base acceleration indicate "resonance" and cannot be used. However, from equations 7.19 and 7.26, the base acceleration is maximum at $\pm k_{h,v}$ for $t/T = 0, 0.5$, and 1 . For the reasons mentioned above, the normalized support pressure, $\sigma_s/\gamma D$, is varied with dimensionless frequencies, $\omega_s H/V_{sH}$ and $\omega_p H/V_{pH}$, using $t/T = 0.5$, as shown in Fig. 7.12. Here, $C/D = 1$, $\phi = 30^\circ$, and $k_h = 0.2$ have been used. From Fig. 7.12, using $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.3\pi$ and 0.6π for the parametric study would be appropriate as they bracket the fundamental frequencies of S-waves and provide feasible solutions.

FIGURE 7.11: Variation of horizontal and vertical accelerations on the ground surface with dimensionless time and frequency for various inhomogeneous parameters.

FIGURE 7.12: Variation of the dimensionless support pressure, $\sigma_s/\gamma D$, with non-dimensional frequencies using $t/T = 0.5$.

7.5.3 Discussion of resultant acceleration fields

From the above discussion, $t/T = 0.5$, $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.3\pi$ and 0.6π are the representative values of dimensionless time and S-wave frequency that will be used for the parametric study. Before discussing the results from the parametric study, it is important to understand the variation of seismic accelerations in the soil domain for different values of wave velocity inhomogeneity. Plots of the resultant acceleration's magnitude, $a_r(z, t)/g$, and direction, ϑ , serve the purpose of a succinct representation seismic acceleration in the domain. The magnitude $a_r(z, t)/g$, and direction, ϑ , of the resultant acceleration are given by equations 4.16 and 4.17, respectively, from Chapter 4, which are found by using the

theory of vector algebra on horizontal and vertical seismic accelerations. Figures 7.13 and 7.14 represent the resultant acceleration fields for $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.3\pi$ and 0.6π , respectively. For representational purposes, $C/D = 1$ and $k_h = 0.1$ have been used. The effect of heterogeneous parameters, V_0/V_H and n , have also been considered.

In Fig. 7.13, for a given V_0/V_H , the resultant acceleration's magnitude increases with n , which is noticeable for $V_0/V_H = 0.2$ (figures 7.13(b) and (c)) than $V_0/V_H = 0.8$ (figures 7.13(d) and (e)). Similarly, the change of $\vartheta(z, t)$ with n is prominent for a lower V_0/V_H . Furthermore, in Fig. 7.13, the direction of the resultant acceleration does not change with depth. The values of t/T and $\omega_s H/V_{sH}$ used here will provide an insight to the above. From equations 7.19 and 7.26, the base acceleration's magnitude is at its maximum at $t/T = 0.5$ and its acceleration is negative. Based on the sign conventions of the present study (refer to Fig. 7.13), the base horizontal acceleration will have a magnitude of $-k_h$ and on the left-hand side of the tunnel center. Similarly, base vertical acceleration with a magnitude of $-k_v$ acts along the downward direction. In Fig. 7.13, $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.3\pi$ is used which is less than the fundamental frequency for any V_0/V_H and n . Therefore, seismic accelerations are in-phase throughout the depth, i.e., seismic acceleration's direction is *preserved* from the base to ground surface. It is also interesting to note that the direction of the resultant acceleration becomes increasingly horizontal, that is, the value of ϑ reduces, as n increases, which is evident for a lower V_0/V_H (figures 7.13(b) and (c)). Referring to Fig. 7.7(a), for $V_0/V_H = 0.2$, the dimensionless frequency of $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.3\pi$ is closer to the S-wave's fundamental frequency when $n = 0.6$ than $n = 0.2$. Therefore, the resultant acceleration's direction in Fig. 7.13(c) is closer to the horizontal axis (lower value of ϑ) than Fig. 7.13(b).

FIGURE 7.13: Resultant acceleration field for $\omega_s H / V_{sH} = 0.3\pi$.

On the other hand, Fig. 7.14 illustrates the resultant acceleration field using $\omega_s H / V_{sH} = 0.6\pi$ for different V_0/V_H and n values. Here, unlike Fig. 7.13, the resultant acceleration's direction changes with depth. For any value of V_0/V_H and n used in this study, the dimensionless frequency of $\omega_s H / V_{sH} = 0.6\pi$ is higher than the shear wave's fundamental frequency. Therefore, the direction of seismic horizontal acceleration changes as the shear wave travels from the base to the ground surface. Contrary to the above, $\omega_s H / V_{sH} = 0.6\pi$ is less than the fundamental frequency of primary waves for any V_0/V_H and n . Hence, the direction of vertical acceleration is *preserved* from base to the ground surface, i.e., it acts downwards. Fig. 7.14 shows the level of inflection beyond which the horizontal acceleration's direction changes. For example, for $n = 0.01$, Fig. 7.14(a) shows that the horizontal acceleration's direction reverses at a depth of $4D$ from the ground surface. At

this level, the horizontal acceleration's magnitude is near-zero, and a tangent drawn at any point on this level will be vertical and directed downwards. Fig. 7.14 says that the horizontal acceleration's inflection level moves closer to the ground surface as the selected frequency moves far away from the S-wave's fundamental frequency. Comparing figures 7.14(b) and (c), the resultant acceleration tends to be more "vertical" for $n = 0.6$ than $n = 0.2$. From Fig. 7.7(a), $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.6\pi$ is far from the S-wave fundamental frequency but closer to the primary wave's fundamental frequency, increasing the vertical acceleration's influence on the resultant acceleration field.

FIGURE 7.14: Resultant acceleration field for $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.6\pi$.

7.5.4 Parametric study

The present section discusses the results of a parametric study conducted to examine the variation of normalized support pressure, $\sigma_s/\gamma D$, with input parameters using $t/T = 0.5$, and $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.3\pi$ and 0.6π . Figures 7.15 and 7.16 illustrate the variation of $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ for $C/D = 1$ using $k_h = 0.1$ and 0.2 , respectively. Similarly, figures 7.17 and 7.18 have been generated for $C/D = 3$ with $k_h = 0.1$ and 0.2 , respectively. The influence of each parameter - soil friction angle, horizontal acceleration coefficient, dimensionless shear wave frequency, and heterogeneous parameters are discussed below.

Effect of friction angle, ϕ : In general, the support pressure decreases with soil friction angle due to an increasing shear strength. The change of support pressure to the change in soil friction angle, within the horizon of wave velocity inhomogeneity, is examined in Fig. 7.19 using the absolute percentage difference in support pressure, $\Delta_\phi(\sigma_s)$. Here, the sensitivity of support pressure for ϕ varied between 30° and 45° has been considered. It can be seen from Fig. 7.19 that the change in support pressure due to friction angle changes is not uniform. Largely, the support pressure is sensitive to friction angle changes when the wave velocity ratio (V_0/V_H) is low and power parameter (n) is high. In other words, the higher the degree of wave velocity heterogeneity, the higher is the influence of friction angle. Similarly, the effect of friction angle on $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ is more prominent for $k_h = 0.2$ than $k_h = 0.1$ for obvious reasons. The magnitude of $\Delta_\phi(\sigma_s)$ in Fig. 7.19 is dependent on the dimensionless frequency of shear waves. For $V_0/V_H = 0.2$, the value of $\Delta_\phi(\sigma_s)$ decreases for $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.3\pi$ to 0.6π . On the other hand, the relative difference increases with the non-dimensional frequency for $V_0/V_H = 0.8$. The proximity of selected frequencies to the corresponding fundamental frequency answers the above trend.

FIGURE 7.16: For $C/D = 1$ and $k_h = 0.2$, the variation of $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ with ϕ , V_0/V_H and n for (a-d) $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.3\pi$, and (e-h) $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.6\pi$.

FIGURE 7.17: Effect of ϕ , V_0/V_H and n on σ_s/γ_D for $C/D = 3$, $k_h = 0.1$ with (a-d) $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.3\pi$ and (e-h) $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.6\pi$.

FIGURE 7.18: Effect of ϕ , V_0/V_H and n on $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ for $C/D = 3$, $k_h = 0.2$ with (a-d) $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.3\pi$ and (e-g) $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.6\pi$.

For example, $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.3\pi$ is closer to the fundamental frequency of shear waves than 0.6π for $V_0/V_H = 0.2$ and $n = 0.6$, hence, $\Delta_\phi(\sigma_s)$ is lower for the later frequency (0.6π). On the other hand, for $V_0/V_H = 0.8$ and for all n values, $\omega_s H/V_s = 0.6\pi$ is closer to S-wave fundamental frequency than 0.3π . Hence, $\Delta_\phi(\sigma_s)$ increases with the selected dimensionless frequency for $V_0/V_H = 0.8$. It is also interesting to note from Fig. 7.19 that support pressure for tunnels placed at a larger cover depth is more sensitive to friction angle changes than shallower ones. This is because of an increased influence of soil arching over tunnels in soils with higher friction angles. Similarly, the effect of other parameters, V_0/V_H , n , and $\omega_s H/V_{sH}$, pertaining to the support pressure changes with friction angle, is negligible for $C/D = 3$.

FIGURE 7.19: Effect of ϕ : Absolute percentage difference in support pressure, $\Delta_\phi(\sigma_s)$, between $\phi = 30^\circ$ and 45° .

Effect of wave velocity ratio, V_0/V_H : Fig. 7.20 shows the influence of wave velocity ratio, V_0/V_H , over the normalized support pressure. Here, $\Delta_{V_0/V_H}(\sigma_s)$ represents the absolute difference in support pressure due to the change in V_0/V_H between 0.2 and 0.8. It has been observed from the parametric study that the support pressure reduces with the wave velocity ratio, V_0/V_H .

FIGURE 7.20: Effect of wave velocity ratio, V_0/V_H : Absolute percentage difference in support pressure, $\Delta_{V_0/V_H}(\sigma_s)$, between $V_0/V_H = 0.2$ and 0.8.

From Fig. 7.20, the support pressure is highly sensitive to V_0/V_H for a higher value of the power parameter, n . The above-mentioned observation is prominent for $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.3\pi$. Similarly, Fig. 7.20 reveals that the influence of V_0/V_H is higher for tunnels with a lower cover depth-to-diameter ratio. Fig. 7.7 shows the influence of the power parameter, n , in horizontal and vertical amplification ratios. This has been re-plotted in Fig. 7.21 to

highlight the influence of V_0/V_H for $n = 0.2$ and 0.6 , which will be useful to envision the sensitivity of support pressure to changes in V_0/V_H .

From Fig. 7.21, for any $\omega_s H/V_{sH}$ value, the variation of horizontal and vertical amplification ratios with V_0/V_H is negligible for $n = 0.2$ than $n = 0.6$. Therefore, the support pressure is highly sensitive to V_0/V_H for a higher value of n . Comparing the results of $\Delta_{V_0/V_H}(\sigma_s)$ between $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.3\pi$ and 0.6π , it can be seen from Fig. 7.20 that the change in support pressure is higher for the later frequency when n value is low, and the opposite is true for $n = 0.6$. This is because $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.6\pi$ is closer to shear wave's fundamental frequency for $n = 0.2$ and any V_0/V_H (refer to Fig. 7.21(a)). Contrary to the above, referring to Fig. 7.21(b), for $n = 0.6$, the dimensionless S-wave frequency of 0.3π is closer to respective fundamental frequency, especially for a lower V_0/V_H value. Nevertheless, the considerable effect of n in Fig. 7.20(b) is due to the rise of vertical amplification ratio at $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.6\pi$, which enunciates the importance of incorporating both shear and primary wave propagation into the analysis.

FIGURE 7.21: Horizontal and vertical amplification ratios, highlighting the effect of V_0/V_H , for (a) $n = 0.2$, and (b) $n = 0.6$.

Effect of power parameter, n : The influence of power parameter, n , in altering the support pressure is explored in Fig. 7.22. Here, $\Delta_n(\sigma_s)$ represents the absolute difference in support pressure for n varied between 0.2 and 0.6. In general, the support pressure increases with the power parameter because of an increase in the level of wave velocity inhomogeneity with n . However, this is not uniform for other problem parameters.

FIGURE 7.22: Effect of power parameter, n : Absolute percentage difference in support pressure, $\Delta_n(\sigma_s)$, between $n = 0.2$ and 0.6 .

Fig. 7.22 indicates that, largely, the support pressure differs substantially with n for a lower V_0/V_H value. The reason lies in the significant change in horizontal and vertical amplification ratios with the power parameter for $V_0/V_H = 0.2$ (refer to Fig. 7.7(a)). At a higher V_0/V_H value, the effect of n on the wave velocity inhomogeneity and seismic acceleration decreases, which reflects in the support pressure being less sensitive to n , for

$V_0/V_H = 0.8$, in Fig. 7.22. For a low V_0/V_H value, Fig. 7.22 shows that the support pressure is significantly affected by power parameter for $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.3\pi$. This is because the aforementioned frequency is closer to the respective shear wave's fundamental frequency than $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.6\pi$. Contrary to this, $\Delta_n(\sigma_s)$ is higher for $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.6\pi$ with $V_0/V_H = 0.8$. The amplification ratio in Fig. 7.7(d) says that, for $V_0/V_H = 0.8$, the shear wave's fundamental frequency is approximately $\pi/2$ for any n value. Since $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.6\pi$ is closer to $\pi/2$ than 0.3π , support pressures show a heightened sensitivity to n at the dimensionless frequency of 0.6π for $V_0/V_H = 0.8$.

Effect of horizontal acceleration coefficient, k_h : For $t/T = 0.5$, the base horizontal acceleration is given as $a_h(H, t) = -k_h g$. Thus, an increase in the horizontal acceleration coefficient, k_h , increases the base horizontal acceleration. Moreover, in the present study, the vertical acceleration coefficient, k_v , is also a function of k_h . Hence, an increase in k_h increases both horizontal and vertical seismic acceleration throughout the domain, which increases the support pressure. The change of $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ with k_h is assessed in Fig. 7.23 using the absolute difference of support pressure, $\Delta_{k_h}(\sigma_s)$, for $k_h = 0.1$ and 0.2 . In essence, for any value $\omega_s H/V_{sH}$, the support pressure shows excessive changes to k_h for tunnels with a lower cover depth in soils with a lower friction angle and higher level of wave velocity heterogeneity (low V_0/V_H and high n). From Fig. 7.7, for $V_0/V_H = 0.2$, the shear wave's fundamental frequency goes close to $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.3\pi$ with n . Therefore, the influence of k_h on the support pressure surges with n for a lower wave velocity ratio at $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.3\pi$ (refer to figures 7.23(a) and (c)). Contrary to the above, at $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.6\pi$, the shear wave's fundamental frequency moves away and that of primary wave comes closer to this frequency. The above-said is evident from Fig. 7.7 for a lower V_0/V_H .

FIGURE 7.23: Effect of horizontal acceleration coefficient, k_h : Absolute percentage difference in support pressure, $\Delta_{k_h}(\sigma_s)$, between $k_h = 0.1$ and 0.2 .

Hence, the support pressure shows a substantial change to k_h for a lower wave velocity ratio and higher power parameter due to the combined effect of horizontal and vertical seismic accelerations. For the heterogeneous parameters mentioned above, the value of $\Delta_{k_h}(\sigma_s)$ drops with the selected dimensionless frequency (0.3π to 0.6π). This is due to an out of phase nature of horizontal seismic accelerations at $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.6\pi$ (refer to Fig. 7.14). Nevertheless, the vertical seismic acceleration is still in phase, which has a significant contribution to support pressure's sensitivity. From Fig. 7.23, the above-said trend of $\Delta_{k_h}(\sigma_s)$ with $\omega_s H/V_{sH}$ reverses for a higher wave velocity ratio, i.e., for $V_0/V_H = 0.8$, the support pressure is more sensitive to changes in k_h for $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.6\pi$ than

0.3π . This is again answered using Fig. 7.7 that the proximity of dimensionless shear wave frequency of 0.6π to the corresponding fundamental frequency.

7.5.5 Collapse patterns

Figures 7.24, 7.25, and 7.26 illustrate the pattern of soil collapse around tunnels under homogeneous and heterogeneous wave velocity conditions. These have been obtained using the velocity vectors and indicate the plausible direction of soil movement around the tunnel at its ultimate collapse. Analyzing the collapse patterns helps to visualize the extent of soil yield around tunnels due to seismicity. For the current discussion, $k_h = 0.1$ and $t/T = 0.5$ have been used. Fig. 7.24 show the pattern of collapse for near-homogeneous wave velocity profile, $n = 0.01$, using $C/D = 1$ and $\phi = 30^\circ$. The effect of the selected dimensionless frequency of the S-waves, $\omega_s H/V_{sH}$, is highlighted.

FIGURE 7.24: Collapse patterns for homogeneous wave velocities emphasizing the influence of the dimensionless frequency.

The resultant acceleration fields in Fig. 7.13(a) for $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.3\pi$ indicate that the horizontal acceleration is directed along the left-hand side of the tunnel center. Therefore the collapse pattern in Fig. 7.24(a) is also skewed towards the negative X direction. Contrastingly, Fig. 7.24(b) says that, for $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.6\pi$, a larger extent of the soil lying on the right-hand side of the tunnel center takes part in the collapse. The resultant acceleration field in Fig. 7.14(a) depict that about 80% of the soil domain is accelerated

towards the positive X-direction, resulting in the right-handedness of the collapse pattern in Fig. 7.24(b). Another interesting thing to note is that the overall extent of the collapse pattern increases in Fig. 7.24(b) compared to Fig. 7.24(a). This is because, for $n = 0.01$, Fig. 7.7 shows that, among 0.3π and 0.6π , $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.6\pi$ is closer to the shear wave's fundamental frequency (0.5π). Fig. 7.24 shows a region near the ground surface where the velocity vectors are directed outwards of the soil domain. This region exists when the selected frequency is in the vicinity of the fundamental frequency of shear waves and the magnitude of the horizontal acceleration is higher near the ground surface. Furthermore, the extent of this region increases when the selected frequency is closer to the S-wave's fundamental frequency.

FIGURE 7.25: For $C/D = 1$, collapse patterns highlighting the effect of inhomogeneity parameters V_0/V_H and n .

Fig. 7.25 has been plotted to depict the influence of the heterogeneity parameters V_0/V_H and n on the collapse pattern considering $C/D = 1$ and $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.3\pi$. As said earlier, the entire domain is accelerated in the negative X direction under $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.3\pi$. Therefore, collapse patterns in Fig. 7.25 are skewed along the left-hand side of

the tunnel center. Furthermore, the soil region participating at ultimate collapse increases with n , and this is noticeable for a lower V_0/V_H , as in figures 7.25(a) and (b). It should be noted that the S-wave fundamental frequency for $V_0/V_H = 0.2$ and $n = 0.6$, i.e., $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.38\pi$, is the closest to the selected frequency of 0.3π in Fig. 7.25. Hence, compared to others, the collapse pattern's extent is the highest in Fig. 7.25(b). For a higher V_0/V_H , the influence of the power parameter is negligible; hence, the change in the collapse pattern's extent is also negligible in figures 7.25(c) and (d). Here, too, a small region of soil near the ground surface tends to move out of the domain at ultimate collapse for the reasons mentioned before, and its extent increases with the proximity of the selected frequency and S-wave's fundamental frequency.

Comparing figures 7.25(b) and 7.26(a), the extent of the collapse pattern increases with the tunnel cover depth-to-diameter ratio, C/D . Even though the extent of outward region near the ground surface increases with C/D , the insets show that the length of the velocity vectors in this region has significantly reduced. This is because, a higher magnitude of seismic horizontal acceleration for the case of $V_0/V_H = 0.2$, $n = 0.6$, and $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.6\pi$, do not influence the soil collapse for tunnels placed at a higher cover depth. In other words, the seismic stability of tunnels at a shallower cover depth is critical than a deeper one. For $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.6\pi$, Fig. 7.26(b) indicate that the change in the horizontal acceleration's direction caused the reversal of the collapse pattern's skewness. The extent of collapse has reduced and the outward moving region near the ground surface has vanished in Fig. 7.26(b). This is because of the fact that the selected dimensionless frequency of 0.6π is far from the corresponding shear wave's fundamental frequency (0.38π). From figures 7.26(b) and (c), for tunnels placed at a higher cover depth in soils with high friction angle values, the collapse pattern loses its contact with the ground surface, and the soil collapse is confined around the tunnel periphery.

FIGURE 7.26: Effect of the tunnel cover depth, soil friction angle and dimensionless frequency on the soil collapse pattern.

7.5.6 Horizontal and vertical stress contours

Figures 7.27 and 7.28 show the distribution of normalized horizontal, $\sigma_x/\gamma D$, and vertical, $\sigma_z/\gamma D$, stress contours over the domain highlighting the influence of heterogeneity parameters V_0/V_H and n , tunnel cover depth-to-diameter ratio, C/D , and the selected dimensionless frequency, $\omega_s H / V_{sH}$. The vertical stress contours in figures 7.27 and 7.28 indicate the occurrence of soil arching around the tunnel periphery owing to the transfer of vertical stresses from the yielding to non-yielding region. In these figures, the yielding region's boundary is marked by dashed lines obtained from the corresponding collapse pattern. Moreover, the stress distribution is skewed respective to the horizontal acceleration's direction.

FIGURE 7.27: Dimensionless horizontal and vertical stress contours highlighting the effect of wave velocity's inhomogeneity parameters.

From Fig. 7.27, it is evident that the magnitude of stress in the non-yielding region around the tunnel increases with n . The above effect is evident for a lower V_0/V_H value, as in figures 7.27(a) and (b). Comparing figures 7.27(b) and 7.28(a), as the tunnel cover depth increases, the influence of soil arching in the transfer of stresses increases. In other words, the magnitude of stresses in the non-yielding portion increases with C/D , which

reduces the stress magnitude in the immediate vicinity of the tunnel periphery. Thus, the tunnel stability is improved.

As the value of the dimensionless frequency crosses the fundamental frequency, the direction of horizontal acceleration changes, which reverses the skew of the soil arch (refer to Fig. 7.28(b)). From figures 7.28(a) and (b), for $V_0/V_H = 0.2$ and $n = 0.6$, albeit negligible in magnitudes, the maximum magnitude of the horizontal stress decreases and the vertical stress increases with an increase in $\omega_s H/V_{sH}$ from 0.3π to 0.6π . A justification to the above trend is that, for $V_0/V_H = 0.2$ and $n = 0.6$, $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.6\pi$ is closer to the fundamental frequency of the primary wave (0.71π) than the shear wave (0.38π). Hence, compared to Fig. 7.28(a), the maximum magnitude of $\sigma_x/\gamma D$ has decreased and $\sigma_z/\gamma D$ has increased in Fig. 7.28(b).

Figures 7.28(b) and (c) enunciate the effect of the soil friction angle in the stress distribution under the seismic loading. The stress concentration occurring in the adjoining non-yielding portion is prominent in Fig. 7.28(c) because the influence of soil arching is stronger in granular soils with a high friction angle. In essence, for tunnels in granular soils of high friction angles placed at a larger cover depth is more stable as the stress magnitudes in the vicinity of the tunnel reduces due to a stronger soil arching effect.

7.5.7 Normal stress distribution

Computing the normal stress, σ_n , on all the tunnel nodes, the normal stress is expressed in dimensionless form as $\sigma_n/\gamma D$. The distribution has been represented as polar plots with $\sigma_n/\gamma D$ against the angles made by the radial lines from the tunnel center to the nodes on its periphery with respect to the horizontal. Using $C/D = 3$, $\phi = 30^\circ$ and $t/T = 0.5$, the distribution of $\sigma_n/\gamma D$ has been obtained for various values of wave velocity heterogeneity and seismic parameters, as shown in Fig. 7.29. The normal stresses show a meager change

FIGURE 7.28: For $C/D = 3$, horizontal and vertical stress contours emphasizing the influence of frequency and soil friction angle.

with n , at $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.3\pi$, in Fig. 7.29(a) owing to a lower value of k_h . Fig. 7.29(b) suggests that $\sigma_n/\gamma D$ increases with n for a comparatively higher k_h value. Comparing figures 7.29(b) and 7.29(c), at $V_0/V_H = 0.8$, the normal stress distribution is not affected with n . Furthermore, figures 7.29(a-c) have been plotted using $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.3\pi$. The implication of this is that the maximum normal stress in all the cases is located on the left-hand side of the tunnel center, which happens to be the predominant direction of the horizontal acceleration at $t/T = 0.5$, i.e., the negative X direction (refer to Fig. 7.13). Fig. 7.29(d) shows the $\sigma_n/\gamma D$ distribution using $V_0/V_H = 0.2$, $k_h = 0.2$, and $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.6\pi$, apart from parameters mentioned above.

FIGURE 7.29: Normal stress distribution for tunnels in heterogeneous wave velocity media.

Compared to Fig. 7.29(b), the magnitudes of $\sigma_n/\gamma D$ in Fig. 7.29(d) are less because of the out-of-phase nature of the horizontal acceleration at the non-dimensional frequency of 0.6π . Moreover, Fig. 7.29(d) reveals that for lower n value the maximum normal stress is clearly on the right-hand side of the tunnel center. Whereas, as n rises to 0.6, the distribution is almost symmetric. The degree of skew in the normal stress distribution is dependent on the horizontal acceleration's magnitude. From figures 7.14(b) and (c), the

direction of resultant acceleration tends to be more vertical as n increases, indicating a decreased influence of the horizontal acceleration. Therefore, the normal stress distribution for $V_0/V_H = 0.2$ and $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.6\pi$ in Fig. 7.29(d) tends to be symmetric as n increases. Nonetheless, the maximum normal stress in Fig. 7.29(d) increased with n due to the combined effect of shear and primary waves.

7.6 Summary

In this chapter, the solution to governing differential equations of seismic body waves propagation in a medium with heterogeneous wave velocities have been derived. The continuously varying shear and primary wave velocities were modeled using a generalized power law function. Unlike the previous studies, the analytical expressions for the horizontal and vertical accelerations varying in both space and time were derived by satisfying the boundary conditions on the ground surface and the base. These analytical expressions were then used to ascertain the seismic stability of a circular tunnel placed in granular soils with continuously varying shear and primary wave velocities given by the generalized power law. The lower bound theorem of limit analysis in combination with the finite elements was used to obtain the distribution of stresses around the tunnel periphery. The maximum normal stress on the tunnel periphery, termed as support pressure of the tunnel and was expressed non-dimensionally as $\sigma_s/\gamma D$. The influence of tunnel cover depth-to-diameter ratio (C/D), soil friction angle (ϕ), seismic acceleration coefficients (k_h and k_v), heterogeneity parameters (V_0/V_H and n), non-dimensional frequencies of shear and primary waves at the base ($\omega_s H/V_{sH}$ and $\omega_s H/V_{pH}$), and the dimensionless period of shaking (t/T) on $\sigma_s/\gamma D$ was studied.

8

Conclusions

8.1 General

The present thesis investigated the seismic stability of circular tunnels placed in different ground conditions under spatiotemporal horizontal and vertical seismic accelerations considered to be generated due to the harmonic base shaking. The stability analysis has been performed using the finite element limit analysis, the lower bound approach, and the second-order cone programming. Many studies have reported the amplification caused due to seismic waves in the presence of tunnels, deformation of the ground surface due to tunnels, and forces and displacements of the tunnel lining, which were evaluated assuming the structural parameters of the lining. It is required to analyze the soil medium to know the stress magnitude transferred by surrounding soil onto the tunnel periphery, which aids in a safe design on the tunnel lining. The minimum support pressure offered by the tunnel lining should be greater than or equal to the maximum normal stress imposed by the surrounding soil. Therefore, in the present study, the maximum normal stress is reported as the support pressure. The present study's objective is to perform a thorough investigation of the seismic stability of circular tunnels considering the effect of (i) soil

type–cohesive-frictional and granular soils, (ii) ground surcharge and anisotropy in friction angle for granular soils, (iii) interaction between top and bottom tunnels in piggyback configuration, and (iv) heterogeneity in wave propagation velocities. The results presented in this thesis include the variation of support pressure in the dimensionless frequency-time space, a complete parametric study with a meta-analysis on determining the influence of each problem parameter, region of soil collapse, horizontal and vertical stress contours, and normal stress distribution around the tunnel periphery. The results were provided as dimensionless charts to be used by practicing engineers to readily compute the support pressure and use them to find the necessary lining thickness to prevent tunnel failure due to a seismic event.

8.2 Conclusions from the present study

Following are the conclusions based on various works carried out in the present study:

- In general, the support pressure increases with an increase in the horizontal acceleration coefficient, k_h , and a decrease in soil friction angle, ϕ , and damping ratio. The effect of k_h on tunnel support pressure reduces with the tunnel cover depth-to-diameter ratio, C/D . The region of soil collapse, horizontal and vertical stress contours, and normal stress distribution around the tunnel periphery is symmetric about the vertical through tunnel center static loadings, and skewed towards the direction of seismic horizontal acceleration in tunnel's vicinity.
- Most of the results have been obtained using a non-zero vertical acceleration coefficient, $k_v = k_h/2$, where k_h is the horizontal acceleration coefficient. The consideration of a non-trivial k_v ensures the inclusion of the effect of vertical seismic acceleration generated due to primary wave propagation on the support pressure.

- The vertical stress contours revealed the phenomenon of soil arching based on the increased magnitude of stress transferred from the yielding to the non-yielding zone.

For tunnels placed in cohesive-frictional soils:

- The effect of soil unit weight, γ , tunnel diameter, D , and soil cohesion, c , was considered using $\gamma D/c$. An increase in $\gamma D/c$ can be inferred as a decrease in soil cohesion for given values of γ and D .
- The normalized support pressure, σ_s/c , is primarily affected by shear waves for a higher value of $\gamma D/c$ (lower cohesion) and primary waves for a lower value of $\gamma D/c$ (higher cohesion), for any value of soil friction angle.
- Soil friction angle has a higher influence on σ_s/c for lower values of $\gamma D/c$ (higher cohesion), because the change in friction angle for soils with higher cohesion changes its behavior from being nearly cohesive to cohesive-frictional. The opposite is true for a higher $\gamma D/c$ (lower cohesion) because the material behavior is more or less frictional for any friction angle value.
- Out of all other problem parameters, $\gamma D/c$ had the highest influence on tunnel support pressure. The effect of $\gamma D/c$ is higher for a higher friction angle because the material behavior changes from being nearly frictional to cohesive-frictional. This is an extensive change in soil behavior, which reflects in the support pressure, compared to that in soils with a lower friction angle where the frictional resistance is low.
- The effect of the horizontal acceleration coefficient, k_h , on the support pressure is less for tunnels placed in cohesive-frictional soils with a higher magnitude of cohesion.

- When the soil friction angle is low and cohesion is high, the normal stress distribution tends to be uniform around the tunnel periphery as the cover depth increases. This uniform tending nature decreases with the horizontal acceleration coefficient, k_h , and soil friction angle, and vanishes for a higher value of $\gamma D/c$.
- The region of soil collapse around tunnels increases with $\gamma D/c$, and reduces with ϕ . The effect of soil arching is higher for a higher magnitude of soil friction angle considering a given value of soil cohesion.
- The normal stress distribution around the tunnel periphery for tunnels in $c - \phi$ soils revealed that the location of the maximum normal stress is dependent on the tunnel cover depth and soil friction angle, and independent of $\gamma D/c$. The maximum normal stress occurred near the crown for tunnels placed in soils with a lower friction angle at a lower cover depth. On the other hand, for a higher cover depth, the maximum normal stress occurred near the tunnel springline. Contrary to the above, for a higher ϕ value, the maximum normal stress occurred near the springline for any cover depth.

For tunnels placed in anisotropic granular soils with ground surcharge:

- The equivalent soil friction angle, ϕ , is defined using the anisotropy ratio, m , and maximum friction angle, ϕ_1 . The equivalent friction angle increases with an increase in the value of ϕ_1 and/or m .
- The normalized support pressure, $\sigma_s/\gamma D$, is predominantly affected by shear waves, for any tunnel cover depth, when ϕ is low. On the other hand, for tunnels placed in soils with a higher equivalent friction angle, shear waves influence the support pressure when the tunnel is at a lower cover depth, and primary waves influence for relatively deeper tunnels.

- The magnitude of ground surcharge has negligible effect on the tunnel support pressure when $C/D > 3$, i.e., for relatively deeper tunnels as stresses redistribute such that no additional stress is transferred to the tunnel periphery. However, for $C/D \leq 3$, the influence of ground surcharge magnitude is higher for soils with a lower friction angle.
- The influence of anisotropy ratio, m , and maximum friction angle, ϕ_1 , is higher when their combination increases the magnitude of the equivalent friction angle, ϕ . An increase in ϕ increases the influence of soil arching, which changes the support pressure magnitude.
- The extent of soil collapse increased with a reduction in the equivalent friction angle (reduced m and/or ϕ_1), and an increase in the horizontal seismic acceleration coefficient. For tunnels placed at a larger cover depth, as the equivalent friction angle increases, the soil collapse is confined to tunnel's vicinity.
- The magnitude of vertical stress transferred to the adjoining non-yielding region is high for tunnels placed at a larger cover depth in soils with a higher equivalent friction angle.
- A comparative study for tunnels in granular and cohesive-frictional soils revealed that the influence of shear waves on the support pressure decreases and that of primary waves increases with the magnitude of soil cohesion.
- As the magnitude of soil cohesion increases, the collapse pattern tends to be symmetrical around the tunnel periphery, indicating the reduced influence of horizontal seismic acceleration. The influence of soil arching increases with soil cohesion as the amount of shear strength available for mobilization increases.

For piggyback dual circular tunnels in granular soils:

- The center-to-center separation distance between tunnels and soil friction angle play a major role in determining the seismic wave type that influences the support pressure. For any value of the separation distance, shear waves influence the stability of piggyback tunnels placed in soils with a low friction angle. On the other hand, for a higher friction angle, the influence of shear waves is more when tunnels are close to each other, whereas primary waves influence the most when tunnels are far apart.
- The influence of friction angle on the support pressure is higher for bottom tunnels than top, and this influence decreases with the separation distance between tunnels. Compared to the top tunnel, the support pressure of the bottom tunnel is less sensitive to the changes in the horizontal acceleration coefficient. Similarly, for both top and bottom tunnels, the support pressure is less sensitive to the horizontal acceleration coefficient for a large separation distance.
- For any value of tunnel cover depth, horizontal acceleration coefficient, and soil friction angle, there exists a critical value of the separation distance till which the support pressure for bottom tunnel is higher than the top, and it plummets thereafter. This is because the effect of overburden is prevalent till this critical distance beyond which the soil arching takes over.
- For tunnels placed close to each other, a unified collapse pattern forms indicating an increased interference effect. On the other hand, the collapse patterns become confined to the respective tunnel beyond a certain separation distance, which indicates an independent soil collapse due to reduced interference. This critical distance to initiate an independent soil collapse reduces with soil friction angle and increases with tunnel cover depth and horizontal acceleration coefficient.

- From the stress contours around piggyback tunnels, three zones of soil arching form above top and bottom tunnels. These have been identified as undisturbed, arch, and loosened zones over the top tunnel, similar to a single tunnel, and disturbed, arch, and loosened zones over the bottom tunnel.
- The magnitude of normal stress is significant near the invert and crown for top and bottom tunnels, respectively, when they are placed close to each other. As the separation distance increases, the interference decreases, and the normal stress magnitude drops around these regions.

For tunnels in granular soils with heterogeneous wave propagation velocities:

- The support pressure is most affected by shear waves for tunnels with a lower cover depth, whereas the primary wave influence is dominant, otherwise.
- For a given value of the dimensionless shear wave frequency, the normalized support pressure, $\sigma_s/\gamma D$, increases with an increase in the power parameter, n , and horizontal acceleration coefficient, k_h , and a decrease in soil friction angle, ϕ , and wave velocity ratio, V_0/V_H .
- Two values of dimensionless shear wave frequency, $\omega_s H/V_{sH}$, have been considered— 0.3π and 0.6π . The support pressure, for a given combination of V_0/V_H and n , increases when the selected frequency is closer to the corresponding fundamental frequency. Thus, $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.3\pi$ is critical for $V_0/V_H = 0.2$ and $n = 0.6$.
- The magnitude of $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.6\pi$ is critical for two cases— $V_0/V_H = 0.2$ and $n = 0.6$, and $V_0/V_H = 0.8$ and any n value. For $V_0/V_H = 0.2$ and $n = 0.6$, $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.6\pi$ is closer to the corresponding fundamental frequency of primary waves. This makes the support pressure surge for the above-said combination of input parameters, enunciating the need to include primary wave's effect in the analysis. Contrary

to the above, $\omega_s H/V_{sH} = 0.6\pi$ is critical for $V_0/V_H = 0.8$ because it is close to the fundamental frequency of shear waves. The effect of the power parameter, n , diminishes at $V_0/V_H = 0.8$.

- Given the values of V_0/V_H and $\omega_s H/V_{sH}$, the region of soil collapse increases with an increase in the power parameter, n . The change in horizontal acceleration's direction due to the change in $\omega_s H/V_{sH}$ is reflected in the collapse region's skew about the tunnel centerline.
- Because the selected frequencies are closer to the fundamental frequency for some combinations of V_0/V_H and n , a region of soil near the ground surface showed an outward movement at ultimate collapse. The extent of this region increased with the increase in wave velocity's heterogeneity (lower V_0/V_H and higher n) and a decrease in soil friction angle.

8.3 Scope for further work

Some of the future extensions to the present study are:

- The lower bound limit analysis considered in this study assumed the soil to follow the associated flow rule. The suggestions by Davis (1968) and Drescher and Detournay (1993) in finding the modified cohesion and friction angle from a known value of dilation angle can be implemented to find the tunnel support pressure for a non-associated medium.
- The current study assumed the tunnel to be placed in dry soil. In reality, the degree of saturation of the soil could vary between dry to fully saturated. Further research is needed to extend the present study considering the effect of excess pore pressure developed in such soil conditions because of seismic wave propagation.

- The earthquake waves traveling in a medium are hindered by the presence of structural elements. Thus, seismic soil-structure interaction effects on the stability of tunnels should be accounted for. In the present study, the tunnel lining has not been modeled explicitly. Hence, including the structural elements along with the soil elements shall be undertaken in the future to study the influence of soil-tunnel structure interaction on tunnel's stability.
- The anisotropy in the friction angle considered in this study is based on the empirical relation by Meyerhof (1978). Recently, Veiskarami and Shokoohi (2023) found the bearing capacity of surface footings on transverse isotropic granular soils using an iterative procedure with the *fabric tensor* concept, which can be extended to compute the support pressure for tunnels. Furthermore, the heterogeneity of soil shear strength parameters shall be accounted for in future studies.
- Similar to the anisotropy in soil's shear strength parameters, it is possible for shear and constrained moduli of soil to be anisotropic. Closed-form solutions of the spatiotemporal seismic accelerations in above soil conditions shall be developed and applied to study the seismic stability of tunnels. Moreover, in this thesis, the non-homogeneity in wave propagation velocities were considered using a generalized power-law variation. But there can be possibilities that some of the field data might not exactly fit into this mathematical function. Hence, solutions for such soil conditions need to be developed in the future.
- Soil parameters like the cohesion, friction angle, shear modulus, and damping ratio have been taken to be deterministic in this study. However, the uncertainty associated with the occurrence of these parameters in the field can be considered by considering the above parameters as random variables. Further, the uncertainty in the spatial distribution of these parameters can also be accounted for using random field analysis.

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